

GAPS

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Turkey Country Dossier

WP3: Return Migration Infrastructure in Turkey from Europe to Europe

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List of Abbreviations

ABR	Aegean Boat Report
AFAD	The Disaster and Emergency Management Authority
AI	Amnesty International
AIDA	Asylum Information Database
AKP	Justice and Development Party
ASAM	Association for Social Development and Aid Mobilisation (Former Association of Solidarity with Asylum Seekers and Migrants)
AVRR	Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration
CIS	Commonwealth of Independent States
ECCHR	The European Centre for Constitutional and Human Rights
ECRE	The European Council on Refugees and Exiles
EU	European Union
EUAA	European Union Agency for Asylum
EUTRA	EU-Turkey Readmission Agreement
EUTRS	EU-Turkey Statement
FSA	Free Syrian Army
GDS	General Directorate of Security
GÖKSEM	Irregular Migrant Pre-Admission and Referral Centres
HRW	Human Rights Watch
ICMPD	International Centre for Migration Policy Development
IDP	Internally Displaced Person
IHH	Foundation for Human Rights and Freedoms and Humanitarian Relief
IM	InfoMigrants
IOM	The International Organisation for Migration
IP	International Protection
IPA	The Instrument for Pre-Accession Assistance

JAP	Joint Action Plan
LEUs	Law Enforcement Units
LFIP	The Law on Foreigners and International Protection
MMP	Mobile Migration Points
MoFA	The Ministry of Foreign Affairs
MoI	The Ministry of Interior
MS	Member State
Mülteci-Der	Association for Solidarity with Refugees
N-AVRR	National Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration System
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OES	Operation Euphrates Shield
OOB	Operation Olive Branch
PDMM	The Provincial Directorate of Migration Management
PMM	The Presidency of Migration Management
RCs	Removal Centres
RMIs	Return Migration Infrastructures
RPTG	Readmission Protocol of Turkey and Greece
RRT	Refugee Rights Turkey
SNC	Syrian National Council
SOHR	Syrian Observatory for Human Rights
TAC	Temporary Accommodation Centre
TAF	Turkish Armed Forces
TCGC	Turkish Coast Guard Command
TCN	Third-country nationals
TİKA	Turkish Cooperation and Coordination Agency
TPR	The Temporary Protection Regulation

TRC	The Turkish Red Crescent
UNHCR	The United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
US	United States
USSR	The Union of Soviet Socialist Republics

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Executive Summary

This country dossier/report examines Turkey's return migration infrastructure (RMI), with a particular focus on pushforward strategies and readmissions under the EU-Turkey Statement (EUTRS, 2016). It specifically investigates return movements from Europe to Europe, analysing how Turkish authorities manage migrant mobility through indirect means in the grey area, including incentives for onward movement toward Greece and Bulgaria, as well as readmission agreements or similar political statements. The study highlights how pushforward practices intensified before and for a short period after the Pazarkule Events (2020), shaping border governance in Edirne and its surrounding regions, as well as readmission practices in Izmir from Europe as part of the EUTRS.

The findings in this report are based on desk research and multi-sited qualitative fieldwork conducted in key locations, including Edirne, Istanbul, Izmir, and Kırklareli, where various aspects of return migration are addressed. The research relies on semi-structured interviews with various return-related actors, including NGO representatives, legal practitioners, local authorities, human smugglers, and migrants, providing direct insights into the procedural, legal, and operational challenges of return migration governance.

The selection of entry points for research—Edirne and Kırklareli, along with their border villages—as a key transit hub reflects the geographic and institutional fragmentation of Turkey's migration control mechanisms. For the EUTRS, Izmir was also approached. Edirne serves as a critical location for analysing how migrants are directed toward Greece and Bulgaria, while Izmir emerges as the primary entry point for third-country nationals returned under the EUTRS.

The concept of pushforward, referring to the strategic facilitation of migrant movement toward Greece and Bulgaria, emerges as a defining feature of Turkey's border enforcement strategy. The statements of the interview respondents from the fieldwork indicate that Turkish authorities employ a combination of selective non-enforcement, indirect incentives, and logistical facilitation to encourage migrants to cross into the EU. During and after the Pazarkule Event (2020), Turkish security forces—particularly the gendarmerie and border police—were reported and claimed to have permitted, and in some cases actively facilitated, the movement of migrants toward the Greek and Bulgarian borders. This facilitation often involved coordinated transportation, relaxation of security patrols, and cooperation with local actors, including smugglers and transportation networks. The research also reveals that some local actors, including village authorities, played a key role in structuring pushforward practices, either by providing logistical support or withholding intervention in irregular crossings.

On the other hand, although the EU-Turkey Readmission Agreement (2013) was designed to facilitate the returns of third-country nationals and Turkish citizens from the EU to Turkey, it cannot be implemented, and due to the European Refugee Crisis in 2015, the EUTRS was accepted as a political statement by two sides. During its implementation from 2016 to 2020, the majority of returned individuals under EUTRS were transferred from Izmir-Dikili to the Pehlivan köy Removal Centre in Kırklareli, a location that serves as a key processing hub, reflecting an attempt to geographically manage and disperse returnees.

For both return types and the selected entry points, the geopolitical dimension of Turkey's return migration policies also plays a crucial role. The shift in Turkey's migration governance

post-2023 reflects a broader effort to reduce migrant visibility in urban centres, tighten border security, and expand return operations. Turkey's strategic use of pushforwards aligns with EU migration externalisation policies, reinforcing a system in which migrants are managed through informal deterrence rather than structured legal frameworks. However, the increasing reliance on smuggling networks and informal transportation mechanisms raises concerns about the long-term sustainability of this model, as irregular migration flows remain resilient despite intensified enforcement efforts.

Key Findings

1. Pushforward Practices and State-Facilitated Mobility Toward Greece and Bulgaria
 - In Edirne and Kırklareli, pushforwards have emerged as an alternative to formal return mechanisms, functioning as a strategy that indirectly forces migrants towards the EU borders.
 - Pushforward strategies in Edirne during the Pazarkule Event (2020) involve a mix of active facilitation and selective non-enforcement. Turkish security forces, particularly the gendarmerie and border police, were reported to escort or, at times, coordinate the movement of migrants toward the Greek and Bulgarian borders, particularly during and after the Pazarkule events.
 - The Pazarkule events of 2020 illustrate how Turkish authorities responded to Greek pushbacks by encouraging outward movement, creating a multi-actor return infrastructure that included state security forces, local smugglers, and village intermediaries.
 - Smuggling networks, local actors, and informal facilitators played a key role in the pushforward process, often with tacit state approval or indirect cooperation. There are claims that villagers, transport operators, and even certain security personnel have reportedly been involved in these dynamics, either by turning a blind eye or directly assisting with crossings.
2. The EUTRS Readmissions and Institutional Constraints
 - While the Presidency of Migration Management (PMM) in Ankara and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MoFA) formally oversee these returns, Provincial Directorates of Migration Management (PDMMs) have limited autonomy in managing the process. As a result, EUTRS readmissions operate within a largely opaque and highly centralised structure.
 - International organisations, such as UNHCR and IOM, are largely excluded from EUTRS implementation due to limitations in their mandates. However, they continue to provide humanitarian assistance and monitoring in other border-crossing and return contexts.
3. The Role of Istanbul as a Coordinating Hub for Returns and Pushforwards
 - Istanbul plays a central role in migration governance, both in terms of return processes and onward movement toward Europe.
 - The city serves as a transit hub for migrants seeking to enter the EU, often through organised networks that arrange transportation and logistical support for border crossings.
 - The tightening of migration policies post-2023 has led to an increase in administrative removals and efforts to reduce migrant visibility in Istanbul, further fuelling demand for irregular migration and smuggling services.
4. The Geopolitical and Policy Implications of Turkey's Return Migration Strategies
 - Turkey's return migration governance aligns with EU externalisation policies, reflecting a broader strategy of deterring settlement and encouraging onward movement rather than enforcing structured legal return mechanisms.

- The selective implementation of pushforward tactics and EUTRS readmissions highlights the discretionary nature of Turkey's migration enforcement system, where some migrants are informally encouraged to leave while others are detained and processed under readmission agreements.
- The increasing reliance on informal actors, smugglers, and transport networks in border governance raises serious questions about the sustainability of current enforcement approaches. While strict enforcement measures have been intensified, irregular migration flows remain resilient, adapting to new restrictions through evolving mobility patterns.

Policy Implications and Recommendations

- **Enhancing Transparency in Return Processes**
 - The lack of clear documentation, legal notifications, and procedural safeguards undermines the credibility of Turkey's return migration policies.
 - Improved data-sharing mechanisms between provincial and national authorities are needed to ensure accountability and oversight.
- **Addressing the Legal and Human Rights Gaps in Pushforwards**
 - Pushforward strategies blur the line between voluntary return and forced removal, raising concerns about compliance with international protection norms.
 - Ensuring access to asylum procedures and monitoring border enforcement practices is crucial to prevent human rights violations.
- **Re-evaluating the Functionality of the EU-Turkey Readmission Framework (EUTRA& EUTRS)**
 - The EUTRS has failed to establish a sustainable return mechanism, as readmission operations remain sporadic and politically selective.
 - A more structured, transparent, and rights-based approach is necessary to ensure procedural fairness and legal access for returnees.

In conclusion, this report highlights that Turkey's return migration infrastructure is shaped as much by informal, coercive mechanisms as by formal, legal agreements. Pushforward strategies in Edirne, particularly before and after the Pazarkule events, illustrate how migration governance is implemented through a combination of state-managed facilitation and discretionary law enforcement. The selective implementation of EUTRS readmissions, the fragmented institutional structure of migration control, and the coexistence of state and non-state actors in shaping return pathways all point to the need for greater transparency, oversight, and rights-based migration governance. Addressing these issues requires policy reforms that prioritise legal safeguards over reactive border enforcement measures, ensuring that return and readmission practices align with international human rights standards rather than ad hoc containment strategies.

Keywords: Return Migration Infrastructure, Pushback, Pushforward, EU-Turkey Readmission Agreement, the EU-Turkey Statement, Forced Return, Voluntary Return vs. Coerced Return

The GAPs Project

GAPs is a Horizon Europe project that aims to conduct a comprehensive multidisciplinary study on the drivers of return policies and the barriers and enablers of international cooperation on return migration. The project aims to examine the disconnects and discrepancies between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes by decentring the dominant, one-sided understanding of “return policy-making”. To this end, GAPs:

- Examines the shortcomings of the EU’s return governance;
- Analyses enablers and barriers to international cooperation and;
- Explores the perspectives of migrants themselves to understand their knowledge, aspirations and experiences with return policies.

GAPs combines its decentring approach with three innovative concepts:

- A focus on return migration infrastructures, which allows the project to analyse governance fissures;
- An analysis of return migration diplomacy to understand how relations between EU MSs and third countries hinder cooperation on return and;
- A trajectory approach that uses a socio-spatial and temporal lens to understand migrant agency.

GAPs is a three-year interdisciplinary project (2023–2026) coordinated by Uppsala University and the Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies with 17 partners in 12 countries on four continents. The 12 countries in which fieldwork has been conducted are Sweden, Nigeria, Germany, Morocco, the Netherlands, Afghanistan, Poland, Georgia, Turkey, Tunisia, Greece, and Iraq.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Explaining the GAPS Project and WP3

Return migration has become a policy priority worldwide, particularly in Europe. The GAPS project is a Horizon Europe project (2023-2026) that investigates the drivers of return policies and the potential disconnects between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes on the ground. It follows a de-centring approach to migration governance and seeks to move beyond a Eurocentric understanding of return policymaking. The consortium comprises 17 partners from 12 countries across four continents. This country dossier of Turkey is part of Work Package 3 of the GAPS project. This work package aims to study how return migration governance is *put into practice* through the concept of “Return Migration Infrastructures (RMIs),” focusing on the so-called “crucial meso-level.”¹ Following the infrastructural turn in migration studies (e.g. Xiang and Lindquist 2014)², the aim is to understand the relations and interactions between a wide variety of actors and their roles, their practices (“doings”), as well as the materialities and technologies that together shape – i.e. facilitate *or* undermine and contest – the daily operation of returns. In doing so, it examines how the aforementioned works together on multiple scales and creates complex realities on the ground through a range of practices.³ Moreover, WP3 investigates an axis of coercion that encompasses three types of RMIs: assisted returns, forced removals, and pushbacks, by moving beyond simplistic binaries of voluntariness versus forced returns.⁴ WP3 research was implemented in both the European Union (EU) and its member countries, particularly in Germany, Greece, the Netherlands, Poland, and Sweden, as well as in Georgia, Iraq, Morocco, Nigeria, Tunisia, and Turkey. The EU partner countries focus on RMIs returning people from the EU to either the EU, in the case of Dublin, or non-EU countries, while non-EU partners focus on RMIs receiving returnees from the EU.

1.2. Introducing the Country-Case

Turkey occupies a unique and strategic position in the context of return migration, serving as a major transit and destination country for migrants moving between Europe, Asia, and the Middle East. Turkey’s approach to return migration is shaped by its strategic partnership with the EU, its national policies, and the diverse nature of return practices, including pushbacks, forced returns, and voluntary returns. This layered approach reflects both the legal and ethical challenges of managing return migration in a context where Turkey is positioned as a gatekeeper to Europe.

In terms of geopolitics, the role of the EU and the Europe-to-Europe route is important. Turkey’s return migration infrastructure is significantly shaped by its bilateral and multilateral agreements

¹ Thomas Faist, “The crucial Meso Level” in *Selected Studies in International Migration and Immigrant Incorporation*, Marco Martiniello and Jan Rath (end.), 2010, Amsterdam, pp. 59-90.

² Biao Xiang and Johan Lindquist, “Migration infrastructure”, *International Migration Review*, 48(1_suppl), pp. 122-148.

³ Maria Koinova, et al., “It’s Ordered Chaos: What Really Makes Polycentrism Work” *International Studies Review*, 2021, Vol. 23, Issue 4, pp. 1988–2018.

⁴ Zeynep Sahin-Mencutek and Anna Triandafyllidou, “Coerced return: formal policies, informal practices and migrants’ navigation” *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 2024, pp. 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369183X.2024.2371209> (Accessed 4 April 2025).

with the EU, most notably the EU-Turkey Readmission Agreement (EUTRA, 2013)⁵ and the EU-Turkey Statement (EUTRS, 2016)⁶. This Statement was established to control irregular migration flows into Europe by enabling the return of irregular migrants from Greece to Turkey. Under this arrangement, Turkey agreed to accept these returns, a process that has placed significant responsibility on Turkish authorities to handle return logistics, reintegration, and border management. Turkey's role as a return destination has intensified as the country has committed to strengthening its borders and implementing readmission agreements, especially in light of increasing EU pressure to control irregular migration into Europe. The country case for Turkey reflects a complex migration management system in which legal stratification, temporality, and external pressures converge. Turkey's role as a host country and buffer zone for Europe complicates the nature of returns. The EU's financial and political influence remains pivotal in shaping Turkey's return policies, although internal challenges, such as the aftermath of the 2023 earthquakes⁷, economic crises, and rising anti-migrant sentiment, continue to affect the implementation of these policies.

Turkey's approach to return migration policy involves several key elements, encompassing legal frameworks, international cooperation, and specific programmes aimed at facilitating the return of migrants to their countries of origin.

In terms of the legal framework, Turkey enforces return migration through a legal and regulatory framework aligned with national laws and international agreements. The Law on Foreigners and International Protection (LFIP, 2013)⁸ is a cornerstone, setting out the procedures and conditions for returning foreigners in Turkey who are found to be staying irregularly or may not qualify for international protection. The LFIP outlines procedures for deportation, voluntary return, and the rights and obligations of migrants and refugees within Turkish territory. This legal framework is also in alignment with international law, standards, and obligations, which include adherence to the principles of non-refoulement, human rights considerations, and the dignity and safety of migrants throughout the return process.

Regarding international cooperation, Turkey has entered into readmission agreements with several countries and the EU. In addition, Turkey has a bilateral agreement-like political document, the EUTRS (2016), which has articles related to return and readmission. Turkey also collaborates with international organisations, such as the International Organisation for Migration (IOM), the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), and the International Centre for Migration Policy Development (ICMPD) to ensure the humane and orderly return of migrants.

⁵ EU/ EUR-Lex, "Agreement between the European Union and the Republic of Turkey on the readmission of persons residing without authorisation", *Official Journal of the European Union*, L 134/3, 7 May 2014. Available at: [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:22014A0507\(01\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:22014A0507(01)) (Accessed 4 October 2024).

⁶ European Council, "EU-Turkey Statement", 2016, Available at: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2016/03/18/eu-turkey-statement/> (Accessed 4 April 2025).

⁷ Umutcan Yüksel, "Impact of 2023 Earthquakes on Return Dynamics of Syrian Migrants in Türkiye: Observations from the Field", *GAPs Project*, 10 June 2024, Available at: <https://www.returnmigration.eu/gapsblog/impact-of-2023-earthquakes-on-return-dynamics-of-syrian-migrants-turkiye> (Accessed 4 April 2025).

⁸ The Law on Foreigners and International Protection (#6458), Available at: <https://en.goc.gov.tr/kurumlar/en.goc/Ingilizce-kanun/Law-on-Foreigners-and-International-Protection.pdf> (Accessed 1 May 2025).

Concerning specific programmes, the Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration Programme (AVRR) with IOM and the National Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration Programme (N-AVRR) with ICMPD are important for facilitating voluntary, safe, and dignified returns for migrants who wish to return to their countries of origin, often including support for reintegration efforts.

Based on Turkey’s legal framework and practical applications, three types of returns are observed: pushbacks, forced returns and voluntary (assisted or spontaneous) returns. Regarding the pushbacks, the Turkey-Greece sea and land borders, as well as the Turkey-Bulgaria land border, are critical on the west. The Turkey-Iran and Turkey-Syria land borders represent the eastern and southern borders, respectively. Considering the regional focus of this report, in terms of types, referring to the grey area of return policy, pushbacks – often characterised by their extra-legal nature – are a contentious form of return that has been documented at Turkey’s borders with Greece and Bulgaria. These pushbacks frequently occur without formal legal proceedings or individualized assessments, leading to allegations of human rights violations. Human rights organizations such as the Aegean Boat Report (ABR), Amnesty International (AI), the Asylum Information Database (AIDA), the European Centre for Constitutional and Human Rights (ECCHR), the European Council on Refugees and Exile (ECRE), the Human Rights Watch (HRW), InfoMigrants (IM)⁹ have raised concerns about the legality and ethicality of pushbacks, obligations of the related countries under international refugee and human rights laws. In terms of pushback, the aforementioned NGOs and their reports claim that Greece and Bulgaria primarily employ pushback practices at the EU’s borders. But this research shows that Turkey has been responding to pushbacks (in particular during the Pazarkule Events in 2020 and after) with the “pushforwards” that can be described as the practice of a country facilitating or directing the movement of migrants toward the borders of another state, often as a response to pushbacks

⁹ Aegean Boat Report (ABR), “Aegean Boat Report Annual Report 2024”, 2024, Available at: <https://aegeanboatreport.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/ABR-Annual-Report-2024-1.pdf>; ABR, “Aegean Boat Report Annual Report 2023”, 2023, Available at: <https://aegeanboatreport.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/ABR-Annual-Report-2023.pdf>; Amnesty International (AI), “Greece: Violence, lies, and Pushbacks”, 2021, Available at: <https://www.amnesty.org/en/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/EUR2543072021ENGLISH.pdf>; Asylum Information Database (AIDA), “Access to the territory and push backs”, 24 August 2024, Available at: <https://asylumineurope.org/reports/country/turkiye/asylum-procedure/access-procedure-and-registration/access-territory-and-push-backs/>; European Centre for Constitutional and Human Rights (ECCHR), “Analyzing Greek Pushbacks: Over 20 Years of Concealed State Policy Without Accountability”, 2021, Available at: https://www.ecchr.eu/fileadmin/Publikationen/ecchr_analysis_greek_pushback_practice.pdf; European Council on Refugees and Exile (ECRE), “Push backs and human rights violations at Bulgarian and Greek borders with Turkey”, 2 March 2018, Available at: <https://ecre.org/push-backs-and-human-rights-violations-at-bulgarian-and-greek-borders-with-turkey/>; ECRE, “Balkan Route: Continued Concerns About Migrant Pushbacks from Bulgaria to Türkiye”, 7 June 2024, Available at: <https://ecre.org/balkan-route-continued-concerns-about-migrant-pushbacks-from-bulgaria-to-turkiye-%E2%80%95-ngos-blame-hungarys-migration-policy-for-boosting-smuggling-networks-%E2%80%95-eu-set-to-sign-front/>; Human Rights Watch (HRW), “Bulgaria: Migrants Brutally Pushed Back at Turkish Border”, 26 May 2022, Available at: <https://www.hrw.org/news/2022/05/26/bulgaria-migrants-brutally-pushed-back-turkish-border>; InfoMigrants (IM), “Exclusive: Why are migrant pushbacks from Bulgaria to Turkey soaring?”, 30 August 2023, Available at: <https://www.infomigrants.net/en/post/51259/exclusive-why-are-migrant-pushbacks-from-bulgaria-to-turkey-soaring>; IM, “ECTHR finds Greece’s border ‘pushbacks’ illegal in landmark ruling”. 8 January 2025, Available at: <https://www.infomigrants.net/en/post/62120/ecthr-finds-greeces-border-pushbacks-illegal-in-landmark-ruling> (Accessed 3 May 2025).

conducted by neighbouring countries.¹⁰ However, in eastern Turkey, there are claims regarding Afghans' pushbacks, with a notable increase in such incidents since 2022.¹¹

In terms of forced returns, administrative detention for return, deportation, and readmission agreements exist, but Turkey also has readmission agreements and similar political collaboration pacts, such as the EUTRS (2016). Turkey also engages in forced returns as part of its migration management strategy, often under the framework of deportation (used as "removal" in the Turkish legal framework). Forced returns typically involve the return of migrants and asylum seekers to their countries of origin or third countries without their explicit consent. The LFIP (2013) outlines procedures for deportation but has faced criticism for lacking adequate protections for vulnerable groups, especially in cases involving Syrians under temporary protection. Forced returns are frequently conducted in collaboration with the EU and neighbouring countries, as Turkey seeks to align its practices with the broader European agenda of reducing irregular migration.¹² However, in addition to these international cooperations in which the EU is predominantly involved, it is also evident that Turkey has significantly institutionalised its national mechanism in line with its own needs.¹³

Voluntary returns represent the third major type of return migration in Turkey's infrastructure, facilitated through incentives and assistance programmes. Turkey, with support from international organisations such as the IOM, has established a reintegration assistance programme (AVRR) aimed at promoting voluntary return as an alternative to forced repatriation since 2009.¹⁴ This was followed by the N-AVRR with the ICMPD in 2019.¹⁵ However, the line between forced and voluntary returns is often blurred, especially given the challenging conditions for migrants in Turkey, where limited access to rights and resources can coerce individuals into "voluntarily" returning to their home countries.¹⁶ These dynamics illustrate the complex and often conditional nature of voluntary returns in Turkey's migration governance landscape. Finally, there are also "spontaneous returns", although not highly representative, that are not supported and are based on individual decisions. A primary legal framework exists for both forced returns and assisted voluntary returns.

In terms of return-related general figures, Turkey hosts one of the largest refugee populations globally, hosting over 2.8 million Syrian refugees under temporary protection (TP) as of 27

¹⁰ N. Ela Gokalp Aras, "The Politics of Care and Control: Governmentality in Turkey's Evolving Border Policy with the Reflections from Turkey-EU Borders", *Journal of borderland Studies*, 2024. DOI: 10.1080/08865655.2024.2428636.

¹¹ AIDA, "Cessation of Temporary Protection", 20 August 2024, Available at: <https://asylumineurope.org/reports/country/turkiye/temporary-protection-regime/qualification-temporary-protection/cessation-temporary-protection/> (3 May 2025).

¹² N. Ela Gokalp Aras and Zeynep Şahin Mencütek, "Evaluation of Irregular Migration Governance in Turkey from a Foreign Policy Perspective". *New Perspectives on Turkey*, 2018, No. 59, p. 63.

¹³ N. Ela Gokalp Aras, et. al. *Ibid.*, 2025.

¹⁴ IOM, "Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration", 2024, Available at: <https://turkiye.iom.int/assisted-voluntary-return-and-reintegration#:~:text=The%20AVRR%20programme%20facilitates%20the.return%20and%20rebuild%20their%20lives> (Accessed 2 June 2025).

¹⁵ ICMPD, "N-AVRR: Supporting the Implementation and further Strengthening of Türkiye's National Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration System", 2021, Available at: <https://www.icmpd.org/news/launching-project-on-supporting-turkey-s-national-assisted-voluntary-return-reintegration-system> (Accessed 4 May 2025).

¹⁶ Şebnem K. Akçapar and Doğuş Şimşek, "The politics of Syrian refugees in Turkey: A question of inclusion and exclusion through citizenship", *Social Inclusion*, 2018, Vol. 6, Issue 1, pp. 176–187.

February 2025.¹⁷ Another group of foreigners are international protection (IP) holders. According to the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), there were 219,000 refugees and asylum seekers in Turkey as of 2025.¹⁸ According to the latest news interview with Minister of Interior Ali Yerlikaya, 215,579 IP holders from countries including Iraq, Afghanistan, Iran and Ukraine constitute another group of foreign nationals.¹⁹ In 2024, 9,009 asylum seekers applied for IP, representing a 52% decrease compared to the previous year, when 19,007 asylum seekers applied for IP.

Regarding the legal framework, return types and practices also differ significantly between the different nationalities. For example, Syrians fall under the TP regime, which does not allow specific and explicit safeguards against deportation. However, the effect of the non-refoulement principle is evident in individuals under TP in terms of deportation to their country of origin (Syria), as the very reason for these individuals to be protected under the TP is closely related to this principle. However, Syrians face pressures to return voluntarily, exacerbated by socio-economic difficulties and uncertainty surrounding their status. As representing the major nationality among the non-Syrian population, Afghans, on the other hand, are typically classified as irregular migrants, facing forced deportations and pushbacks, particularly at Turkey's eastern border with Iran. Afghans often do not have the same legal protections as Syrians, resulting in a precarious status and swift deportations.

In terms of return-related figures for these two important nationalities, for Syrians, there is a blurred line between voluntary and forced return. These returns, however, raise concerns about their voluntariness due to economic pressures and the limited long-term integration options available in Turkey. However, due to recent developments in Syria since 8 December 2024, there has been a surge in voluntary returns to Syria, illustrating how evolving political realities in origin countries can influence return trends.²⁰ Voluntary returns from Turkey since 2017 have reached 792,625 by January 2025. Since 8 December 2024, over the past month, 52,622 Syrians have returned to their homeland in a voluntary, safe, and dignified manner.²¹

On the other hand, Afghans face a much different scenario, with increased deportations in 2023, reaching a 146% increase compared to 2022.²² The deportation process is swift and often conducted without sufficient legal procedures.²³ Afghans face pushbacks, forced returns, and

¹⁷ PMM, "Temporary Protection", 27 February 2025, Available at: <https://en.goc.gov.tr/temporary-protection27> (Accessed 7 March 2025).

¹⁸ UNHCR, "Türkiye", 2025. Available at: <https://reporting.unhcr.org/operational/operations/t%C3%BCrkiye#:~:text=T%C3%BCrkiye%20has%20been%20the%20largest,protection%20applicants%20and%20status%2Dholders>. (Accessed 2 February 2025).

¹⁹ Ibid.

²⁰ Umutcan Yüksel and N. Ela Gökalg Aras, "Preliminary Reflections on Post-Assad Syria: Emerging Dynamics and the Complex Reality of Refugee Returns from Türkiye", *GAPs Project*, 23 December 2024, Available at: <https://www.returnmigration.eu/gapsblog/preliminary-reflections-on-post-assad-syria> (Accessed 24 June 2025).

²¹ PMM, "Geri Dönüş". 12 January 2025, Available at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/icisleri-bakani-ali-yerlikaya-bir-ayda-52-bin-622-suriyeli-gonullu-guvenli-onurlu-ve-duzenli-geri-donus-yapt-merkezicerik> (Accessed 12 March 2025).

²² TRT Haber, "Sınır dışı edilen düzensiz göçmen sayısı 21 bin 211'e ulaştı", 13 March 2023. Available at: <https://www.trthaber.com/haber/gundem/sinir-disi-edilen-duzensiz-gocmen-sayisi-21-bin-211e-ulasti-752711.html> (Accessed 7 June 2025).

²³ AIDA, Ibid., 3 May 2025.

assisted voluntary returns, with a significant increase in pushbacks since 2022.²⁴ Afghans are the top nationality of persons apprehended after an irregular border crossing, representing 27% of the total apprehensions²⁵; however, Syrians were the second-highest nationality among the irregular arrivals, with 58,621.²⁶

In general, Turkey's approach to return migration is shaped by a complex interplay of legal, political, and socio-economic factors, resulting in differential treatment of specific nationalities. This stratified approach is evident not only in entry procedures and legal statuses but also in return policies, particularly for Syrian and Afghan migrants, who have the highest numbers in the country. The differentiated approach of Turkey's migration policies is immediately apparent in the reception and legal statuses granted to different nationalities. Turkey's territorial access policies have also evolved differently for these two groups. Turkey's return migration policies are shaped by a combination of domestic priorities and international cooperation, aiming to manage return migration in a way that respects the rights of migrants while meeting the country's regulatory and security needs. These policies are subject to ongoing evaluation and adaptation, reflecting changes in migration flows, international agreements, and the broader geopolitical context.

2. Methods

2.1 General methodological framework of WP3

The WP3 research, which spanned from June 2023 to June 2024, consisted of two main tasks. First, an overview of RMIs in each partner country was created by producing flow maps through desk research. Desk research involved studying reports, policy briefs, informative leaflets, data reports, newsletters, and websites, among other sources, on the implementation of returns by involved actors and/or observers, following an examination of the legal framework on return migration.²⁷ Desk research and the flow maps produced are structured around i) the actors involved, ii) their doings, and iii) the materials and technologies used. Second, the WP3 research focused on the selection of a particular RMI type (assisted returns, forced removal, and pushbacks) as a case study. In Turkey, pushbacks, pushforwards, and forced returns were chosen in the context of the EUTRS. The research started from a specific "entry point" on the ground related to the everyday workings of the RMI selected. It included the implementation of 21 interviews in each country (for Turkey, 33 in total) with actors involved at the meso-level of the everyday operation of the return procedure, which may both facilitate and contest return operations. All interviewees were provided with an information letter, and consent was obtained

²⁴ Ibid.

²⁵ The apparent contradiction—Afghans being both the largest group of IP applicants and irregular migrants—stems from two factors: irregular entry (many Afghans arrive irregularly due to limited legal pathways) and rejections and status loss (while some apply for IP to regularize their status, high rejection rates push many backs into irregularity). Thus, Afghan irregularity results both from initial unauthorized entry and failed asylum claims, reflecting structural barriers in Turkey's asylum system.

²⁶ AIDA, Ibid., 3 May 2025.

²⁷ Neva Övünç Öztürk, Gökalp Aras, N. E., Yüksel, U. and Ünay, H. (forthcoming, 2025). "Legal and Policy Infrastructures of Returns in Turkey. WP2 Country Dossier" in *GAPs: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond*.

from the participants in the research. Partners were also encouraged to conduct ethnographic observations during the interviews or on other suitable occasions on a voluntary basis.

2.2 Specific conditions of data collection and analysis of the case study

This research adopts a qualitative approach to analyse Turkey's return and readmission policies, with a specific focus on Europe-to-Europe and, in this regard, pushbacks and returns as a part of the EUTRS. Combining desk research with document analysis and multi-sited ethnographic research in Edirne and Izmir provides a comprehensive understanding. By integrating multiple data sources and perspectives, the methodology ensures a robust analysis that captures the legal and practical dimensions of the return processes, as reflected in both macro- and meso-level analyses. The methodology integrates comprehensive desk research with multi-sited fieldwork across several key locations in Turkey.

For the desk research component, data are generated through document analysis. The desk research component involved an extensive review of relevant documents, policies, and literature, with a particular focus on pushbacks and the impact of readmission agreements, specifically the EUTRA and the EUTRS. The analysed documents cover the two types of returns in Turkey and were selected for analysis, including government reports, legal documents, reports from non-governmental organisations (NGOs), academic articles, and media publications.

The research is designed as a multi-sited ethnography, which allows for the examination of pushbacks and pushforwards within different local contexts. As part of this ethnographic research, the primary data collection method involved in-depth interviews at the meso-level, along with participant observations. The research was conducted in five cities (Ankara, Edirne, İzmir, İstanbul and Kırklareli) between January and May 2024. However, in particular, Edirne, Izmir, and Kırklareli were the focus of this report. These cities were chosen due to their strategic importance in the context of migration and return practices in Turkey. İzmir and Edirne are crucial transit points for migrants attempting to reach Greece, Bulgaria, and the EU. İzmir, located on Turkey's Aegean coast, is one of the closest cities to Greek islands, making it a popular departure point for sea crossings to Europe. Izmir is significant not only as a major hub for migration but also because it hosts Dikili, the only location where the EUTRS (2016) is actively implemented. This initiative was established to manage and limit irregular migration flows into Europe. Under this framework, migrants arriving in Greece who do not qualify for asylum are returned to Turkey, and Dikili serves as the primary reception point for these returns. As a result, Dikili has become a focal point for the operationalisation of Turkey's return migration infrastructure, symbolising Turkey's role as both a transit and buffer zone for Europe.

Edirne, situated near the Greek and Bulgarian borders along the Meriç River, is a primary entry point for migrants trying to cross into the EU. Its proximity to these borders has made it a focal point for migration, particularly during crises such as the 2015-2016 surge and the events of early 2020, resulting in heightened tensions and increased security measures in the area. Edirne has long been a crucial land border crossing point, comparable to Izmir in terms of its significance for migration routes. However, it gained even greater importance following the 2020 Pazarkule Events. During this period, large numbers of migrants gathered at the Pazarkule border gate after Turkey announced it would no longer prevent their passage to Europe, resulting in a tense standoff and highlighting the border's strategic significance. This incident brought Edirne into

the international spotlight as a focal point of migration, highlighting the complexities of border management in the region.

Additionally, due to the increase in pushbacks along traditional routes, migration flows have shifted towards Kırklareli, making it another critical area in terms of migration dynamics. This shift has been partly driven by intensified enforcement and pushback practices, leading migrants to seek alternative, less monitored crossing points. As a result, Kırklareli has become increasingly significant within the broader migration route as migrants adapt to the evolving challenges at the borders. Ankara, Turkey's capital, is the political and administrative centre where key policies are developed and implemented. Ankara hosts the headquarters of many vital actors. Ankara and Istanbul host the headquarters or important offices of key institutional actors, and Istanbul is also a significant transit hub.

In total, 33 semi-structured meso-level interviews (Ankara: 4, Edirne: 14, Istanbul: 3, Izmir: 9, Kırklareli: 3) were conducted with key informants and non-state actors, including government officials, NGO representatives, legal experts, and community leaders. In addition, interviews with supranational organisations, intergovernmental organisations, and NGOs from Ankara and Istanbul provided valuable insights into the economic and social benefits that Turkey derives from Europe and vice versa. Additionally, observation visits were conducted to 14 border villages and other key border-crossing points. Finally, two focused group meetings were held in January 2024, with over 20 participants, including legal experts, practitioners, and scholars from the selected cities. A second meeting was held in May 2024 with representatives from Syrian and Afghan NGOs. These focus groups facilitated detailed discussions on returns, administrative detention issues, and appeal processes, providing the perspectives of the concerned populations. The insights gained from this meeting were instrumental in understanding the broader legal and practical challenges associated with return policies.

The data analysis of the interviews, conducted through transcriptions, was performed using NVivo 14 software, ensuring a systematic and rigorous analysis. Also, the data analysis is based on the use of thematic coding and interpretation of field notes, interviews, and observations.

Research has been subject to ethical review by the host institutions of the individual researchers conducting the country-specific research. The ethics committee approval for the research was granted by Özyeğin University, which conducted the Turkey-based studies of the GAPs Project in collaboration with the Swedish Research Institute.²⁸ The Ethics Committee Decision was obtained on 26 April 2023, with approval code "2023/07/07." Regarding the interviews, oral consent is obtained from respondents, and their anonymity and untraceability are ensured.

One significant limitation of this study is the inability to conduct interviews with state actors up until the time of writing. Despite extensive efforts, the securitised and centralised nature of the state apparatus has posed challenges to accessing these actors for interviews. This lack of direct engagement with state representatives remains a notable gap in the research.

²⁸ Since the Swedish Research Institute is headquartered in Stockholm, it was jointly decided that the ethics committee approval from the said university would be necessary and sufficient for the research to be conducted in Turkey.

3. Context

3.1. Context of migration (Outmigration/ mainly to Europe due to the focus of the report)

Turkey's migration profile has evolved dramatically over the past few decades, positioning it as a complex nexus of migration dynamics in the region. Historically known primarily as a source country, Turkey saw millions of its citizens migrate to Western Europe for labour opportunities in the mid-20th century, with lasting impacts on both Turkey and its diaspora communities in Europe. In recent years, however, Turkey has transitioned into a destination, transit, and continued source country for diverse migration flows, reflecting regional crises, economic shifts, and changing geopolitical landscapes. The multi-layered migration profile highlights Turkey's unique position and its significant influence on migration patterns in Europe, underscoring the need for comprehensive policies that address its role as both a source, destination, and transit country within the broader migration landscape. The historical milestones regarding the outmigration from Turkey to Europe can be contextualised in different distinct periods.

The first period refers to the early migration and Population Exchange (1923-1960s), marked by the 1923 Turkey-Greece Population Exchange, which resulted in the expulsion of at least 1.3 million Greeks from Turkey and some 500,000 Muslims from Greece.²⁹

The second period refers to the labour migration to Western Europe (1960s-1980s). Turkey's significant wave of outmigration began in the 1960s, primarily due to labour migration to Western Europe, and Turkey signed numerous labour recruitment agreements with several Western European countries.³⁰ After Turkey signed the first labour recruitment agreement with Germany in 1961, Turkey became a significant labour supplier. Between 1961 and 1974, approximately 800,000 Turkish workers emigrated to Europe.³¹ However, after labour recruitment ended in the 1970s, migration continued through family reunification, with many Turkish migrants bringing their families to Europe in subsequent years.

The third period refers to the political migration and asylum Seekers (1980s-1990s). Following Turkey's 1980 military coup, political persecution led to a surge in asylum applications in Europe. Conflicts in southeastern Turkey, particularly involving the Kurdish population, led to further increases in asylum applications, with Europe remaining the main destination. In the

²⁹ Martin Baldwin-Edwards, "Migration between Greece and Turkey: From the Exchange of Populations to the Non-recognition of Borders", *Journal for Labour and Social Affairs in Eastern Europe*, 2006, Vol. 9, No. 3, Borderland 2: Greece, Bulgaria and Turkey, pp. 115-122.

³⁰ Germany (1961), the United Kingdom (1961 but less comprehensive agreement), Austria (1964), the Netherlands (1964), Belgium (1964), and France (1965), Sweden (1967), Australia (1967), Switzerland (1971), Denmark (1973), Norway (1981) [Erhard Franz (2011). *Population Policy in Turkey*, Hamburg, Deutsches Orient-Institut, 1994, pp. 5-16.]

³¹ Ahmet İçduygu, "50 Years After the Labour Recruitment Agreement with Germany: The Consequences of Emigration for Turkey." *Perceptions*, Summer 2012, Volume XVII, Number 2, pp. 11-36. For further information: Ahmet Akgündüz, *Labour Migration from Turkey to Western Europe- 1960-1974*, 2006, Amsterdam, University of Amsterdam; Nermin Abadan-Unat, *Turks in Europe: From Guest Worker to Transnational Citizen*, New York, Berghahn Books, 2011.

1980s, Turkey was the major country of origin, with 243,000 applicants.³² Between 1980 and 1995, approximately 400,000 asylum seekers from Turkey applied to Western Europe.³³ The 1973 oil crisis led to a decrease in state-led labour migration in Western Europe. During the 1980s and 1990s, Turkey experienced significant emigration to other regions and countries, including the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) and Arab states. In relation to Turkey's transit country role, starting from the 1980s, the country experienced an influx of refugees and irregular transit migrants, particularly from the Middle East as well as from Africa and Asia. In light of these developments, Turkey's transit role gained attention in the 1990s by the EU. By 1997, estimates suggested that around 10,000 to 15,000 irregular migrants from or through Turkey attempted to reach Europe annually.³⁴

The fourth period refers to the economic migration and skilled migration (1990s-2000s). In terms of outmigration, the 1990s and early 2000s saw emigration driven by financial instability and high unemployment, especially during Turkey's 2001 economic crisis. However, in general, during the 2000s, emigration and asylum from Turkey to Europe slowed considerably, as did return migration for many of the early migrants to Europe who had migrated in the 1960s and 1970s.³⁵ Starting in the 1990s, Turkey's relationship with the EU and its prospects for EU membership also influenced migration flows, as visa and work opportunities were expanded for Turkish citizens in some European countries. The EU dimension officially began in Turkey with the Helsinki Summit of the European Council in December 1999, and it has been evolving dynamically since then. The primary issue in EU-Turkey relations regarding migration and mobility has consistently been the irregular transit migration of third-country nationals through Turkey en route to Europe, which has prompted Turkey's return and readmission policy.³⁶

The fifth period can be categorised as the 2000s-present, marked by numerous highly fragmented developments regarding outmigration from Turkey to Europe. Despite the changing profile of emigration, in the late 2000s, for the first time, "the number of people emigrating from Turkey to Europe was less than the number of people, Turkish or foreigners, immigrating from Europe or returning to Turkey".³⁷ Additionally, there was a considerable decline in asylum applications in the early 2000s, with an annual figure of around 15,000; by 2010, this figure had dropped to less than 8,000.³⁸

In the late 2000s and early 2010s, Turkey experienced increased political tensions due to economic downturns and rising inflation, prompting Turkish nationals to seek stability and economic security, particularly after the 2013 Gezi Park protests.³⁹ This led to a gradual rise in

³² UNHCR Geneva, "Asylum Applications in Industrialized Countries: 1980 – 1999", 2001. Available at: <https://www.unhcr.org/statistics/STATISTICS/3c3eb4of4.pdf> (Accessed 4 June 2025).

³³ Ahmet İçduygu, *Ibid.*, 2012, p. 17.

³⁴ Kemal Kirişçi, "Turkey: A Transformation from Emigration to Immigration", *Migration Policy Institute*, 2003. Available at: <https://www.migrationpolicy.org/article/turkey-transformation-emigration-immigration> (Accessed 17 June 2025).

³⁵ Ahmet İçduygu, *Ibid.*, 2012, p. 18.

³⁶ Elif Çetin, et al., "Turkey – Country Report Legal & Policy Framework of Migration Governance", *Respond Project*, 2018. Available at: <https://www.respondmigration.com/wp-blog/2018/8/1/comparative-report-legal-and-policy-framework-of-migration-governance-pclyw-ydmzj-bzdbn-sc548-ncfcp> (Accessed 4 May 2025).

³⁷ Ahmet İçduygu, "International Migration and Turkey", *2010 OECD SOPEMI Report*, Istanbul, 2010.

³⁸ Ahmet İçduygu and Kemal Kirişçi, *Land of Diverse Migrations: Challenges of Emigration and Immigration In Turkey*, Istanbul Bilgi University Press, 2009.

³⁹ The Gezi Park protests began in May 2013 as a reaction to the Taksim Project, a development plan that proposed removing Gezi Park in Istanbul. What started as a local environmental protest quickly evolved

Turkish citizens seeking asylum in European countries. Also, after the coup attempt in 2016⁴⁰, asylum applications surged, with over 100,000 Turkish citizens seeking asylum in European countries between 2016 and 2020.⁴¹ Also, an OECD Report showed an increase in skilled migration from Turkey to Europe in the 2010s.⁴²

Considering the 2015 European Refugee Crisis and subsequent developments, the Syrian mass migration in 2011 was also a significant development in this period. While Turkey became a major destination for refugees, political and economic uncertainties within Turkey itself also contributed to rising outmigration. In 2015-16, outmigration from Turkey to Europe, particularly irregular migration, surged to unprecedented levels due to the Syrian refugee crisis and regional instability. In 2015 alone, over 861,630 individuals crossed from Turkey to Greece via the Aegean Sea and the land border, marking one of the largest movements of people from Turkey to Europe in recent history.⁴³ The following year, 2016, saw a significant drop in irregular crossings after the EU-Turkey Statement was implemented in March. This resulted in a decrease in numbers, with approximately 177,234 sea and land arrivals recorded for that year.⁴⁴

During the 2020s, economic instability, high inflation, and currency devaluation since 2018 have intensified outmigration from Turkey, particularly among young, educated individuals seeking better job opportunities and stability. Also, according to Eurostat, in 2022 alone, approximately 50,000 Turkish citizens applied for asylum in the EU, with Germany and the Netherlands as top destinations.⁴⁵ Additionally, around 60,000 Turkish citizens obtained EU residence permits primarily for employment and family reunification.⁴⁶

The post-2021 increase in Afghan arrivals to Turkey is particularly significant, as Afghans represent a substantial proportion of both irregular migration and asylum applications. This rise reflects Turkey's critical role as a transit country in relation to outmigration. Following the Taliban's return to power in Afghanistan, the outflow of Afghans has intensified, positioning Turkey as a key point in migratory routes due to its geographic proximity.

The recent economic crisis and the 2023 earthquake have amplified outmigration pressures from Turkey to Europe, driving both regular and irregular migration flows. Economic instability, characterised by high inflation and currency devaluation, has eroded purchasing power, particularly for young and skilled workers, who are now seeking better opportunities abroad. The earthquake added to these pressures, displacing millions in southeastern Turkey and pushing many to migrate internally or toward Europe due to lost livelihoods and infrastructure.

into a larger movement, uniting thousands of people who gathered to express their opposition to the Government's policies.

⁴⁰ On 15 July 2016, a faction within the Turkish Armed Forces, organized an attempted a coup d'état against the Government and the state institutions.

⁴¹ European Union Agency for Asylum (EUAA), "EU received over 1.1 million asylum applications in 2023", 28 February 2024. Available at: <https://euaa.europa.eu/news-events/eu-received-over-1-million-asylum-applications-2023> (Accessed 19 June 2025).

⁴² OECD, "Migration Outlook Migration Trends and Policies. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development", 2015.

⁴³ UNHCR, "Europe Arrivals", 10 November 2024. Available at: <https://data.unhcr.org/en/situations/europe-sea-arrivals/location/24489> (Accessed 12 March 2025).

⁴⁴ Ibid.

⁴⁵ Eurostat, "Asylum applications: Annual statistics", 2023. Available https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Asylum_applications_-_annual_statistics (Accessed 19 June 2025).

⁴⁶ Ibid.

Additionally, Turkey's emphasis on return policies for migrants, mainly Syrians, has created a sense of insecurity, leading some refugees and residents to consider irregular routes to Europe. For example, in Turkey, both international and temporary protection beneficiaries are legally required to reside in the province assigned to them by the Presidency of Migration Management (PMM). Leaving the assigned province without official permission may result in being considered irregular, leading to administrative sanctions or even detention (LFIP, Articles 71 and 77, and TPR, Articles 33 and 35). Unauthorised movement outside the assigned province may result in exclusion from services, administrative detention, or removal procedures. European border agencies have noted a recent uptick in irregular crossings and asylum applications from Turkey, underscoring how intertwined economic and environmental crises are driving new migration dynamics across the region. However, we have not yet been able to quantify these changes. We can only observe the increase in irregular crossings from Turkey and the rise in asylum applications since 2018.

Briefly, Turkey's outmigration patterns over the past 25 years reflect a complex interplay of economic, political, and social drivers, with periods of economic instability, political repression, and regional conflict each influencing migration trends. Outmigration has become more diversified, with skilled migration, family reunification, and asylum-seeking now comprising significant portions of Turkish emigrants abroad. Considering the focus of the WP3 Report, we analysed the available data since 2014, with a specific focus on the last decade. As **Figure 1** displays, enforcement patterns reveal an interesting trend: while the number of illegal presences increased dramatically, the proportion of those ordered to leave and those who actually returned remained relatively stable. They reflect that the initial period (2014-2017) showed relatively stable numbers of illegal presence in the EU, averaging around 10,000 annually. A notable shift occurred between 2018 and 2019, when the number of undocumented individuals doubled to over 20,000. This coincided with Turkey's economic crisis and increased political pressure on opposition groups. The COVID-19 pandemic temporarily reduced numbers in 2020, but by 2021, the upward trend resumed. The most dramatic surge occurred in 2022-2023, with cases of illegal presence skyrocketing. The migrant profile has diversified significantly, expanding beyond traditional political dissidents to encompass a range of social groups and economic migrants. Early estimates from the European Border and Coast Guard Agency (Frontex) suggest that around 380,000 unauthorised border crossings happened at the EU's external borders in 2023, primarily via the Mediterranean route. This figure represents the highest level recorded since 2016 and reflects a 17 per cent rise compared to 2022, highlighting a steady increase over the past three years.

Figure 1: Turkish Nationals Found to be Present Illegally- Ordered to Leave- Returned in the EU (2014-2024)

Source: Prepared based on the Eurostat ([migr_eipre](#), [migr_eiord](#), [migr_eirtn](#)) data by the authors.

Figure 2: Turkish National Returnees to Turkey by Return Type (2021-2024)

Source: Prepared based on the Eurostat ([migr_eirtn1](#)) data by the authors.

Figure 3: Comparison - Annual Returns to Third Countries vs. Quarterly Returns to Turkey

Source: Prepared based on the Eurostat ([migr_eirtn](#) & [migr_eirtn1](#)) data by the authors.

Regarding **Figures 1, 2, and 3**, the Eurostat datasets⁴⁷ reveal a complex picture of migration enforcement concerning Turkish nationals in the EU from 2014 to 2024. The data tracks three distinct but related phenomena: Turkish nationals found to be illegally present in EU territory, those formally ordered to leave, and those who were actually returned following such orders. The dramatic surge in all three categories, particularly from 2022 onwards, reflects broader political and economic developments in Turkey, including economic instability, political pressures, and increased emigration among Turkish citizens. The sharp increase in undocumented presence, from 46,545 in 2022 to 83,520 in 2023, represents a 79% jump, suggesting significant changes in migration patterns. Notably, the return rate (comparing those ordered to leave versus those actually returned) has improved over time, from approximately 27% in 2016 to 31% in 2024; however, this still means that the majority of deportation orders are not executed.

The EUTRA, signed in December 2013 and entering into force on 1 October 2014, was designed to facilitate the return of irregular migrants between the EU and Turkey. However, the provisions specifically related to the readmission of Turkish nationals only became applicable from the agreement's inception, while the provisions for third-country nationals were delayed until

⁴⁷ A critical limitation of the Eurostat data is the inability to distinguish between returns conducted specifically under the EU-Turkey readmission agreement and those executed through other legal frameworks, such as bilateral agreements between individual EU member states and Turkey, or standard deportation procedures. The datasets capture all returns of Turkish nationals, regardless of the legal mechanism used. Furthermore, the discrepancy between annual data showing returns to "third countries" and quarterly data showing returns specifically to Turkey reveals another complexity: not all Turkish nationals are returned to Turkey. In 2024, for instance, while 7,910 Turkish nationals were returned to third countries, only 3,055 were confirmed as having been specifically returned to Turkey. This gap suggests that some Turkish nationals may be returned to other countries where they have residence rights or through which they transited. Without specific coding in the Eurostat system to identify readmission agreement cases, researchers cannot isolate the agreement's direct impact from broader migration enforcement trends, making it impossible to evaluate the agreement's specific effectiveness in comparison to general deportation efforts.

October 2017. The timing is crucial for understanding the data: returns of Turkish nationals begin appearing in the statistics from 2016, with 1,815 returns, gradually increasing to 7,910 by 2024. This increase coincides with both the full implementation of the agreement and Turkey's deteriorating economic conditions, which have prompted a rise in emigration. The agreement was tied to visa liberalisation promises for Turkish citizens, which have not materialised, leading Turkey to announce the suspension of certain provisions in July 2019; however, returns have paradoxically continued to increase.

Figure 4: Turkish Asylum Applicants in the EU (2014-2024)

Source: European Union Agency for Asylum (EUAA), “Latest Asylum Trends 2024 - Annual Analysis”, 3 March 2025. Available at: <https://public.flourish.studio/visualisation/21463544/> (Accessed 12 March 2025).

Figure 4 reflects an increase in asylum applications by Turkish nationals in the EU from individuals travelling through or originating from Turkey. The high number of unauthorized crossings at the EU’s external borders could indicate that more people, including those from Turkey or passing through Turkey, are attempting to enter the EU due to various push factors, such as political or economic instability in the region, conflicts in nearby countries, or limited legal migration pathways. In the last three years, the numbers have doubled each year compared to the previous one. This indicates a sharp upward trend, suggesting that factors driving migration have intensified significantly during this period.

3.2. Historical Overview of the Development of Return Migration Infrastructures in Turkey

Over the past decade, shifting public sentiments, economic pressures, and evolving political dynamics have intensified the discourse on migrant return, contributing to the development of both formal and informal return infrastructures. In Turkey, the most significant populations under temporary and international protection are Syrians and Afghans. Therefore, it is essential

to prioritise an examination of relevant parameters from a return perspective for these groups⁴⁸ while also acknowledging the presence of other nationalities.

3.2.1. Social Dynamics and Public Sentiment

A 2024 Ipsos study for the UNHCR revealed that Turkey has the highest rate of anti-refugee sentiment among 52 surveyed countries, with 77% of respondents supporting completely closing the country's borders to refugees.⁴⁹ Moreover, 70% of the Turkish public believes that refugees are not fleeing war but seeking a more comfortable life.⁵⁰ In particular, the most recent Syrian Barometer (2023) by Murat Erdoğan examines Turkish public perceptions toward Syrians and finds a growing desire within the host population for the return of Syrian refugees. Economic difficulties, such as rising inflation and unemployment, have intensified this sentiment, with many Turkish citizens viewing Syrians as a burden on public resources and the labour market. The Barometer 2023 indicates that while Turkish society was initially sympathetic to Syrians, the prolonged presence of a large refugee population—combined with economic hardship—has shifted public opinion toward a stronger preference for return policies. Finally, regarding Afghans, following the Taliban's return to power in 2021, Turkey experienced a notable rise in Afghan arrivals, which has been politicised and instrumentalised within domestic policies. Unlike Syrian refugees, Afghan migrants have faced less humanitarian acceptance and were rather deemed as irregular migrants without proper consideration of international protection.⁵¹ In general, Afghan refugees in Turkey are often perceived through a lens of negativity, with frequent public discourse portraying them as security risks, economic burdens, or cultural threats.⁵²

3.2.2. Economic Pressures and Strain on Resources

Economic difficulties often exacerbate the perception of immigrants as a threat to the public, and immigrants are frequently viewed as the cause of crises.⁵³ The economic crisis in Turkey, marked by high inflation and rising living costs, has amplified the perception of migrants as economic burdens. The COVID-19 pandemic exacerbated these pressures, leading to widespread job losses among migrants and increased financial insecurity. As economic challenges mount, public frustration and resentment toward migrants have grown, further reinforcing calls for restrictive migration policies and return programmes. Due to Turkey's economic challenges, including inflation and unemployment, refugees and migrants are often scapegoated as contributing to these difficulties, intensifying the demand for return policies.⁵⁴

⁴⁸ As a part of the GAPs Project under Work Package 4 (Return Migration Governance in the African and Middle Eastern Regions and the Role of the EU), the returns of Syrians and Afghans were analysed in details, in particular focusing on forced and voluntary returns as well as pushbacks. See N. Ela Gökalp Aras, Umutcan Yüksel and Hakan Ünay, "Return Migration from Turkey to Syria and Afghanistan", WP4 Country Report in *GAPs Project*, 2025. DOI :

⁴⁹ Ipsos, "Global Attitudes to Refugees: A 52-Country Survey from Ipsos and UNHCR", 18 June 2024, Available at: <https://www.ipsos.com/en/unhcr-ipsos-survey-shows-enduring-public-support-refugees-alongside-stark-variations-attitudes> (Accessed 30 May 2025).

⁵⁰ Ibid., 2024.

⁵¹ Shaddin Almasri, "Why is Syria a War but Not Afghanistan? Nationality-based Aid and Protection in Turkey's Syria Refugee Response," *Refugee Survey Quarterly*, Volume 42, Issue 1, March 2023, Pages 29–54, <https://doi.org/10.1093/rsq/hdaco28> (Accessed 18 May 2025).

⁵² Özden Melis Uluğ, et al., "Attitudes Towards Afghan Refugees and Immigrants in Turkey: A Twitter Analysis", *Current Research in Ecological and Social Psychology*, Vol. 5, 2023, Article 100145.

⁵³ Boris Heizmann and Nora Huth, "Economic conditions and perceptions of immigrants as an economic threat in Europe: Temporal dynamics and mediating processes", 2021, *International Journal of Comparative Sociology*, 62(1), pp. 56-82.

⁵⁴ Murat Erdoğan, Ibid., 2023.

The 2023 earthquakes in southeastern Turkey placed additional strain on the nation's migration infrastructure. The disaster displaced around 1.7 million Syrians in affected regions, leading to severe living conditions in temporary accommodations, with issues related to hygiene, safety, and limited access to services.⁵⁵ According to the surveys, the most important issue on the agenda of the Turkish people is the problems in the economy, followed by the "refugee problem".⁵⁶ In recent years, Turkey has faced an economic crisis, and inflation has become a significant factor affecting people's daily lives. Economic difficulties often exacerbate the perception of immigrants as a threat to the public, and immigrants are frequently viewed as the cause of crises.⁵⁷

3.2.3. Political Shifts and Policy Developments

Political rhetoric, especially before the 2023 general elections, has increasingly focused on return, with opposition parties pushing for stricter policies.⁵⁸ Since 2022, there has been a noticeable rise in anti-migrant sentiment, with increased discussions during the election campaign in the 2023 General Election centring on issues such as voluntary return, unwanted immigrants, and border protection.⁵⁹ Domestic political rhetoric, particularly around the 2023 general elections, further amplified the focus on return.⁶⁰ In the lead-up to general elections in spring 2023, opposition politicians have made speeches that fuel anti-refugee sentiment and suggest that Syrians should be returned to war-torn Syria⁶¹. As a reaction to rising anti-refugee sentiment stoked by opposition parties and the society calling for the return of Syrians to war-torn Syria, President Erdoğan has promised to relocate at least 1 million Syrians to Turkish-controlled regions of northern Syria.⁶²

After the 2019 municipal elections and during the 2023 general elections, the issue of migrant presence became a prominent topic in politicians' speeches and commitments. After the May 2023 general elections, the implementation of security-focused migration policies was exemplified by the introduction of mobile migration points and Kalkan (Shield) operations.⁶³ In February 2024, Minister of Interior Ali Yerlikaya outlined a four-pronged approach to address irregular migration.⁶⁴ Regarding the return, neither in terms of policy nor statistics is official data

⁵⁵ UNHCR, "A Year after Türkiye-Syria quakes, UNHCR Warns of Rising Humanitarian Needs", 2024, Available at: <https://www.unhcr.org/news/briefing-notes/year-after-tuerkiye-syria-quakes-unhcr-warns-rising-humanitarian-needs> (Accessed 12 March 2025).

⁵⁶ Mustafa Aydın, et al., "Kantitatif Araştırma Raporu: Türkiye Siyasal Sosyal Eğilimler Araştırması 2022", 2023, İstanbul, Global Akademi ve Akademetre.

⁵⁷ Boris Heizmann and Nora Huth, *Ibid.*, 2021.

⁵⁸ N. Ela Gökalp Aras, Umutcan Yüksel, and Hakan Ünay, "Migration & Return Rhetoric in Türkiye's General & Presidential 2023 Elections: Navigating the Controversial Terrain of Return Migration", *GAPs Project*, 2023. Available at: <https://www.returnmigration.eu/gapsblog/turkiyes-2023-elections-navigating-the-controversial-terrain-of-return-migration?rq=election> (Accessed 12 March 2025).

⁵⁹ AIDA, "2023 Update AIDA Country Report: Türkiye", 8 August 2024, Available at: <https://ecre.org/aida-country-report-on-turkiye-2023-update/> (Accessed 30 May 2025).

⁶⁰ N. Ela Gökalp Aras, Umutcan Yüksel, and Hakan Ünay, *Ibid.*, 2023.

⁶¹ Soner Cagaptay, "Growing Anti-Syrian Sentiment in Turkey", *The Washington Institute for Near East Policy*, 2019, Available at: <https://www.washingtoninstitute.org/policy-analysis/growing-anti-syrian-sentiment-turkey> (Accessed 18 May 2025).

⁶² Presidency of Turkey Republic, "Cumhurbaşkanı Erdoğan'ın, İdlib Briket Evleri açılışına gönderdiği video mesaj", 2022, Available at: <https://x.com/tcbestepe/status/1521429496355819520> (Accessed 18 May 2025).

⁶³ AIDA, *Ibid.*, 8 August 2025.

⁶⁴ PMM, "İçişleri Bakanımız Sayın Ali Yerlikaya Düzensiz Göçle Mücadelede 4 Strateji Uyguladığını İfade Etti", 2024, available at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/kurumlar/goc.gov.tr/GOC-TV/2024/3-Mart/01->

available; however, public official statements, particularly the lengthy presentations by the MoI, have become an important source for tracing official policies on return and are intensively used for this report.

In terms of political aspects, the EU's critical role as a political driving force in shaping Turkey's return migration policies should also be mentioned. The EUTRS (2016) positioned Turkey as a gatekeeper, significantly reducing irregular arrivals to Europe, particularly Greece, while providing Turkey with financial aid and political incentives in exchange for managing the returns of migrants not eligible for asylum in the EU.

3.2.4. Institutional and Legal Frameworks

Turkey's legal and institutional frameworks, primarily under the LFIP (2013), have been essential in managing the migration landscape. The restructuring of the Directorate General of Migration Management (DGMM) into the PMM reflects Turkey's commitment to a comprehensive migration policy (DGMM, 2013). These frameworks regulate refugees' stay, movement, and return, although they have inadvertently contributed to social tensions and integration challenges by limiting refugees' mobility and access to public resources.

The development of Turkey's return migration infrastructure has been shaped by a comprehensive legal and institutional framework aimed at addressing the growing complexities associated with irregular migration and asylum management. As the legal foundation, the LFIP (2013) provides the legal basis for Turkey's migration governance, enabling Turkey to regulate the deportation, voluntary return, and rights of migrants. This legislation forms the core of Turkey's approach to managing foreign nationals, integrating frameworks for the protection and control of migration while emphasising the significance of addressing irregular migration.

As the institutional component, the PMM was established as part of a restructuring initiative. The PMM centralises migration governance in Turkey. Working in collaboration with international bodies such as IOM, UNHCR, and ICMPD, the PMM administers return programs, manages technical assistance for reintegration, and coordinates legal frameworks with a focus on maintaining adherence to international standards of refugee protection. Additionally, the removal centres and Temporary Accommodation centres are crucial components of the institutional framework.

There are also operational tools and programmes. For example, Mobile Migration Points (MMPs) were introduced in 2023, serving as decentralised units equipped with advanced fingerprinting and identification technology. These mobile units, deployed across 81 provinces, allow the PMM to conduct on-the-spot checks, identification, and referrals of irregular migrants to Removal Centres and Irregular Migrant Reception and Referral Centres (GÖKSEM). GÖKSEMs are part of the infrastructure supporting returns, as facilitating the processing and deportation of migrants found without documentation. These centres work in conjunction with MMPs, ensuring efficient handling of identified irregular migrants within Turkey's administrative framework for return. According to official reports, between July 19, 2023, and September 20, 2024, 1,581,027 migrants underwent these security checks, of whom 138,356 were reportedly irregular migrants.⁶⁵

[Mart/İçişleri Bakanımız Sn. Ali Yerlikaya-Duzensiz-Gocle-Mucadelede-4-Strateji-Uygulandigini-Ifade-Etti.mp4](#) (Accessed 22 May 2025).

⁶⁵ A Haber, "İçişleri Bakanı Ali Yerlikaya'dan A Haber'e Özel Açıklamalar", 26 September 2024, Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vvCTLLDWJxQ> (Accessed 30 May 2025).

International cooperation is also important because various readmission agreements with multiple countries have bolstered Turkey's return migration infrastructure. The EUTRS (2016) emphasises cooperation with the EU on migration management, particularly regarding Syrian refugees, and has played a crucial role in Turkey's efforts to align with international migration standards.

Briefly, Turkey's return migration infrastructure is a product of intersecting social, economic, and political factors, with each domain shaping policies and public sentiment regarding migration and return. Social tensions, economic pressures, and political rhetoric have fuelled a feedback loop in which public and political demands reinforce each other, prompting a shift toward increasingly restrictive migration policies. Turkey's legal, institutional, and physical infrastructures, from return centres to regulatory frameworks, reflect its evolving migration approach and its complex role within regional migration dynamics. A combination of historical migration trends, regional conflicts, international agreements, and domestic pressures has driven the development of return migration infrastructures in Turkey. The Syrian refugee crisis, the EUTRS, and domestic political discourse have all contributed to shaping Turkey's return migration policies. Today, Turkey's return migration infrastructure includes temporary accommodation centres, removal centres, legal frameworks, and partnerships with the EU, underscoring the country's evolving role in regional and international migration governance.

3.3. Return migration: Trends and Figures

Turkey's role as a central hub in the migratory routes between the Middle East, Asia, and Europe has brought complex dynamics to its return migration landscape, especially concerning returns from Turkey to Europe. Since this report focuses on returns from Europe to Turkey and Turkey to Europe, it will analyse forced returns in relation to readmission under the EUTRA (2013). However, due to the limited implementation of this agreement, the primary focus will be on the EUTRS (2016), which was actively enforced between 2016 and 2020.

Additionally, the report addresses return migration practices that constitute a "grey area", with a particular emphasis on returns from Europe to Europe, identified as one of the most significant types of returns. To ensure clarity, this analysis distinguishes between sea and land borders, as each presents unique dynamics and challenges. While statistical data on these practices remains extremely limited, the report adopts a holistic approach to integrating all relevant and accessible statistics. This includes data related to irregular migration and border crossings, with a specific focus on pushback and pushforward practices. By situating these dynamics within the broader context of Turkey and its associated borders, the report aims to enhance understanding of these complex and controversial return practices.

As already mentioned, Turkey is the largest refugee-hosting country worldwide, as the number of people forcibly displaced across the world due to conflict, violence and persecution hit record levels. Turkey currently hosts some 2.8 million registered Syrian refugees⁶⁶, along with close to 222,000 persons of concern from other nationalities.⁶⁷ **Figure 5** reflects the situation since 2015.

⁶⁶ PMM, *Ibid.*, 27 February 2025.

⁶⁷ UNHCR, *Ibid.*, 2025.

Following the 2021 peak in the number of Syrians, there has been a steady decline over the last three years, which is also the case for non-Syrian international protection beneficiaries.

Figure 5: Number of Migrants under Temporary Protection and International Protection (2015-2024)

Source: Prepared by the authors based on PMM, “Temporary Protection”, 12 December 2024, Available at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/gecici-koruma5638> (Accessed 12 June 2025); UNHCR, “Refugee Data Finder”, 2024, Available at: <https://www.unhcr.org/refugee-statistics/download/?url=1M1Dak> (Accessed 3 May 2025).

Figure 6 illustrates that between 2005 and 2024, the number of captured irregular migrants increased gradually, reflecting the growing migratory pressures in the region. A sharp rise is evident between 2015 and 2019, with the figure peaking at 454,662 in 2019, followed by declines in subsequent years. This peak can be explained by the escalation of conflicts in neighbouring regions, particularly in Syria, Afghanistan, and Iraq, which likely contributed to the increased migration flows. The EUTRS's (2016) mid-term impact was that it aimed to curb irregular migration through the Aegean, but it shifted pressure to land and other sea routes, thereby increasing irregular crossings.

Figure 6: Number of Irregular Migrants (2005-2024)

Source: PMM, “Irregular Migration”, 16 January 2025. Available at: <https://en.goc.gov.tr/irregular-migration> (Accessed 16 January 2025).

Figure 7 illustrates the national breakdown of irregular migrants captured in Turkey from 2014 to 2024. Irregular migration from Syria peaked in 2016 (74,842) but has seen a steady decline since, stabilising at around 40,000 annually in recent years. However, despite the significant decrease after the EUTRS, which can also be attributed to increased border security and enforcement, 2019 marks a peak year across most nationalities, with notable increases for Afghans, Syrians, and other groups, such as Iranians and Iraqis. Most nationalities saw a sharp decline in 2020, coinciding with the COVID-19 pandemic, which restricted global mobility.

Figure 7: Distribution of Irregular Migrants by Citizenship by Year (2014-2024)

Source: PMM, “Irregular Migration”, 16 January 2025. Available at: <https://en.goc.gov.tr/irregular-migration> (Accessed 16 January 2025).

As reflected by **Figure 7**, Syrians and Afghans represent the largest groups in Turkey, both in terms of individuals under international and temporary protection and as irregular migrants. Considering specific arrangements, such as the EUTRS, which predominantly address Syrians, it is particularly valuable to focus on these two nationalities in detail.

It is not possible to access official figures regarding return decisions, deportation numbers, or the number of rejected asylum seekers in Turkey. However, based on information primarily compiled from presentations made by the Minister of Interior on television channels, it is possible to present figures on deportations, particularly since 2020. **Figure 8** is also based on official statements and reflects these publicly shared statistics, showing that deportations rose consistently from 43,658 in 2020 to 130,609 in 2023.

Figure 8: Number of Deportations (2020-2024)

Source: The authors prepared the official data from the Minister of Interior’s statements.⁶⁸

⁶⁸ A Haber, “İçişleri Bakanı Ali Yerlikaya’dan A Haber’e Özel Açıklamalar”, A Haber Youtube Channel, 2025. Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vvCTLIDWJxQ> (Accessed 12 March 2025).

As this report centres on pushbacks, pushforwards, and forced returns under the EUTRS, the following section will focus on the relevant and available statistics related to these practices.

3.3.1. Pushbacks from Greece

The unofficial and concealed nature of Greece’s pushback practice makes it challenging to estimate the total number of pushbacks executed; however, reporting indicates that Greek pushbacks have affected thousands to tens of thousands of individuals each year. According to the 2025 Aegean Boat Report (ABR), 3,312 boats carrying 90,702 people were pushed back from Greek islands into Turkish waters between 2020 and 2024. The annual breakdown of Aegean Boat Report’s push-back records is provided in **Figure 9**.

Figure 9: Pushbacks from Greece to Turkey (2020-2024)

Source: Prepared by the authors based on the Aegean Boat Report Data.⁶⁹

The ECCHR’s report⁷⁰ on pushbacks by Greece provides some estimates of the scale of pushbacks over the years. The collected data on pushbacks and interdictions at Greece’s borders highlights a consistent and significant trend of increasing activity over time, with notable variations in the scale and documentation of incidents. For example, in the 2008–2017 period, initial pushbacks were documented. The 2021–2023 period refers to the Numbers with Systematic Documentation. However, a significant discrepancy emerged between reports (While Greece’s Minister of Shipping stated 29,000 refugees and migrants were rescued by the Coast Guard, the Minister of Immigration and Asylum reported fewer than 9,000 entries, indicating large-scale pushbacks.

⁶⁹ See ABR, “Aegean Boat Report Data Studio”, 2025. Available at: https://lookerstudio.google.com/u/o/reporting/1CiKR1_R7-1UbMHKhZzE_Ji_cvqF7xlfH/page/A5Q0 (Accessed 12 March 2025).

⁷⁰ ECCHR, *Ibid.*, 2021, pp. 5-6.

Pushback practices have escalated both in scale and systematic organisation, shifting from smaller-scale incidents prior to 2013 to large-scale operations by 2020.

However, based on figures from various reports by ECCHR, ABR, and others, the trend is characterised by an increasing use of both land and sea pushbacks, which is intensifying political and human rights scrutiny. Greece's reported rescue numbers and migrant entry figures often show unexplained discrepancies, reflecting the covert nature of many operations. The documented data demonstrates the sustained and growing scale of pushbacks, with increasingly systematic efforts to prevent entry into Greece and the EU.

The Turkish Coast Guard Command (TCGC)⁷¹ has been reporting and sharing incidents of pushbacks by Greece and Bulgaria in a publicly accessible manner since 2020. Over the span of 5 years, there were a total of 110 pushback incidents involving 3,147 pushed-back migrants. A total of 81 pushback incidents occurred, involving 2,335 migrants who were pushed back in 2024. It is possible to access both the official case files and, if available, photos and videos through public access.

3.3.2. Turkish Coast Guard Operations

Examining the data on the TCGC's irregular migration from 2017 to 2024, we observe significant fluctuations in both migration patterns and enforcement responses in the Eastern Mediterranean. The Turkish Coast Guard's operations peaked in 2019, with 60,600 people stopped or rescued, followed by a sharp decline during the COVID-19 pandemic (20,356 in 2020) before increasing again to 56,954 in 2023. Meanwhile, deaths at sea haven't correlated directly with the volume of TCG operations - the highest death toll was recorded in 2018 (93 deaths) when TCG stopped/rescued 26,678 people, while 2023 saw only 20 deaths despite TCG operations involving 56,954 people.

Comparing TCG operations with pushback data reveals an interesting pattern: TCG stops/rescues consistently outnumber reported pushbacks, typically at a ratio of about 1:2 or higher. For instance, in 2023, while there were 25,855 pushbacks, TCG stopped or rescued 56,954 people. This gap widened further in 2024, with 13,083 pushbacks compared to 45,766 TCG operations, suggesting intensified maritime enforcement activities. Despite increased interventions, the persistence of fatalities (averaging around 35 deaths annually since 2020) indicates ongoing humanitarian challenges in the region.

⁷¹ TCGC

Figure 10: Deaths (red) and Stopped/ Rescued (Blue) by the Turkish Coast Guard (2017-2024)

Source: Prepared by the authors based on the Turkish Coast Guard.⁷²

3.3.3. Arrivals to Greece

As shown in **Figure 11**, sea arrivals to Greece from Turkey exhibit significant fluctuations over the past decade. After unprecedented numbers in 2015, with arrivals during the Syrian refugee crisis, figures dropped sharply in 2016 following the EUTRS. The period between 2017 and 2019 showed relatively stable numbers, but they dropped significantly in 2020 due to COVID-19 restrictions. Recent years show a gradual increase, while land arrivals present a different pattern, with initial low numbers in 2014-2015 before peaking in 2018. Following this peak, land arrivals have stabilised in recent years. This trend occurs against the backdrop of increasing pushbacks and intensified TCG operations (56,954 stops/rescues in 2023).

Meanwhile, returns under the EUTRS have declined in 2020, with returns suspended after March 2020 due to the pandemic. The relationship between arrivals, pushbacks, and the TCG operations adds another layer of complexity. While TCG operations have remained substantial (56,954 stops and rescues in 2023), the number of arrivals has also increased significantly. This suggests that despite intensified maritime enforcement, with TCG operations consistently outnumbering both arrivals and pushbacks, migration pressure remains high. The humanitarian cost of these dynamics is evident in the death toll, which reached 799 in 2023, matching the peak levels of 2015 despite enhanced enforcement measures.

⁷² Ibid, 2025.

Figure 11: Number of Sea and Land Arrivals, Deaths and Missing in Greece (2014-2024)

Source: Prepared by the authors based on both the UNHCR Europe Sea Arrivals Dashboard and the Aegean Boat Report.⁷³

⁷³ UNHCR Operational Data Portal, “Europe Sea Arrivals / Greece”, 2025. Available at: <https://data.unhcr.org/en/situations/europe-sea-arrivals/location/24489> (Accessed 12 March 2025); ABR, Ibid., 2025.

3.3.4. Returns from Greece to Turkey

Figure 12 shows that returns from Greece to Turkey under the EUTRS have demonstrated a consistent downward trend since their implementation in March 2016. Since March 2020, returns have been suspended due to the COVID-19 pandemic, with Turkey refusing to receive refugees from Greece. By 2022, a total of 2,140 people had been returned from Greece to Turkey under the deal, a notably low figure compared to the initial expectations of the agreement. This limited implementation of returns stands in stark contrast to the growing number of TCG operations and reported pushbacks. Furthermore, while returns have remained suspended, approximately 32,472 Syrian refugees have been resettled from Turkey to EU Member States under the agreement's "one-for-one" mechanism.

Figure 12: Returns from Greece to Turkey as a part of the EU-Turkey Statement (2016-2020)

Source: Prepared by the authors based on the UNHCR.⁷⁴

4. Return Migration Infrastructures in Turkey

Turkey's position as a key actor in migration governance is shaped by its geographical location and its role as a host and transit country for millions of migrants and refugees, particularly from Syria and Afghanistan. The dynamics of return migration, which is defined as “the movement of persons returning to their country of origin after having moved away from their place of habitual residence and crossed an international border”,⁷⁵ in Turkey encompass three main types of returns: forced returns, voluntary returns, and pushbacks, in line also with the conceptual framework of the GAPs Project.⁷⁶ These types highlight the complexities of

⁷⁴ UNHCR, “Returns from Greece to Turkey (under EU-Turkey statement) as of 31 March 2020”, Available at: <https://data.unhcr.org/en/documents/details/75075> (Accessed 17 February 2025).

⁷⁵ IOM, “Glossary on Migration”, 2019, p. 86. Available at: https://publications.iom.int/system/files/pdf/iml_34_glossary.pdf (Accessed 12 March 2025).

⁷⁶ Zeynep Sahin-Mencütek, et al., “Framework paper on the concepts and typologies on returns, combined with four conceptual notes” in *Global Migration: Consequences and Responses* Vol.1: 78,

Turkey's migration management system, which is influenced by international agreements, domestic policies, and socio-political pressures.

In terms of forced returns, administrative detention for returning and deportation exists, particularly targeting migrants who are in violation of LFIP (including irregular migrants, unregistered, linked with terrorist organisations, involved in criminal activities, etc.). Turkey also has two main assisted voluntary return programmes supported by IOM and ICPMD (the national programme is supported), particularly for non-Syrians. Finally, there are also “voluntary returns of Syrians” that are not spontaneous and are based on individual decisions. A primary legal framework exists for both forced returns and voluntary returns. However, due to regularisation, deprivation, and increased intimidation policies, criminalisation practices have become increasingly observable since 2019.

Turkey's return migration policies illustrate the complex interplay between national interests, international pressures, and humanitarian obligations. As Turkey continues to navigate its role as a key actor in regional migration governance, future policies must strike a balance between these often-competing priorities. Academically, this necessitates ongoing research to critically evaluate the impact of these policies on migrant rights, regional stability, and the evolving nature of international migration governance.

Forced returns are defined as “the act of returning an individual, against his or her will, to the country of origin, transit or to a third country that agrees to receive the person, generally carried out on the basis of an administrative or judicial act or decision.”⁷⁷ In Turkey, these are governed by a legal framework that allows for deportation under specific conditions, primarily targeting irregular migrants and those deemed to pose security threats. While international agreements such as the principle of non-refoulement provide safeguards, implementation practices have often raised concerns regarding human rights violations. Forced returns in Turkey are characterised by legal or physical compulsion, often implemented through deportations or removal processes. Returns under the EU-Turkey Statement of 2016 also fall under the category of forced returns. While framed as a tool for managing irregular migration, the Statement facilitates the return of migrants and asylum seekers from Greece to Turkey, including those who fail to qualify for asylum in the EU. These returns are carried out under binding agreements rather than the free will of the individuals involved, thereby meeting the definition of forced returns.

Voluntary returns are defined as “the assisted or independent return to the country of origin, transit or another country based on the voluntary decision of the returnee.”⁷⁸ Turkey promotes both spontaneous return (voluntary, independent return of migrants) and assisted voluntary return (AVR) (supported by financial, logistical, or reintegration aid) as key parts of its migration policy, especially for Syrians under TP. However, the voluntariness of these returns is debated, with socio-economic pressures, anti-migrant sentiment, and limited integration prospects acting as indirect, yet coercive, factors. For Afghans, voluntary returns are supported by international mechanisms, including IOM-assisted programmes, yet remain overshadowed by precarious living conditions in Turkey.

Pushbacks are defined by the UN Human Rights Council Special Rapporteur on the human rights of migrants, Felipe González Morales, as:

2023, Uppsala: Acta Universitatis Upsaliensis. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1002123; Zeynep Sahin-Mencuttek and A. Triandafyllidou, “Coerced return: formal policies, informal practices and migrants’ navigation”, *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, pp. 1–18, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369183X.2024.2371209>

⁷⁷ IOM, *Ibid.*, 2019, p. 77.

⁷⁸ *Ibid.*, p. 229.

“The various measures taken by States which result in migrants, including asylum seekers, being summarily forced back to the country from where they attempted to cross or have crossed an international border without access to international protection or asylum procedures or denied of any individual assessment on their protection needs which may lead to a violation of the principle of non-refoulement.”⁷⁹

Turkey-Iran land borders in the east have seen significant interceptions and denial of access to territory, particularly since 2021, when the Taliban took over power in Afghanistan and an increased flow of migrants was observed at the Turkey-Iran land borders. These measures reflect a securitised approach to migration management, focusing on deterrence and border control, often at the expense of migrants’ rights. However, this report specifically focuses on the returns from Europe to Europe. Thus, the main focus is on the EU-Turkey borders, where, based on the existing literature⁸⁰ and the conducted fieldwork show that pushbacks were mainly conducted by Greece, in particular at the sea borders, but at the land border for a limited period by Turkey as responding to pushbacks with “pushforwards” that can be described as the practice of a country facilitating or directing the movement of migrants toward the borders of another state, often as a response to pushbacks conducted by neighbouring countries.⁸¹

Here, the main legal and institutional framework, along with the related actors, will be provided, and the EUTRS and pushbacks and pushforwards at the EU-Turkey borders will be examined in more detail as the selected case studies.

4.1 Voluntary Return Mechanism in Turkey

Turkey’s assisted voluntary programmes can be classified into the AVRR and N-AVRR programmes, which are implemented collaboratively by the IOM, the PMM, and ICMPD, as well as non-assisted voluntary returns.

4.1.1. Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR) Programme

The AVRR is one of the primary activities of IOM Turkey, established in 2009. The AVRR programme facilitates “the orderly and humane return and reintegration of migrants who are unable or unwilling to remain in host or transit countries and wish to return voluntarily to their countries of origin”.⁸² The programme provides a safe and supportive pathway for them to return and rebuild their lives.

⁷⁹ Human Rights Council (HRC), “Report on means to address the human rights impact of pushbacks of migrants on land and at sea”, 2021, p. 4. Available at: <https://undocs.org/en/A/HRC/47/30> (Accessed 12 March 2025).

⁸⁰ ABR, Ibid., 2024; ABR, Ibid., 2023; AI, Ibid., 2021; AIDA, Ibid., 24 August 2024; ECCHR, Ibid., 2021; ECRE, Ibid., 2 March 2018; ECRE, Ibid., 7 June 2024; HRW, Ibid., 26 May 2022; IM, Ibid., 30 August 2023; IM, Ibid., 8 January 2025.

⁸¹ N. Ela Gokalp Aras, “The Politics of Care and Control: Governmentality in Turkey’s Evolving Border Policy with the Reflections from Turkey-EU Borders”, *Journal of borderland Studies*, 2024. DOI: 10.1080/08865655.2024.2428636

⁸² IOM, “Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration”, 2024. Available at: <https://turkiye.iom.int/assisted-voluntary-return-and-reintegration> (Accessed 7 May 2025).

In 2009, when the IOM launched its AVRR programme in Turkey, the country had not yet developed a formal institutional framework for managing migration. The DGMM was only established in 2013. Before the DGMM's formation, IOM collaborated primarily with Turkey's Ministry of Interior, specifically with departments such as the Foreigners' Department within the Turkish National Police, which was then responsible for migration-related issues.⁸³ During this period, IOM's AVRR activities were coordinated with various governmental bodies and border management authorities to ensure the safe, voluntary return of migrants. Additionally, IOM partnered with international organisations, such as the UNHCR, and local NGOs to maintain adherence to the principles of voluntariness and dignity in the return process.⁸⁴ This inter-agency collaboration enabled IOM to effectively implement AVRR activities despite the absence of a centralised migration authority. Following the establishment of PMM (formerly DGMM), this main activity of the IOM has been conducted in partnership with this state actor, along with other relevant authorities, NGOs, and diplomatic missions of the countries of return.

At the time of writing this report, due to the prevailing security situation in Syria, the AVRR Programme with the IOM does not operate in Syria, although Syrians are the majority of beneficiaries of international and temporary protection in Turkey. Thus, IOM was currently not involved in any operation in Turkey related to the voluntary return/repatriation of Syrians to Syria.⁸⁵ However, since mid-December 2024, return movements have intensified following the ousting of President Bashar Al-Assad's government. According to the UNHCR's latest figures, as of 8 December 2024, a total of 628,029 individuals have voluntarily returned to Syria from abroad, with over 200,000 having returned from Turkey.⁸⁶ The most recent official figures regarding voluntary returns of Syrians are given in **Figure 13**. However, it should be noted that although those returns are registered as "voluntary", they are still not classified under AVRR.

Figure 13: Syrian Voluntary Returns from Turkey since 8 December 2024

Source: Prepared by authors based on the UNHCR. (2025, June 26). Regional Flash Updates on the Syria Situation Crisis.

⁸³ Ahmet İçduygu, "Turkey's Evolving Migration Policies: A Mediterranean Transit Country Perspective. Transatlantic Council on Migration", *Istituto Affari Internazionali*, Working Papers 15, 31 September 2015. Available at: <https://www.iai.it/sites/default/files/iaiw1531.pdf> (Accessed 12 March 2025).

⁸⁴ Kemal Kirişçi, *Syrian Refugees and Turkey's Challenges: Going Beyond Hospitality*, 2015, Brookings.

⁸⁵ IOM, *Ibid.*, 2024.

⁸⁶ UNHCR, "UNHCR Regional Flash Update #33 - Syria Situation Crisis, 2025. Available at: <https://reliefweb.int/report/syrian-arab-republic/regional-flash-update-33-syria-situation-crisis> (Accessed 26 June 2025).

<https://reliefweb.int/search/results?search=Regional+Flash+Update+Syria+situation+crisis> (Accessed 7 July 2025).

On the other hand, IOM has offered AVRR for Afghans who are unable or unwilling to remain in host countries and wish to return voluntarily to Afghanistan; however, “due to the current situation in Afghanistan, certain services have been temporarily put on hold”.⁸⁷ Before this is upheld, services include assistance in transit and reception upon arrival, as well as pre-departure and post-arrival provision of information, counselling, and referral services. Additionally, services encompass onward transportation to the final in-country destination, provision of immediate and longer-term reintegration assistance, and medical assistance.⁸⁸

IOM provides services as part of the AVRR Programme, based on the IOM’s Policy on the Full Spectrum of Return, Readmission, and Reintegration (2021).⁸⁹ This policy is based on three core principles: voluntariness, safety, dignity, and reintegration support. Voluntariness is central to the AVRR process, as it involves the voluntary nature of the return. Migrants make an informed decision, without coercion, based on comprehensive counselling provided by IOM and PMM.⁹⁰ The Programme ensures that the rights and safety of returnees are prioritised, with risk assessments conducted to prevent harm during and after the return process. The programme also emphasises the preservation of human dignity throughout each stage of return. Finally, the AVRR includes post-return assistance tailored to individual needs, such as vocational training, economic support, and psychosocial care, to facilitate reintegration and promote self-sufficiency in the country of origin. In terms of implementation, migrants initiate the AVRR process through the Provincial Directorates of PMM, where they submit a request and receive the necessary information. After completing the required documentation, IOM coordinates travel arrangements and provides support at every stage, including reception upon arrival in the country of origin. IOM also offers reintegration assistance, aiming to reduce re-migration and enhance the sustainability of returns.⁹¹ As stated in the IOM’s Mission Strategy for 2021-2025⁹², Turkey is in the process of establishing a National Voluntary Return Mechanism. The IOM, PMM, and partners have been working to strengthen the AVRR mechanism in Turkey by providing technical support to develop the legislative framework, operational capacity, and Standard Operational Procedures. **Figure 15** provides the flowchart for the IOM’s procedures for the AVRR.

Regarding voluntary returns (not AVRR), the UNHCR also states that as of 6 March 2025, 133,000 Syrians have returned since the fall of the Assad regime voluntarily and in dignity from Turkey to Syria.⁹³ Also, as of 26 February 2025, the go-and-see visits for Syrians under

⁸⁷ IOM Afghanistan, “Assisted Voluntary Return (AVR)”, 2023. Available at: https://www.iom.int/jahia/webdav/shared/shared/mainsite/activities/countries/docs/afghanistan/avr_factsheet_sept08.pdf (Accessed 12 March 2025).

⁸⁸ IOM Afghanistan, “Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration”, 2024. Available at: <https://afghanistan.iom.int/assisted-voluntary-return-and-reintegration#:~:text=Through%20the%20Assisted%20Voluntary%20Return,to%20return%20voluntarily%20to%20Afghanistan> (Accessed 12 March 2025).

⁸⁹ IOM, “IOM’s Policy on the Full Spectrum of Return, Readmission and Reintegration”, 2021. Available at: <https://www.iom.int/sites/g/files/tmzbdl486/files/documents/ioms-policy-full-spectrum-of-return-readmission-and-reintegration.pdf> (Accessed 12 March 2025).

⁹⁰ Ibid.

⁹¹ ICMPD, “Communication and Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration”, 2024. Available at: https://www.icmpd.org/file/download/60843/file/20231214_%2520Communication%2520and%2520AVRR_%2520Design.pdf (Accessed 12 March 2025).

⁹² IOM Türkiye, “IOM Turkey Mission Strategy 2021-2025”, 2020, p. 17. Available at: https://turkiye.iom.int/sites/g/files/tmzbdll061/files/documents/iom_turkey_missionstrategy2021-2025.pdf (Accessed 12 March 2025).

⁹³ UNHCR, “Regional Flash Update #17 Syria situation crisis”, 7 March 2025, Available at: <https://data.unhcr.org/es/documents/download/114985> (Accessed 10 March 2025).

TP, as well as all Syrian nationals legally residing in Turkey and those who acquired Turkish citizenship, restarted after being halted in 2022.⁹⁴ For the voluntary returns, the UNHCR monitors returns at 20 PDMM offices, four border crossings in the south-east, and Istanbul Airport. UNHCR is also prepared to monitor at Sabiha Gökçen Airport in Istanbul and Ankara Esenboğa Airport when the announced flights commence. A growing number of returnees prefer travelling at night to avoid heat and crowds, prompting UNHCR to pilot night monitoring shifts.⁹⁵ In addition, in response to recent developments, on 6 February 2025, the UNHCR launched a new funding appeal seeking \$370.9 million to implement a new “Operational Framework for the Voluntary Return of Syrian Refugees and Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs),” aimed at facilitating the voluntary return of refugees.⁹⁶

4.1.2. National Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (N-AVRR) Programme

Turkey’s voluntary return mechanism facilitates the return of individuals under international protection to their country of origin, “ensuring that the decision to return is made freely and with full awareness of the implications, including the termination of their protection status in Turkey”.⁹⁷ In this regard, Turkey upholds “the principles of voluntary, safe, and dignified return, in line with international law”. Thus, under these principles, no individual under temporary or international protection is subject to forced return or pressure to leave Turkey.⁹⁸ The process emphasises a return in conditions that maintain human dignity, ensuring that individuals are informed of their rights and the consequences of their decisions.

To support sustainable return outcomes, Turkey promotes reintegration efforts in the individuals’ home countries, aiming to enhance their stability and quality of life upon return.

Voluntary return is regulated under several sources in the Turkish law:

- 1) The LFIP was made in 2019 under Article 60/A. According to this Article, among irregular migrants for whom a deportation decision has been taken and who wish to voluntarily return to their country of origin, in-kind or in-cash support may be provided to persons deemed appropriate by the PMM. Activities related to the voluntary return of irregular migrants may be carried out in cooperation with international organisations, public institutions, and non-governmental organisations.
- 2) The Regulation on the LFIP (Implementation Regulation, 2016)⁹⁹ also has certain provisions regarding voluntary return. Pursuant to the Regulation (Art. 63), foreigners who request voluntary return to their country of origin or a third country of their choice may be sent directly to their country of origin or a third country of their choice without being transferred to removal centres and without being bound by the time limit set out

⁹⁴ UNHCR, “Regional Flash Update #16”, 27 February 2025, Available at: <https://data.unhcr.org/en/documents/download/114904> (Accessed 8 March 2025).

⁹⁵ UNHCR. (2025, June). Syria situation crisis regional flash update #31. <https://www.unhcr.org/media/syria-situation-crisis-regional-flash-update-31> (Accessed 4 July 2025).

⁹⁶ UNHCR, “UNHCR’s Financial Requirements Voluntary Return of Syrian Refugees and IDPs: January-December 2025”, 6 February 2025. Available at: <https://reporting.unhcr.org/unhcr%E2%80%99s-financial-requirements-voluntary-returns-syrian-refugees-and-idps> (Accessed 12 March 2025).

⁹⁷ PMM, “Voluntary, Safe and Dignified Return”, 2024. Available at: <https://en.goc.gov.tr/voluntary-safe-and-dignified-return> (Accessed 2 March 2025).

⁹⁸ Ibid.

⁹⁹ Resmi Gazete, “Yabancılar ve Uluslararası Koruma Kanununun Uygulanmasına İlişkin Yönetmelik”, 17 March 2016. Available at: <https://www.resmigazete.gov.tr/eskiler/2016/03/20160317-11.htm> (Accessed 12 March 2025).

in Article 53 of the Law (minimum 15 days, maximum 30 days), unless they have an obstacle to their travel. Foreigners who request voluntary return while in a removal centre are taken to the border gate by the general law enforcement under the coordination of the provincial directorate. The deportation and administrative detention decisions on them are terminated upon arrival at the border gate, and the exit procedures are recorded as "voluntary return" or "voluntary departure".

- 3) The third source regulating voluntary return is the TPR (2014). According to the TPR, the foreigners within the scope of the Regulation who will voluntarily return to their countries are provided with the necessary convenience and support to the extent possible (TPR, Art. 42). The PMM may plan, prepare and implement projects and programmes for voluntary return in cooperation with the relevant country authorities, public institutions and organisations, international organisations and non-governmental organisations (TPR, Art. 42). The procedures and principles regarding the implementation of voluntary return operations and the assistance to be provided to voluntary returnees are determined by the PMM and implemented by the governorates. However, it is worth noting that there are currently no publicly accessible specific regulations in this regard.
- 4) The LFIP regulates voluntary return under “support for voluntary return” under Article 87 (1), and beneficiaries of TP have the right to voluntarily return to Syria; “Material and financial support may be provided to those applicants and IP beneficiaries who would wish to voluntarily return”. According to paragraph 2 of the same article, the PMM (formerly the DGMM), under the MoI, as the governmental authority responsible for overall migration and IP affairs in Turkey, is the responsible authority for carrying out voluntary repatriation activities in coordination with international organisations, public institutions, and civil society organisations.

The authorised actor, the PDMM, explains the voluntary return process, which begins with the submission of a "Voluntary Return Request Form" (**Annex 1**) at the PDMM office in the individual's area of residence.¹⁰⁰

For Syrians under TP, the process is overseen by independent bodies, such as international organisations and non-governmental organisations, to ensure transparency and impartiality. The UNHCR or, when unavailable, the Turkish Red Cross (*Kızılay*, TRC) must sign the request form. In cases where neither the UNHCR nor the TRC representatives are present, an authorised non-governmental organisation or a representative from the Human Rights and Equality Board of the governorate can provide the necessary oversight. Once a request for voluntary return is approved, individuals are informed that re-entry to Turkey may be restricted, which could potentially impact their future applications for temporary protection.

In line with international law, Turkey commits itself to the voluntary, safe, and dignified return of individuals to their countries of origin.¹⁰¹ Those who want to voluntarily return must apply to the PDMM office in their city of registration. They must complete a Voluntary Return Form and take a copy of it along with a travel permission document. In addition to Syrians themselves, there are three signatories of the voluntary return form:

- i. PDMM official,
- ii. Translator,

¹⁰⁰ PMM, “Gönüllü Geri Dönüş”, 2025. Available at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/gonullu-geri-donus> (Accessed 12 March 2025).

¹⁰¹ PMM, *Ibid.*, 2024.

- iii. UNHCR¹⁰², the TRC, and NGOs are deemed feasible by the governorate or human rights committee members of the governorates, who have an observatory role concerning the voluntariness of the return of Syrians who wish to voluntarily return to Syria.

With these forms signed, Syrians may travel freely to the designated border crossing points. A border crossing point for voluntary return is determined based on the list of open and permitted crossing points, travel safety, and the migrants' choice. Once migrants arrive at the desired border crossing point, with their travel permission document and a signed copy of their voluntary return form, they may leave Turkey. Voluntary return means accepting the termination of the TP status¹⁰³ (including a V-87 restriction code¹⁰⁴ on their respective ID card), and all rights afforded to TP-ID holders are consequently forfeited. Authorities thus take away their TP-ID Card at the border.¹⁰⁵

Re-applying the TP status for V-87 coded migrants who return to Turkey is at the discretion of the PDMMs, subject to the approval of the respective governorates. DGMM sent a circular to the 81 provinces of Turkey's 81 governorates in January 2019. According to the circular, Syrians under TP who signed a voluntary return form, returned to Syria and consequently had their TP status "deactivated" with a V-87 code can, in fact, reapply to reactivate their TP status even if previously rejected by Governorships; however, this may only apply under certain conditions (e.g. illness, hospital admission, elderly age, marriage purposes, school enrolment, employment, etc.), but there are practical hurdles, including restricted registration access and rejected applications.

Article 87 (1) of LFIP assigns the responsibility to the PMM (formerly the DGMM), under the MoI, as the governmental authority responsible for overall migration and IP affairs in Turkey, to carry out voluntary repatriation activities in coordination with related state and non-state actors, as well as IGOs. In the case of an organised, large-scale repatriation operation, the Disaster and Emergency Management Presidency, responsible for emergency management and civil protection nationwide in Turkey (AFAD), takes over responsibility from DGMM at the border crossings. At the provincial level, PDMM, district governorates, and law enforcement units, such as police, gendarmerie and border control authorities, are central to implementing return policies. NGOs such as the Association for Social Development and Aid Mobilisation (ASAM) and the Cooperative for Assistance and Relief Everywhere (CARE), as well as international organisations like the UNHCR, provide legal aid and protection services. UNHCR observes the voluntary nature of returns. In the absence of the UNHCR, the TRC, and other local-level authorised civil organisations are involved in observing voluntariness.

On the other hand, unlike the individual voluntary returns, the ICMPD Turkey has been working with the PMM to establish an N-AVRR mechanism. As a result of long-standing consultations and background work within the ICMPD projects' framework, the national stakeholders of the N-AVRR programme were identified as PMM, TRC, the Turkish Cooperation and Coordination Agency (TİKA), and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MoFA).

¹⁰² UNHCR monitors the voluntary return interviews conducted by PDMMs in 16 provinces. PDMMs are responsible for interviewing, counseling, and processing refugees' applications to voluntarily return to Syria.

¹⁰³ Article 85 (1/ç) of the LFIP states that "the international protection status shall terminate in cases where the beneficiary voluntarily returned to the country from which they have fled or stayed outside of due to fear of persecution"

¹⁰⁴ The V-87 code is a restriction applied to foreigners in Turkey, typically preventing them from obtaining a new residence permit, visa extension, or long-term legal stay. It is often issued when an individual is deemed ineligible to remain in the country due to violations of immigration rules, security concerns, or overstaying a previous permit. Its key implications are entry ban, residence permit block (LFIP, Article 54).

¹⁰⁵PMM, *Ibid.*, 2024.

Those national stakeholders signed a letter of intent on June 18, 2019, and a Cooperation Protocol on September 2, 2020, laying the foundations for the implementation of the N-AVRR.¹⁰⁶

In general, the PMM collaborates with international organisations, such as the IOM, UNHCR, and ICMPD, to operationalise the return of migrants. These collaborations often include technical assistance programmes that support voluntary return and reintegration into the countries of origin. Operational enforcement involves coordination with international bodies to ensure that returns are conducted in line with international refugee protection standards. PMM has also enhanced its capacity for assisted returns, receiving technical and financial support from the EU and its Member States. The ICMPD oversaw the SUPREME Project (“Strengthening Utilisation of Additional Policies and Measures for Reinforcing Migration Management in Turkey”) from 2019 to 2021.¹⁰⁷ In 2021, the PMM established its own voluntary return mechanism (N-AVRR) with ICMPD’s technical assistance and national budget financing through the Project on Supporting Turkey’s National Assisted Voluntary Return & Reintegration System.¹⁰⁸ While this mechanism allows Afghans to return voluntarily to Afghanistan, the information regarding operations and the number of returnees is not accessible. These returns were temporarily halted following the fall of Kabul but resumed in early 2022 under the banner of ‘voluntary return.’

The ICMPD¹⁰⁹ provides technical and operational assistance to the N-AVRR programme, supporting policy and programme development aimed at promoting voluntary return and reintegration.

The EU supports Turkey’s N-AVRR. According to the European Commission’s “Turkey 2023 Report”, 737 irregular migrants were returned through the national voluntary return scheme, while 2,259 were returned with the assistance of IOM and EU financing in 2022.¹¹⁰ In addition to the Instrument for Pre-Accession Assistance (IPA), individual member states (Denmark, Netherlands and Norway) provided support for the N-AVRR, consisting of two pillars: i) provision of comprehensive support for the implementation and ii) further development of Turkey’s N-AVRR system, including capacity building activities and financial assistance provision for conducting voluntary return operations and reintegration assistance.¹¹¹

Figure 14 outlines the voluntary return process managed by Turkey’s PDMMs. The process begins with migrants submitting an application to the PDMM, in which they express their intention to voluntarily return to their country of origin. Following this, the authorities conduct a registration and verification process to ensure the applicant meets the necessary

¹⁰⁶ Ibid.

¹⁰⁷ ICMPD, “Strengthening Utilization of Additional Policies and Measures for Reinforcing Migration Management in Türkiye”, 2025. Available at: <https://www.icmpd.org/our-work/projects/strengthening-utilization-of-additional-policies-and-measures-for-reinforcing-migration-management-in-tuerkiye-supreme> (Accessed 8 March 2025).

¹⁰⁸ ICMPD, “Launching Project on Supporting Turkey’s National Assisted Voluntary Return & Reintegration System”, 22 March 2022, Available at: <https://www.icmpd.org/news/launching-project-on-supporting-turkey-s-national-assisted-voluntary-return-reintegration-system#:~:text=The%20N-AVRR%20Project%20started%20on,Management%20is%20the%20main%20beneficiary>. (Accessed 8 March 2025).

¹⁰⁹ ICMPD, Ibid., 2024.

¹¹⁰ European Commission, “Commission Staff Working Document: Türkiye 2023 Report”, 8 November 2023. Available at: https://neighbourhood-enlargement.ec.europa.eu/document/download/eb90aefd-897b-43e9-8373-bf59c239217f_en?filename=SWD_2023_696%20T%C3%BCrkiye%20report.pdf (Accessed 12 March 2025).

¹¹¹ ICMPD, Ibid., 2024.

legal and procedural requirements. Once verified, the migrant completes the official voluntary return forms, documenting their consent to return. Upon approval, a road permit document is issued, enabling the individual to travel to the designated border gate. Finally, the migrant's registration in Turkey is terminated, formally completing the return process. This structured procedure ensures the voluntary nature of the return and compliance with both domestic and international standards.

Figure 14: National Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration Programme (N-AVRR) / Voluntary Return Flowchart

Source: Prepared by the authors based on the PMM, “Voluntary, Safe and Dignified Return”, 2024. Available at: <https://en.goc.gov.tr/voluntary-safe-and-dignified-return> (Accessed 12 March 2025).

Figure 15 explains that in both the AVRR and N-AVRR, the first stage is the “Pre-Departure Stage”, where the IOM offers counselling and critical information to help migrants make informed decisions. Necessary medical and logistical support, including health assessments, documentation, and travel arrangements, is provided to ensure a smooth departure. Second is the “Transportation Stage”, where IOM coordinates all travel logistics, including departure assistance, transit support, and, if necessary, medical escorts. This ensures migrants travel safely and with appropriate assistance. The last stage is the “Post-Arrival Stage”, where, upon arrival, migrants receive financial aid, transportation to their final destinations, and reintegration support, including vocational training and micro-financing. IOM collaborates with local organisations to support sustainable reintegration.¹¹²

It should be noted that Syrian refugees are excluded from both AVRR and NVARR, which is grounded in legal, humanitarian, and operational frameworks established by international law and institutional mandates. Syrians’ exclusion is neither arbitrary nor procedural but a necessary adherence to international law and institutional divisions of responsibility. However, individual voluntary returns of Syrians are the case, but not as part of AVRR or N-AVRR.

¹¹² IOM, “Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR)”, 2021. Available at: <https://www.iom.int/jahia/webdav/site/myjahiasite/shared/shared/mainsite/activities/regulating/AVRR-Leaflet-Jan-2011.pdf> (Accessed 12 March 2025).

Figure 15: Return Migration Infrastructures Flow Map (Voluntary Returns)

Source: Prepared by the authors based on the PMM, “Voluntary, Safe and Dignified Return”, 2024. Available at: <https://en.goc.gov.tr/voluntary-safe-and-dignified-return> (Accessed 12 March 2025) & IOM, “Implementation of Assisted Voluntary Returns Including Reintegration Measures (AVRR)”, 2018. Available at: <https://www.onlinelibrary.iihl.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/2019-I1-5.pdf> (Accessed 12 March 2025)

4.2 Forced Return (Removal)

4.2.1. Based on the National Law

In Turkish law, return-related regulations are influenced by LFIP, its Implementation Regulation (IR), and the TP. The Constitution guarantees fundamental rights and freedoms for all individuals, including foreigners, under the principles of equality (Articles 10, 12, 17, 19, 20, 36, 40, 41). However, Article 16 permits restrictions on foreigners' rights by law, provided these conform to the general criteria outlined in Article 13, including proportionality and adherence to democratic principles. Administrative decisions must also align with laws (Articles 7 and 124). The LFIP and IR provide a legal framework for return procedures, ensuring compliance with international and constitutional norms. The TPR plays a critical role in addressing rights related to refoulement, liberty, security, and return for individuals under temporary protection, who form the majority of foreigners in Turkey.

In Turkish law, deportation is based on a deportation decision, with no distinction made between such decisions and removal orders. Once finalised—either after judicial review or upon expiry of the appeal period—the decision becomes enforceable, and the individual is deemed returnable (LFIP, Article 53 (1)). Deportation decisions may include direct removal, voluntary departure, or administrative detention (IR, Article 56/2). PDMM oversees the evaluation, while law enforcement agencies handle the enforcement. Under Article 54 of the LFIP, deportation decisions can be issued for individuals who:

- Pose a threat to public order, safety, or health.
- Commit crimes or use forged documents for entry/residence.
- Overstay visas or work without permits.
- Violate the conditions of entry or exit from Turkey.
- They are associated with terrorism or organised crime.
- Lose international protection status or have inadmissible asylum claims.

For IP applicants and status holders, deportation is limited to cases involving terrorism, organised crime, or public safety risks (LFIP, Article 54/1/b/d/k). Stateless persons can only be deported if they pose a serious threat to public order or safety (LFIP, Article 51/1/b).

Under Articles 55 of the LFIP and 52 of the IR, deportation is prohibited for individuals who:

- Risk death, torture, or degrading treatment in the destination country.
- Face travel risks due to health, age, or pregnancy.
- Requires ongoing life-saving medical treatment that is unavailable in the destination country.
- Are victims of trafficking or violence during their recovery period.
- Have judicial appeals pending under inadmissible or accelerated asylum assessments (IR, Article 52/1/g).

The principle of non-refoulement, enshrined in Article 4 of the LFIP, applies to all removal cases and must be upheld throughout the procedure. Deportation assessments must be completed within 48 hours of an individual's apprehension or transfer to a removal centre (LFIP, Article 57/1; IR, Article 53/2-3). Decisions can also be issued in absentia (IR, Article 53/5). The administration is required to ensure that deportation aligns with legal protections and international standards.

The LFIP does not explicitly prohibit collective expulsion, but its deportation provisions mandate case-by-case assessments, effectively rendering collective expulsion unlawful under Turkish law. Articles 53, 54, and 55 provide the framework.

Deportation may target the country of origin, a transit country, or a third country (LFIP, Art. 52). The destination is determined based on factors such as citizenship, acceptance by the receiving country, or a request for removal to a third country (IR, Art. 51/2). However, individuals at risk can only be deported to a safe third country, adhering to the prohibition of refoulement (LFIP, Art. 4) and exemptions under Article 55.

The LFIP (Articles 73 and 74) and IR (Articles 76, 77/2, 3, and 4) outline the criteria for deporting international protection applicants to a safe third country or the first country of asylum if their applications are deemed inadmissible. If removal is not possible, the international protection process continues. Applicants remain in Turkey until they are removed to the designated country.

Under Article 53 of the LFIP, deportation decisions and their reasons must be communicated to the individual, their legal representative, or their lawyer. If a lawyer does not represent the individual, they must be informed about the decision, appeal procedures, and deadlines. Deportation decisions specify whether the individual will be deported directly, invited to leave, or placed in administrative detention. Notifications must also include instructions for informing the authority issuing the deportation order in the case of an appeal (IR, Article 56).

Turkish law does not require deportation decisions to specify the destination country explicitly. However, Article 55 of the LFIP implies such an obligation by mandating an assessment of risks in the destination country before issuing a deportation decision. For those deemed unfit for deportation due to such risks, Article 57 of the IR states that deportation orders are suspended, and efforts are made to find a safe destination country. During this period, the individual may remain in Turkey with a humanitarian residence permit. Once a safe country is identified, deportation proceeds without issuing a new deportation decision, preventing prior appeals specific to that country. Only deportation decisions can be appealed within 7 days of notification with the administrative court in the issuing province (LFIP, Article 53). The court's decision is final, with no further appeal available. Afterwards, individuals can file an individual application with the Constitutional Court (Constitution, Article 148) if a constitutional or European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR)-protected right is violated (e.g., the right to life, prohibition of torture, or family protection). Deportation is suspended during the administrative court process but not during applications to the Constitutional Court or the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR), where deportation may still occur.

According to Article 60 of the LFIP, law enforcement officers are required to accompany individuals to border crossings. If deportation does not require placement in a removal centre, law enforcement still facilitates the process. Foreigners invited to leave Turkey voluntarily within a specified period are not escorted unless they exceed this timeframe; in such cases, they may be detained and escorted. Article 62 of the IR allows officers to take security measures to prevent escape and, if necessary, accompany individuals during travel to their destination. Deportation costs are typically borne by the foreign national when possible; however, in cases of insufficient funds, the PMM covers the costs, leaving the individual with a basic amount for their needs.

Based on the legal and procedural framework in Turkey, the classification of forced return practices varies depending on the status of the individual being returned: irregular migrants, individuals under temporary protection, and those under international protection.

Irregular Migrants

- Legal Basis: The LFIP and the IR form the primary legal framework.

- **Deportation Decision:** Irregular migrants can be deported through a standardised administrative decision process (LFIP, Article 53).
- **Grounds for Deportation:** Includes unauthorised entry, stay, or work; criminal activities; or public safety threats (LFIP, Article 54).
- **Execution of Deportation:** Decisions are enforceable after finalisation through judicial review or upon expiration of the appeal period (LFIP, Art. 57). Deportations may involve administrative detention.
- **Exemptions:** Individuals with severe health conditions or facing risks like torture or degrading treatment in the destination country are protected under non-refoulement principles (LFIP, Articles 4, 55).

Persons Under Temporary Protection

- **Legal Framework:** Governed by the TPR.
- **Specific Provisions:**
 - Deportation is generally not applicable unless an individual poses a significant threat to public safety.
 - The principle of non-refoulement applies strictly to protect those at risk in their country of origin (TPR, Art. 42).
- **Voluntary Return:** Encouraged under international observation, with safeguards to ensure returns are genuinely voluntary.
- **Enforcement:** Deportation orders may involve withdrawal of temporary protection status after ensuring there are no risks in the destination country.

Individuals Under International Protection

- **Legal Basis:** LFIP and related provisions explicitly limit deportation for applicants and status holders (LFIP, Article 54/2).
- **Restrictions:**
 - Deportation is allowed only under strict conditions, such as association with terrorism or threats to public safety.
 - The principle of non-refoulement is strictly enforced (LFIP, Article 4).
- **Special Cases:**
 - During the appeal process for rejected applications, deportation is stayed.
 - Returning to a safe third country or the first country of asylum is possible, provided that such countries meet detailed protection and connection criteria (LFIP, Articles 73, 74).
- **Procedural Safeguards:** Individuals have the right to judicial review, and deportation is suspended until a final decision is made.

These distinctions highlight that while irregular migrants face more direct deportation measures, individuals under TP or IP benefit from additional safeguards rooted in Turkey's obligations under domestic and international law. Since the procedures for the forced return of individuals not under international or temporary protection have already been outlined, the procedures for these two groups are significantly more complex. Therefore, the following flow maps (**Figures 16 and 17**) detailing the return migration infrastructure for these groups have been provided.

Figure 16: Return Migration Infrastructures Flow Map of Turkey (Temporary Protection)

* Developed based on Framework paper on the concepts and typologies on returns (D.1.1)
 ** Deportation Processes, Presidency of Migration Management, 2024, <https://www.goc.gov.tr/sinir-disi-etme>
 *** Voluntary, Safe, Dignified Return, Presidency of Migration Management, 2024, <https://www.goc.gov.tr/gocullu-geri-donus>
 **** Theoretically, deportation decision can be issued for the third countries, however, PMM claims that it is not possible to issue deportation decision(s) legally about Syrians due to the conditions in Syria.

Source: Prepared by the authors based on the national legal framework (LFIP, TPR, IR, etc.)

Figure 17: Return Migration Infrastructures Flow Map of Turkey (International Protection)

Source: Prepared by the authors based on the national legal framework (LFIP, TPR, IR, etc.)

4.2.2. Readmission Agreements and the EU-Turkey Statement

Readmission agreements (RAs) should be evaluated as a component of forced returns due to their inherent legal, procedural, and practical characteristics, which compel migrants to return to their country of origin, a transit country, or a third country under formalised bilateral or multilateral arrangements. These agreements are often framed as tools for migration management and control; however, their implementation highlights coercive elements, aligning them more closely with the definition of forced returns. While RAs do not always involve direct coercion, they provide the framework that facilitates such removals, often bypassing voluntary decision-making by the individuals concerned.

RAs are international treaties or bilateral arrangements that obligate one country (e.g., the country of transit or origin) to accept the return of its nationals or third-country nationals who have transited through its territory. They inherently involve coercion, as they override individual choice. Migrants are removed without their consent, relying on procedural enforcement rather than voluntary departure. In some cases, such agreements expedite the return process, bypassing thorough evaluations of asylum claims, particularly under accelerated or inadmissibility procedures. Migrants are often held in administrative detention pending their return, highlighting the coercive aspect of these agreements. RAs might contribute to chain refoulement, where individuals are sent to unsafe third countries in violation of the principle of non-refoulement.

Agreements must comply with the principle of non-refoulement, as established in Article 33 of the 1951 Refugee Convention and Articles 3, 6 and 13 of the ECHR. Also, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) require individual assessments and access to remedies, which may be undermined by expedited processes under readmission agreements. When migrants are returned to third countries with inadequate protections, they may face further deportations to unsafe destinations, constituting a violation of customary international law. In terms of practical implications, RAs operationalise forced returns by simplifying legal and administrative barriers to deportation, establishing formalised mechanisms for return, often with deadlines and obligations, and supporting policies that create pressure to comply with return requirements, even for individuals who may otherwise qualify for protection.

These agreements streamline the return process and shift responsibilities to the accepting state, often externalising border control measures. They are also the key instruments in the externalisation of migration policies, particularly in the context of the EU. By shifting responsibilities for migration control to transit countries, such as Turkey or Libya, the EU effectively outsources forced return processes. RAs aim to control borders to block arrivals, but where this is not possible, they aim to help transit and source countries outside of EU borders to readmit migrants and manage the reception of asylum seekers.¹¹³ This has led to critiques that these agreements prioritise border control over human rights and due process protections. **Table 1** provides the RAs of Turkey.

¹¹³ Andrew Geddes, “Europe’s border relationships and international migration relations”, *Journal of Common Market Studies*, 43(4), 2015, pp. 787-806; Daniel Thym, “Towards international migration governance? The European contribution” in *The EU’s Role on Global Governance: The Legal Dimension* (Eds. Bart Van Vooren, Steven Blockmans and Jan Wouters), 2013, Oxford: Oxford University Press; Anna Triandafyllidou and Angeliki Dimitriadi, “Governing irregular migration and asylum at the borders of Europe: Between efficiency and protection”, *Instituto Affari Internazionali*, 6, pp. 1-34, 2015.

Table 1: List of Readmission Agreements of Turkey

Type of Bilateral Agreements and Negotiations	Title	Year
Standard Readmission agreements signed	The Readmission Agreement between Turkey and Syria	2001
	The Readmission Protocol between Turkey and Greece	2001
	The Readmission Agreement between Turkey and Kyrgyzstan	2003
	The Readmission Agreement between Turkey and Romania	2004
	The Readmission Agreement between Turkey and Ukraine	2005
	The Readmission Agreement between Turkey and Pakistan	2010
	The Readmission Agreement between Turkey and Russia	2011
	The Readmission Agreement between Turkey and Nigeria	2011
	The Readmission Agreement between Turkey and Yemen	2011
	The Readmission Agreement between Turkey and Moldova	2012
	The Readmission Agreement between Turkey and Bosnia and Herzegovina	2012
	The Readmission Agreement between Turkey and Belarus	2013
	The Readmission Agreement between Turkey and Montenegro	2013
	The Readmission Agreement between Turkey and the EU	2013
	The Readmission Agreement between Turkey and Kosovo	2015
The Readmission Agreement between Turkey and Norway	2016	
Political Documents	The EU-Turkey Statement	2016

Source: MoFA. (2011). “Türkiye’nin Yasadışı Göçle Mücadelesi”, Available at: http://www.mfa.gov.tr/turkiye_nin-yasadisigocle-mucadelesi-tr.mfa (Accessed 3 February 2025).

As regards the geographical focus of this report, the EUTRA and EUTRS are significant. The EUTRA (2014)¹¹⁴ establishes the obligation for Turkey to accept third-country nationals who have transited through Turkey en route to the EU. This agreement aligns with the EUTRS (2016)¹¹⁵, facilitating forced returns of migrants and asylum seekers from Greece to Turkey.

A readmission agreement between the EU and Turkey has been on Brussels’ agenda since the late 1990s, and on 16 December 2013, the EUTRA was signed. Following the ratification of the EUTRA (2014), the number of entries at the EU border reached its peak. This development created another shift in EU-Turkey relations and a search on both sides for new cooperation tools since the EUTRA was not a sufficient mechanism to handle mass population movements. The provision for the readmission of third-country nationals (TCNs) will take effect as of 1 October 2017. The response to the Syrian mass migration first started with the EU–Turkey Joint Action Plan (JAP) in 2015¹¹⁶, which focused on cooperation in accelerating procedures

¹¹⁴ Full text of the agreement is available at: [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:22014A0507\(01\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:22014A0507(01)) (Accessed 8 March 2025).

¹¹⁵ European Council, “The EU-Turkey Statement”, 2016. Available at: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2016/03/18/eu-turkey-statement/> (Accessed 8 March 2025).

¹¹⁶ European Commission, “EU-Turkey Joint Action Plan”, 2015. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/de/memo_15_5860 (Accessed 1 March 2025).

for the readmission of irregular migrants who were not in need of international protection. Then, the EUTRS—an informal readmission tool—was signed on 18 March 2016.

As a crisis-driven readmission tool, the EUTRS is directly connected to Syrians, and as a flexible form of readmission tool, it has different articles regarding the EU-Turkey relations from an external differentiated integration perspective. Regarding return and readmissions, Turkey agreed to accept all irregular migrants and asylum seekers whose applications were declared inadmissible, crossing from Turkey to the Greek islands on 20 March 2016 (Article 1) by the EUTRS. The EUTRS's readmission-related commitments are also included in Articles 3 and 4 of the EUTRA. In this regard, the EUTRS fell within the realm of the EU's readmission competence, and the authorities were identified as the Council and the European Parliament (Article 218 TFEU, Treaty of Lisbon, 2007).

The EUTRS also created a mechanism for the return of Syrians via the 'one-to-one' formula. Accordingly, for every Syrian returned to Turkey from the Greek islands, another Syrian would be resettled in the EU (Article 2). Since the EUTRS is not an international agreement but a bilateral statement, it needed a legal basis: the 2002 Readmission Protocol of Turkey and Greece (RPTG). The Protocol introduced the notion of a 'safe third country'. Drawing on the Protocol, the EUTRS paved the way for the immediate return of Syrian refugees arriving on the Greek islands because it defined Turkey as a 'safe third country'. However, Turkey's "safe third country" position is criticised for several reasons: human rights violations that are reflected by the decisions of the ECtHR, lack of legal protections, substandard conditions, political and social instability and international criticism regarding Turkey's handling of asylum and migration, citing arbitrary detention, forced returns, and inadequate protection mechanisms.¹¹⁷ The EUTRS also mentions incentives, such as capacity-building support and financial aid, were also included, with an additional €3 billion added to the amount agreed under the JAP.

According to the EUTRA, readmission for TCNs was suspended until 1 October 2017. Thus, the EUTRS accelerated the readmission of TCNs, and on 4 April 2016, Turkey accepted the first readmitted group from Greece as a part of the EUTRS.¹¹⁸ The RPTG served as the legal basis for readmissions in implementing the EUTRS until the EUTRA became applicable to TCNs in 2017. However, Turkey suspended the RPTG unilaterally on 6 June 2018 in response to a decision by a Greek court to release eight former Turkish soldiers who had fled the country a day after the 15 July 2016 coup attempt.¹¹⁹

After 1 October 2017, the EUTRA could not be used for TCNs, only for Turkish citizens, due to administrative measures taken by Turkey in response to delays in the visa exemption process. On 22 July 2019, the Turkish government publicly announced the suspension of the EUTRA in response to the EU sanctioning Turkey's gas drilling operations in Cypriot waters.¹²⁰ He added that "the readmission agreement and visa-free deal [must] be put into effect

¹¹⁷ Gamze Ovacık, Meltem Inerli-Ciger and Orçun Ulusoy, "Taking Stock of the EU-Turkey Statement in 2024", 2024, *European Journal of Migration and Law*, 26 (20 24), pp.154-178.

¹¹⁸ AIDA, "2020 Update: Turkey", 2021. Available at: <https://www.ecre.org/aida-2020-update-turkey/> (Accessed 4 March 2025).

¹¹⁹ TRT, "Turkey suspends readmission deal with Greece", 2018. Available at: <https://www.trtworld.com/turkey/turkey-suspends-readmission-deal-with-greece-cavusoglu-18063> (Accessed 4 March 2025).

¹²⁰ Euractiv, "Turkey suspends deal with the EU on migrant readmission", 2019. Available at: <https://www.euractiv.com/section/global-europe/news/turkey-suspends-deal-with-the-eu-on-migrant-readmission/> (Accessed 4 March 2025).

simultaneously” (Daily Sabah 2019). In parallel, the EU’s official websites indicated that the EUTRS was still operating.¹²¹

In 2016, Turkey began to hint that it might open its borders if the EU failed to meet its demands. This ‘coercive migration diplomacy’ remained strictly rhetorical until 28 February 2020, when Turkish authorities opened the border and allowed thousands of migrants and asylum seekers to walk into Greece, which is known as the Pazarkule Event (2020).¹²² This came in response to attacks against the Turkish military in Idlib, Syria, threatening to send waves of new Syrian migrants into Turkey.¹²³ Turkey took a sudden reaction, and after the diplomatic traffic that lasted throughout the night, news emerged that ‘Turkey will no longer prevent immigrants who want to cross to Europe’.¹²⁴ Hearing the news, thousands of migrants rushed to the Pazarkule border gate on the Turkey-Greece border, particularly to the border villages of Edirne. At that time, the number of migrants crossing the border was regularly announced by the Minister of Internal Affairs, Süleyman Soylu. While it was initially reported that 36,776 immigrants crossed the border on the evening of February 29, 2020, a revised figure of 130,469 immigrants crossing the border on the morning of March 3, 2020, was subsequently announced.¹²⁵ As observed in field studies conducted by numerous local NGOs at the time, the majority of migrants in the region were Afghan.¹²⁶ While some of the immigrants, mostly Afghans, crossed the border, the majority of them remained determinedly in the buffer zone where the Pazarkule border gate is located for about a month, despite the pushbacks and acts of violence implemented by Greece at the border. A month later, due to the spread of COVID-19 in Turkey, migrants in the region were sent to various cities in Turkey. This process led Turkey to centre and instrumentalise migrants in its diplomacy with the EU.¹²⁷

Turkey leveraged migration as a bargaining tool against the EU by declaring that it would no longer prevent migrants from crossing into Europe. This decision was driven by Ankara’s

¹²¹ European Asylum Support Office (EASO), “EASO Asylum Report 2020: Annual Report on the Situation of Asylum in the European Union”, 2020. Available at: <https://euaa.europa.eu/asylum-report-2020> (Accessed 12 March 2025); European Commission, “EU–Turkey Statement four years on”, 2020. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/sites/homeaffairs/files/what-we-do/policies/european-agenda-migration/20200318_managing-migration-eu-turkey-statement-4-years-on_en.pdf (4 March 2025).

¹²² SGDD-ASAM, “Edirne-Pazarkule Müdahalesi Raporu”, 2020. Available at: https://sgdd.org.tr/yayinlar/sgdd_asam_edirne_rapor_tr.pdf (Accessed 12 March 2025); Hakan Ünay, “Düzensiz Göçmenlerin Sınırı Geçme Deneyimleri ve Kararlılıklarının Analizi: Pazarkule Sınır Kapısı Örneği”, *Göç Araştırmaları Vakfı*, October 2020, Available at: <https://gocvakfi.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/GAV-RAPOR-Hakan-U%CC%88nay-1.pdf> (Accessed 9 March 2025).

¹²³ Reuters, “Turkey will no longer stop Syrian migrant flow to Europe: Turkish official”, 27 February, 2020. Available at: <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-syria-security-turkey-migrants/turkey-will-no-longer-stop-syrian-migrant-flow-to-europe-turkish-official-idUSKCN20L33V> (Accessed 2 March 2025).

¹²⁴ Orhan Coşkun and Ezgi Erkoyun, “Turkey says will not stop Syrian refugees reaching Europe after troops killed”, 28 February 2020, *Reuters*, available at: <https://www.reuters.com/article/idUSKCN20MoHo/> (Accessed 28 May 2024).

¹²⁵ Süleyman Soylu (@suleymansoylu), “Saat 21.02 itibarıyla Edirne üzerinden ülkemizden ayrılan göçmen sayısı; 36.776”, 29 February 2020. Available at: <https://x.com/suleymansoylu/status/1233819814428389376> (Accessed 29 May 2024); Süleyman Soylu (@suleymansoylu), “Saat 09.15 itibarıyla Türkiye topraklarından ayrılıp Edirne’den Yunanistan’a geçen göçmen sayısı; 130.469”, 3 March 2020. Available at: <https://x.com/suleymansoylu/status/1234730037326336003> (Accessed 29 May 2024).

¹²⁶ Hakan Ünay, *Ibid.*, October 2020; SGDD-ASAM, *Ibid.*, 2020.

¹²⁷ N. Ela Gökalp Aras, “The European Union’s Externalisation Policy in the Field of Migration and Asylum: Turkey as a Case Study”, *Report Multilevel Governance of Mass Migration in Europe and Beyond Project (#770564, Horizon2020) Working Paper Series*, 2021, Available at <https://www.respondmigration.com/wp-blog/> (Accessed 29 May 2024).

dissatisfaction with Europe's limited support for its military operations in Idlib, where it had sought stronger backing against the Syrian regime. By easing border restrictions, Turkey expressed its frustration with the EUTRS, which had placed the responsibility of migration management on Ankara in return for financial assistance. Turkish authorities actively facilitated the movement of migrants toward the Pazarkule border, exerting both political and humanitarian pressure on Greece and the EU. This strategic manoeuvre aimed to secure increased financial aid, diplomatic backing, and acknowledgement of Turkey's pivotal role in migration governance.

Significantly, neither the EU nor Turkey repudiated the EUTRS as this new crisis unfolded. However, on 9 March 2020, Turkish President Erdoğan, EU Council President Michel and EU Commission President von der Leyen reaffirmed that the EUTRS remained valid and that the remaining outstanding provisions would be completed.¹²⁸

Throughout March 2020, immigrants and refugees from various countries, including Syria, continued to gather at land and sea border areas on the Turkish side, including Edirne, Çanakkale, and İzmir. They were confronted with severe humanitarian tragedies and human rights violations in attempting to cross into Europe. By 28 March, Turkish state actors had begun to round up most of these migrants and distribute them to satellite cities inside Turkey. When the crisis ended on 27 March, the EU Commission Spokesman, Peter Stano, stated, "Negotiations and evaluations regarding the EU–Turkey Statement [would] continue."¹²⁹

The EU maintained its financial support, which included funding for education services and cash assistance programs. During the implementation of the EUTRS, between April 4, 2016, and March 2020, Turkey accepted the return of 2,140 individuals from Greece (nationals from Pakistan, Syria, Algeria, Afghanistan, Iraq, and Bangladesh)¹³⁰, as reflected in **Figure 18**.

The EUTRS also established a specific resettlement procedure ("1:1 scheme"), under which one Syrian national would be resettled from Turkey to an EU Member State (MS) for each Syrian national returned from Greece to Turkey. These resettlements can be viewed as a distinct form of return within the EUTRS. As of December 2023, 39,647 persons have been resettled under this "1:1 scheme", with primary resettlement destinations being Germany, France, the Netherlands, and Sweden.¹³¹ In 2024, around 13 EU countries are expected to participate in the resettlement efforts, including Belgium, the Netherlands, Slovenia, Italy, Finland, France, Norway, and Ireland.¹³²

It is not feasible to create a flowchart illustrating the implementation of the EUTRA; however, since it was applicable to Turkish citizens following its ratification, **Figures 1, 2, and 3**, provided by Eurostat, are included, although Turkey does not provide official figures. For the EUTRS, **Figure 12** provides the figures. Additionally, this report contains a flowchart illustrating its implementation, along with relevant statistical data presented in **Figure 19**. The field findings will be examined in detail in the subsequent sections of the report.

¹²⁸ Milliyet, "Cumhurbaşkanı Erdoğan, Michel ve Von der Leyen ile görüştü", 9 March, 2020. Available at: <https://www.milliyet.com.tr/siyaset/cumhurbaskani-erdogan-michel-ve-von-der-leyen-ile-gorustu-6162131> (Accessed 12 March 2025).

¹²⁹ Anadolu Agency, "Türkiye ile AB arasında Göçmen Mutabakatı'na ilişkin görüşmeler sürüyor", 27 March, 2020. Available at: <https://www.aa.com.tr/tr/dunya/turkiye-ile-ab-arasinda-gocmen-mutabakatina-iliskin-gorusmeler-suruyor/1781961> (Accessed 12 March 2025).

¹³⁰ AIDA, *Ibid.*, 2020.

¹³¹ AIDA, "Resettlement and family reunification departures Türkiye", 20 August 2024, Available at: <https://asylumineurope.org/reports/country/turkiye/content-temporary-protection/movement-and-mobility/resettlement-and-family-reunification-departures/> (Accessed 9 March 2025).

¹³² *Ibid.*

Figure 18: EU-Turkey Statement Implementation Flow Chart

Source: Prepared by authors based on European Commission, 2016, Implementing EU-Turkey Statement, Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/it/memo_16_1664 (Accessed on 12 March 2025)

4.3 Pushbacks and Pushforwards

Pushbacks, as a practice within the broader context of migration management, occupy a contentious and legally ambiguous position in the framework of return policies. These practices involve the immediate return of individuals who attempt to cross international borders without permission, thereby denying them access to asylum procedures or due process. While pushbacks are often justified by states as measures to maintain border security and deter irregular migration, they raise significant concerns regarding compliance with international law, particularly the principle of non-refoulement and the right to seek asylum, enshrined in the 1951 Refugee Convention and other human rights treaties.

Pushbacks represent a grey area in return policies because they blur the lines between legitimate border enforcement and violations of international obligations. In other words, they are *de jure* illegal since they violate various international principles. This ambiguity is exacerbated by the lack of explicit regulations governing such practices in many national legal systems, as well as inconsistent monitoring and reporting mechanisms. Within this context, pushbacks are often implemented covertly, creating a gap between formal commitments to human rights and actual state practices at borders.

The legal and procedural frameworks for pushbacks often exist in tension with international norms. For instance, while some domestic laws allow for measures such as immediate rejection at borders or expedited deportation procedures, these laws frequently lack sufficient safeguards to ensure that individuals are not returned to countries where they face persecution, torture, or other serious harm. This gap highlights the inherent conflict between state sovereignty in controlling borders and the universal principles of human rights protection.

This part of the report examines pushbacks as a grey area in return policies, exploring the legal frameworks that enable or restrict these practices and their implications for human rights and migration governance. By focusing on the intersection of national law, international obligations, and state practices, this analysis seeks to illuminate the systemic challenges and ethical dilemmas posed by pushbacks, particularly in regions where migratory pressures and geopolitical tensions are most acute. Through this lens, pushbacks are not merely a border management tool but a reflection of broader struggles over migration governance and accountability.

Firstly, it is essential to examine how this grey area is addressed within the framework of international law and Turkey's national legislation, as well as the legal justifications and violations it entails.

Due to the *de jure* illegal nature of the pushbacks, the national legal framework cannot be provided; however, at least the rejections at the border, as outlined in the Turkish legal framework, can be cited. The return-related border procedures described here as presenting the legal “alternatives” to pushbacks, while pushbacks are entirely illegal, informal, and covert, do have the legal instruments to refuse entry to, or return, non-citizens who arrive at the border (under conditions and with safeguards for the individuals concerned).

It is not possible for any country to explicitly legislate pushbacks due to their inherent nature, which often conflicts with international law. Pushbacks, by definition, involve forcibly returning individuals across borders without allowing access to asylum procedures or due process. Such practices inherently contravene principles enshrined in international legal frameworks, as mentioned above. Explicitly legalising pushbacks would, therefore, directly

contradict these binding international obligations, rendering it impractical and legally untenable for any country to formalise them through legislation. As a result, pushbacks typically operate in a legal grey area, often as informal practices rather than officially sanctioned policies.

There is no specific national legislation in Turkey explicitly regulating pushbacks. However, return-related border procedures under Turkish law are also relevant. These procedures can be categorised into two main types, as outlined in the LFIP and its Implementation Regulation (IR): rejection at the border and issuance of deportation decisions. These categories provide the legal basis for addressing irregular entry while outlining safeguards against potential violations of international norms, including the prohibition of refoulement.

Rejection at the Border

This procedure applies when a foreigner arrives at a border checkpoint (border gate) and undergoes an initial document check to determine eligibility for entry (LFIP, Arts. 5, 6, 7). If concerns arise during this process, a comprehensive control is conducted by law enforcement (LFIP, Art. 6/5; IR, Art. 6). This secondary control requires prior suspicion and cannot be carried out arbitrarily.

- **Duration:** The foreigner may be held for a maximum of 4 hours during this process, excluding time spent in judicial proceedings. If this period is exceeded, the foreigner's consent is required (LFIP, Art. 6/3).
- **Rights and Safeguards:** The procedure must respect the foreigner's security and privacy, and checks should take place near the passport control area. If entry requirements are not met, the individual is deemed inadmissible (INAD) and returned to their country of origin by the carrier, following written notification. Judicial review is available as this is considered an administrative act (LFIP, Art. 6/3; IR, Art. 6).
- **Prohibition of Refoulement:** Under LFIP, Art. 4, authorities must ensure compliance with the principle of non-refoulement throughout this process. Additionally, Art. 8 of the LFIP mandates that border procedures must not prevent individuals from applying for international protection.

Issuance of Deportation Decisions

For individuals violating or attempting to violate entry requirements, deportation decisions, rather than rejections at the border, are typically issued (LFIP, Art. 54/1/h). This applies even when the violation occurs at border points lacking official gates or when irregular entry is attempted.

- **Scope of Violations:** In 2019, the law expanded to include "attempted violations", allowing deportation decisions even if a person does not physically cross the border. However, the term "attempted violation" remains undefined in legislation, creating ambiguity about its application.
- **Legal Safeguards:** Although this framework may offer protection against pushbacks and collective expulsions, the lack of clarity around "attempted violations" raises concerns about its scope and implementation.
- **Accelerated Procedures:** If the individual is deemed to require international protection, their application may be processed under the accelerated procedure instead of the standard process. Two provisions in LFIP, Art. 79, support this:
 1. The individual is under administrative detention pending deportation (LFIP, Art. 79/1/ç). Administrative detention is justified if there is a risk of absconding, a violation of entry/exit rules, or a pending deportation decision.
 2. The application is perceived as an attempt to delay or prevent deportation. However, the law provides no clear criteria for assessing such cases.

Intersection of Border Procedures and Pushbacks

Although Turkish law lacks explicit regulations for fast-track border procedures in international protection cases, the legal framework for handling irregular entries de facto establishes such practices. For instance:

- Foreigners who violate or attempt to violate entry laws are likely to face administrative detention and expedited processing.
- Legal provisions emphasise the principle of non-refoulement; however, the practical application remains a challenge due to unclear definitions and procedural ambiguities.

The legal framework in Turkey outlines comprehensive procedures for border management, including safeguards against refoulement and provisions for judicial review. However, the lack of clarity in certain terms, such as ‘attempted violation’, and the discretionary use of accelerated procedures create a grey area in the legal handling of irregular migrants. This ambiguity highlights the need for clearer guidelines to ensure compliance with both national and international standards, while addressing issues related to pushbacks and deportation.

4.3.1. Pushforwards

Regarding the movement from Europe to Europe, the fieldwork showed that rather than pushbacks¹³³, Turkey’s migration governance policies and practices align more closely with ‘pushforward’ strategies than direct expulsions (pushbacks). These practices systematically redirect them to other regions, push them into irregular status, or force them to remain in constant motion, ultimately obstructing their access to secure and permanent legal status, as first observed at the Pazarkule Event in 2020.

The concept of pushforward strategies in migration control—where states indirectly compel migrants to move toward third countries, either by facilitating their passage or through coercive measures—has been explored in academic literature. While pushbacks—direct expulsions at borders—have received significant attention in discussions on migration control, pushforwards represent a more complex and legally ambiguous strategy that warrants further examination. As discussed earlier, pushbacks have been widely documented at the EU’s external borders, particularly in the context of preventing irregular migration. However, within Europe, where formal return and readmission agreements regulate the movement of migrants between states, the mechanisms used to indirectly pressure migrants into leaving rather than outright expelling them remain underexplored.

Push-forwards in migration governance are indirect, state-led measures that pressure migrants to continue moving toward another territory without formalised removal procedures or direct expulsions.¹³⁴ Unlike pushbacks, which involve immediate physical expulsion or denial of asylum, pushforwards rely on security practices, administrative barriers, and indirect coercion to displace migrants and, in the case of Turkey, force them to push migrants into unsafe third countries.

¹³³ There are claims regarding pushbacks at the Eastern borders, in particular for Afghans towards Iran. For further information, Gökalp Aras, N. E, Yüksel, U. Ünay, H. and Öztürk, N. Ö. (2025). “Return Migration from Turkey to Syria and Afghanistan”. WP4 Country Report in GAPs: Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. DOI:

¹³⁴ N. Ela Gokalp Aras, “The Politics of Care and Control: Governmentality in Turkey’s Evolving Border Policy with the Reflections from Turkey-EU Borders.” *Journal of Borderlands Studies*, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08865655.2024.2428636>

Pushforward practices are conceptually linked to the broader mechanisms of migration control and externalisation policies.¹³⁵ They typically occur in regions where blurred jurisdictional boundaries, legal ambiguities, and contested asylum frameworks characterise migration governance. Scholars have highlighted how these strategies fit within the framework of ‘buffer zones,’ where destination states pressure transit countries to prevent the onward movement of migrants.¹³⁶

In Turkey’s irregular migration management, it has been observed that migrants subjected to pushback practices are, in certain cases, redirected to other regions through pushforward strategies. The concept of pushforward can manifest in different ways, including the physical redirection of migrants to another border or country, their displacement to transit areas, or the strategic relocation of irregular migration to third countries.

In this context, Turkey’s migration policies dynamically employ both pushback and pushforward strategies to manage irregular migration. The fieldwork conducted at the Turkey-Greece and Turkey-Bulgaria borders (Edirne and Kırklareli) showed that there are three pushforward practices in Turkey:

Pushforward Following Pushbacks: Turkey, at times, redirects migrants who have been pushed back from border countries such as Greece or Bulgaria to internal regions or alternative border crossing points.¹³⁷ This process may involve migrants being steered toward Turkey-Greece and Turkey-Bulgaria border crossing points again or being facilitated in their onward movement to another country. Turkey has, at times, used irregular migration as a means of leverage in negotiations with the EU. By selectively opening its borders and allowing migrants to move toward Europe, Turkey has applied a political pushforward strategy.¹³⁸

Relocation of irregular migration stock to third countries: The fieldwork also revealed that the relocation of irregular migration to third countries is another means of advancing the process. To manage irregular migration and alleviate border pressures, Turkey actively directs certain migrant groups to third countries.¹³⁹ In this case, pushforward practices are not limited to migrants pushed back from Greece or Bulgaria; rather, they also encompass the redirection of individuals who are already present irregularly in Turkey. Among these, some may belong to the first category—those that have been previously subjected to pushback by these two countries. However, identifying such individuals within the broader irregular migrant population in Turkey remains challenging. At present, without a comprehensive quantitative study, it is not possible to systematically determine the extent or specific characteristics of this group.

¹³⁵ Leonard, S., and Kaunert, C., “The Securitisation of Migration in the European Union: Frontex and its Evolving Security Practices”, *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 00(00), 2020, pp. 1-13. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369183X.2020.1851469> (Accessed 10 March 2025).

¹³⁶ FitzGerald, D. S., *Refuge Beyond Reach: How Rich Democracies Repel Asylum Seekers*. Oxford University Press, 2019; Geddes, A., Maru, M. T., & Lixi, L. “The EU’s New Pact on Migration and Asylum: What Role for External Governance? Migration Policy Centre”, European University Institute, 2020. Available at: <https://www.asileproject.eu/the-new-pact-on-migration-and-asylum-and-african-european-migration-diplomacy/> (Accessed 10 March 2025).

¹³⁷ Baird, T., and van Liempt, I., “Scrutinizing the double disadvantage: Knowledge production in the messy field of migrant smuggling” *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 42(3), 2020, pp. 400–417, <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369183X.2015.1103172>

¹³⁸ B. Kasperek, “The European border regime and the governance of migration in Greece”, *Journal of Borderlands Studies*, 35(4), pp. 563-579, 2020.

¹³⁹ Ayşe Üstübcü, “The governance of international migration: Irregular migrants’ access to right to stay in Turkey and Morocco”, 2020, *Comparative Migration Studies*, 7(1), pp. 1-21.

But for both cases, the state actively enables or encourages migrants to move toward a third country without physically expelling them. This can involve providing logistical assistance, such as facilitating transportation to another country or loosening border controls selectively to allow movement in a specific direction. While this may appear as a voluntary movement, it often occurs in a context where migrants have few or no viable alternatives, making it a form of indirect coercion rather than a genuine choice. In both cases, migrants may be physically escorted toward the border of another country without formal deportation procedures, creating a legal grey area in terms of state responsibility.

Forced pushforward: Unlike facilitated movement, forced pushforward involves indirect pressure that compels migrants to enter a third country. This can take the form of denying legal status, withdrawing basic services, detaining migrants in precarious conditions, or applying security and administrative pressures that render staying impossible. In some cases, migrants may be physically escorted toward the border of another country without formal deportation procedures, creating a legal grey area in terms of state responsibility.

Pushforwards challenge the clear-cut categorisation of forced and voluntary movement, as they often involve indirect coercion, such as the withdrawal of basic services, administrative hurdles in asylum processes, and targeted security enforcement that forces migrants to seek alternative routes or facilitates their crossing of further borders. Scholars have emphasised that these practices contribute to migrants' legal precarity and heighten the risks associated with secondary movements, often without adequate protection mechanisms in place. Bialasiewicz¹⁴⁰ discusses how externalisation strategies, such as the creation of buffer zones, can lead to increased vulnerability among migrants as they are kept in transit countries with insufficient legal protections. Similarly, Carrera and Guild¹⁴¹ analyse how EU migration policies that outsource border control to neighbouring countries result in precarious conditions for migrants, exposing them to risks without proper safeguards. These practices contribute to migrants' legal precarity and increase the risks of secondary movements, as inadequate protection mechanisms are not in place. However, the Pazarkule Event in 2020 was a different type of push forwarding, and during the fieldwork, the respondents stated similar ad hoc practices at the Turkey-Greece and Turkey-Bulgaria borders.

Since 2016, Turkey has intensified its role as a gatekeeper for migration into the EU, particularly through policies reinforced by the EUTRS. Turkey's strategy of pushing forward is part of a broader migration management approach, which aims to reduce irregular migration. In early 2020, Turkey encouraged migrants to cross into Greece, increasing the flow to Evros and exacerbating the existing tensions. In addition to the pushbacks conducted by Greece, Turkey has engaged in its version of pushforwards, redirecting migrants back toward Greece. This is significant for Turkey's eastern border, where migrants from conflict zones such as Afghanistan cross into Turkey, only to be pushed forward toward the EU border. This layered system of control at both western and eastern borders places Turkey in a strategic role within the EU's broader migration containment policies, positioning it as both a transit and destination country for displaced populations. This type will be discussed further as part of the findings.

Regarding the pushbacks, creating a flowchart is inherently challenging because pushbacks often operate outside of legal frameworks and lack transparency. Unlike formal deportation

¹⁴⁰ L. Bialasiewicz, "Off-shoring and Out-sourcing the Borders of EUrope: Libya and EU Border Work in the Mediterranean", 2012, *Geopolitics*, 17(4), pp. 843-866.

¹⁴¹ S. Carrera and E. Guild, "Offshore Processing of Asylum Applications: Out of Sight, Out of Mind?", CEPS Paper in Liberty and Security in Europe, 2017, No. 83, Available at: <https://www.ceps.eu/download/publication/?id=9810&pdf=OffshoreAsylumProcessing.pdf> (Accessed 10 March 2025).

and voluntary return procedures, pushbacks occur extrajudicially, often through informal and ad hoc practices by security forces, making it challenging to standardise the process into a structured diagram. One key difficulty is the lack of official documentation and procedural steps. Unlike deportations, which involve identifiable administrative decisions, appeals, and detention procedures, pushbacks are often immediate, undocumented expulsions at borders, preventing any formal appeal or legal intervention. Instead of a structured decision-making process, pushbacks represent an arbitrary, extra-legal practice shaped by shifting political and security dynamics, making them inherently resistant to standardisation. Additionally, pushbacks are highly variable and context-dependent. The methods used vary depending on border locations, security conditions, and political directives. The lack of uniformity in how pushbacks occur makes it difficult to define clear decision points or sequential steps in a flowchart. Another challenge is the involvement of multiple actors, including border guards, military units, and sometimes third-country cooperation agreements, which function in a discretionary rather than a rule-based manner. Therefore, **Figures 19 and 20** underscore the dynamic and securitised nature of migration governance in the region, illustrating how border control, pushback practices, and migration flows intersect at the Turkey-EU migration corridor.

Figure 19: Return Migration Infrastructure Flow Map of Turkey (Pushbacks 1)

Source: Prepared by the authors based on the UNHCR (<https://data.unhcr.org/en/situations/europe-sea-arrivals/location/24489>) and the MoI official websites

Figure 20: Return Migration Infrastructure Flow Map of Turkey (Pushbacks 2)

Source: Prepared by the authors based on the desk and fieldwork.

5. Case study: Particular RMI in Turkey

This section examines return and readmission practices within the Europe-to-Europe migration framework, analysing Turkey's role in managing migratory movements under different policy mechanisms. The analysis is structured around two key aspects: pushbacks and pushforwards as a migration control strategy in Edirne at the Turkey-Greece border (also Kırklareli at the Turkey-Bulgaria border) and the operationalization of readmissions as a part of the EUTRS (2016) in İzmir (they were mainly transferred to the removal centre in Kırklareli) as a case of facilitated return.

While pushbacks have been widely documented at Europe's external borders, findings from İzmir and Edirne indicate that Turkey does not engage in systematic pushback practices along this route. Instead, migration control policies in the region align more closely with 'pushforward' strategies, mainly in Edirne, wherein migrants are indirectly pressured or facilitated to continue their journey toward alternative destinations. The state proactively assists or incentivises migrants to relocate to a third country without directly removing them from the country. This may include offering logistical support, such as arranging transportation for onward movement or strategically easing border restrictions to enable migration along a preferred route. This phenomenon necessitates a closer examination of how Turkey manages irregular migration through redirection rather than outright rejection.

In contrast, Izmir serves as a crucial transit point for implementing the EUTRS, which focuses on the return of irregular migrants from Greece to Turkey. Unlike the EUTRA (2013), which remains inoperative for third-country nationals (TCNs), the EUTRS (2016) was implemented in Izmir from March 2016 to March 2020. In this framework, this part explores how the pushbacks in Edirne, as a response to Greece's pushbacks, and the EUTRS function as a return mechanism in practice in Izmir, highlighting both policy enforcement and its implications for migrants seeking asylum or transit through Turkey.

By juxtaposing these two return mechanisms—pushforward in Edirne and the structured return process in the form of readmissions in İzmir—this section sheds light on how Turkey navigates its dual role as both a transit and a return country under the EU migration governance frameworks. The findings contribute to broader discussions on the differentiation between forced and facilitated return, the legal ambiguities surrounding migration control strategies, and the geopolitical implications of Turkey's role in Europe's return and readmission system.

5.1 Pushbacks and Pushforwards

5.1.1. Related Actors and Their Roles

5.1.1.1. At National Level

Turkey's institutional structure displays the characteristics of multilevel governance, with central state actors being the most crucial layer of multi-levelness.¹⁴² The complex structure of actors, layers, policies and execution capacities at central, local, and inter-regional levels indicates the country's dynamic nature of migration management. Especially after the transition to a presidential system in 2018, Turkey's governance structure became significantly more centralised. In the field of migration management, the Presidency and the Ministry of Interior (MoI) hold decisive authority. Notably, the PMM operates under the MoI rather than at the ministerial level, reinforcing hierarchical control. At the provincial level,

¹⁴² Zeynep Şahin-Mencütek, et. al, *Ibid.*, 2023.

PDMMs, such as those in Edirne, Kırklareli, or Izmir, cannot undertake independent actions without prior authorisation from the central administration, highlighting the top-down governance model in Turkey's migration management framework.

Due to the implementation of the EUTRS, the MoFA also needs to be mentioned, which handles bilateral cooperation and diplomatic dialogues with countries of origin, facilitating the preparation of travel documents.

Concerning the two selected return types, the Gendarmerie, Police, and Land/Coast Guard Commands also play significant roles. As part of the Turkish state architecture, these entities fall under the umbrella of the MoI, which is responsible for maintaining public order and security. The Gendarmerie primarily operates in rural areas, overseeing law enforcement and public safety, and plays a pivotal role in identifying and processing migrants in these regions. The Police handle similar responsibilities within urban settings, ensuring compliance with migration laws, and often execute security checks, address verifications and carry out referrals and transfers to removal centres where migrants may be held before their return. The Land and Coast Guard Commands focus on border security and control, intercepting illegal entries and exits, thus directly impacting the flow of migrants.¹⁴³

In terms of the IGOs, the UN, primarily through the UNHCR and the IOM, provides critical support for the protection and return of refugees. In particular, the UNHCR focuses on and analyses the pushback cases in Edirne and Izmir. The EU's role regarding Turkey's return policy can be summarised through its emphasis on keeping refugees within Turkey's borders. While the EU's funding has provided Turkey with the capacity to manage a large refugee population, it has also placed Turkey in a position where it must balance EU demands with domestic pressures. The EU significantly shapes Turkey's return policy for Syrians and Afghans through financial assistance, infrastructure support, and strategic policy frameworks. Since the EUTRS, the EU has provided substantial funding to strengthen Turkey's migration management capacity, with investments exceeding €11 billion for border security, asylum processing, and return infrastructure.¹⁴⁴

Figure 21 shows the general return-related actors and those at the local level in the selected cities where the fieldwork is conducted. The figure presents a mapping of actors involved in return processes in Turkey, illustrating the complex and multi-layered governance of migration returns. It categorises actors into migrants, state institutions, civil society organisations, international NGOs, intergovernmental organisations, and supranational entities, such as the EU. This diverse network reflects how migration governance extends beyond state control, involving multiple stakeholders with competing interests and roles.

Critically, this mapping highlights that return migration is not a singular, state-driven process, but a complex field of governance shaped by intersecting legal, political, humanitarian, and informal actors. The inclusion of both enforcement and humanitarian organisations raises questions about whether returns are managed as protection-based processes or as securitised mechanisms of migration control. Moreover, the involvement of local actors and informal networks highlights the blurry line between official return processes and irregular pushback dynamics, making it essential to scrutinise how return policies are implemented in practice.

¹⁴³ Ibid.

¹⁴⁴ Zia Weise, et. al, "The EU is helping Turkey forcibly deport migrants to Syria and Afghanistan", *Politico*, 11 October 2024, Available at: <https://www.politico.eu/article/the-eu-is-helping-turkey-forcibly-deport-migrants-to-syria-and-afghanistan/> (Accessed 17 October 2024).

Figure 21: Actors Related to Returns and Readmission

Source: The authors prepared based on the desk research and the conducted fieldwork.

5.1.1.2. At the Local Level

In Edirne, the governance of migration, particularly in relation to responding to pushbacks and also pushforward practices, involves a complex network of state and non-state actors operating at multiple levels. State actors play a dominant role in managing migration through border enforcement, administrative policies, and coordinated responses to irregular crossings. In contrast, non-state actors, including international organisations, NGOs, and smuggling networks, operate within this contested space, often either mitigating the consequences of migration control or facilitating irregular movement.

As was previously mentioned, at the national level, the PMM in Ankara serves as the central authority overseeing migration policies, including return and readmission mechanisms. It plays a significant role in coordinating pushforward strategies, particularly through administrative and legal frameworks that redirect migrants toward alternative destinations. At the provincial level, the PDMM in Edirne cannot act autonomously; therefore, it must align with the PMM.

At the provincial level, PDMM serves as the primary institution responsible for implementing national migration policies. This institution plays a key role in coordinating the management of migrants apprehended near the border, particularly in temporary detention, registration, and administrative removal processes. While PDMMs do not engage in direct border enforcement, they support pushforward strategies by restricting migrants' access to legal protections and redirecting them toward third-country movements rather than facilitating formal returns. In close collaboration with migration authorities, the Edirne Governorship and district governors oversee the implementation of local migration policy, ensuring coordination among security forces, border control agencies, and administrative bodies.

At the state level, the PMM and the PDMM in Edirne play a crucial role in administrative decision-making and migration control policies. While PDMM is officially tasked with migration management, its limited autonomy means that national-level directives from Ankara largely dictate its operations. This structural dependency results in PDMM indirectly contributing to pushforward mechanisms by limiting access to legal protections and redirecting migrants toward border areas rather than facilitating regular returns.

Similarly, the MoI General Directorate of Security (GDS) oversees law enforcement efforts, ensuring the implementation of migration control policies at the provincial and local levels. At the provincial level, responding to pushbacks (forced returns to Turkey by Greece) and pushforwards (preventing migrants from staying in Turkey but, in the case of this report, directing them towards the EU borders), security forces play a key role in border enforcement, executing policies aimed at preventing irregular migration, controlling border crossings, and enforcing national and international laws. In the case of Pazarkule events and related pushbacks, the respondents stated their role in encouraging departures, indicating that some security units may escort migrants towards border crossings, effectively pushing them forward into Greece or Bulgaria.

The Edirne Provincial Gendarmerie Command and Border Gendarmerie Units play a crucial role in controlling rural and border areas, particularly in regions with dense forests and the Meriç River, which serves as a key crossing point into Greece. These forces engage in both pushback and pushforward practices, physically intercepting migrants and attempting irregular crossings while also preventing them from settling in border areas, forcing them to return to urban centres like Istanbul. Additionally, the Edirne Provincial Police Department manages internal security operations related to migration, conducting raids on migrant settlements and detaining individuals found attempting to cross into Greece. Special forces, including Border Guards and Police and Gendarmerie Special Operations Units (Özel

Harekat), operate in high-risk zones near Pazarkule and Ipsala, engaging in the physical removal of migrants and blocking their movement to certain areas, thereby contributing to both direct expulsions and indirect displacement strategies.

Briefly, security forces—including the Gendarmerie, the Provincial Police, and specialised units such as border guards and commando forces—are pivotal in both restricting settlement and orchestrating indirect removals. Testimonies from respondents suggest that during the Pazarkule crisis, special operations units were actively involved in escorting migrants toward border crossings, thus functioning as operational enforcers of pushforward strategies. The Edirne and Kirklareli provincial governorships also play a significant role in migration control, ensuring coordination between administrative authorities, law enforcement, and humanitarian agencies in ways that shape the execution of pushforward tactics.

Given Edirne's geostrategic location as Turkey's northwesternmost land border with Greece and Bulgaria, the Turkish Armed Forces (TAF) also play a critical role in national border security. Unlike civilian law enforcement agencies such as the gendarmerie and border police, the military's presence is primarily focused on border defence, territorial integrity, and deterrence against unauthorised crossings. It is observed that the First Army Command, stationed in Thrace, oversees military border security operations, particularly in sensitive zones along the Greece-Turkey land border, where cross-border tensions and irregular migration movements frequently occur. The TAF's role is not in direct migration enforcement but rather in maintaining border stability, preventing illegal incursions, and supporting civilian authorities in crisis situations. The TAF, although primarily focused on border defence rather than migration enforcement, are also strategically present in border zones, adding a layer of deterrence against irregular migration. The testimonies further highlight that, beyond regular security forces, specialised military units such as commandos and paramilitary formations were deployed at key border points during the Pazarkule period, further reinforcing the state's active role in facilitating push-forward mechanisms.

During the fieldwork, it was alleged that, in addition to infantry units, special commando forces and special operations teams were deployed at the border before and after the Pazarkule Event, playing a role in Turkey's pushforward response to Greece's pushbacks at crossings. The quotations below provide information about the ad-hoc changes and the temporary actors during and after the Pazarkule Event.

"Before and after Pazarkule, not only infantry but also commandos and special operations teams arrived. The infantry doesn't really understand, but special operations and commandos are different. Now, it's not like that anymore—some special units remain, but it's nothing like the Pazarkule period. Even the infantry has changed; everything is much tighter now. In the past, buses full of people (migrants) would come from Istanbul, but not anymore. Back then, there were so many." (Interview with a border village mukhtar, April 2024, Edirne).¹⁴⁵

"There were infantry units stationed here (at the Greece-Edirne border). You can't even go fishing without permission. Now, commandos have arrived, and a heavy military presence is in place. You can't take a step in the village anymore. It's not like before. You can't walk around at night or even during the day. It's different now—no one can move freely unless they allow it." (Interview with a border village mukhtar, April 2024, Edirne)¹⁴⁶

Additionally, although primarily responsible for maritime migration enforcement, the TCGC indirectly supports border security efforts in Edirne by controlling migrant flows along the Aegean coast and ensuring that intercepted migrants are returned to Turkey rather than

¹⁴⁵ SRII_W3_Meso-Level Interview_Edirne-09

¹⁴⁶ SRII WP3 Meso-Level Interview, Edirne-06

reaching EU territory. The TCGC plays a limited but strategic role, primarily in the monitoring of riverine crossings along the Meriç River, which forms a natural border between Turkey and Greece. While the Coast Guard is primarily tasked with maritime migration enforcement in the Aegean, its units occasionally assist in surveillance, search-and-rescue operations, and interception of migrant movements along inland waterways, particularly in coordination with border security forces.

The Edirne Governorship is another important state actor. According to Article 11 of the Provincial Administration Law, the governors are in command of all the public and private law enforcement actors within provincial borders (Law #5442, 1949). All officers are obliged to fulfil the orders issued by the Governor immediately. According to the same law, Governors have the authority to ensure security in civil airfields, ports, and border gates to facilitate the regular and effective execution of duties and services related to entry and exit, to ensure cooperation and coordination between the responsible organisations, and to take the necessary measures and implement them.

Municipalities in the border regions mainly provide the first level of emergency and humanitarian aid, depending on their location and closeness to border-crossing points.¹⁴⁷ In terms of pushforwards, the respondents claimed the role of mukhtar and the coordination of different state actors. Regarding the local government's role, including that of the Edirne and Istanbul Governorships, the quote below explains the collaboration among various actors.

“...local authorities, including village mukhtars and governors, come together, and the governor’s office provides significant assistance for border-crossings. They distribute thermal blankets, food, clothing, and other essential items. In some cases, the scale is quite significant—one smuggler, for instance, said, ‘I moved seven buses in a single day.’” (Interview with an NGO representative, June 2025, Istanbul)¹⁴⁸

Beyond state actors, IGOs play a critical role in migration governance. The UNHCR is involved in monitoring border practices and advocating for the protection of asylum seekers in Edirne. It actively documents cases of pushbacks and forced removals, but despite the interviews, we had no access to that data. On the other hand, at the time of the fieldwork, the IOM offices in Edirne were closed. The interview with the Izmir IOM office stated that IOM initiated its operations in Edirne in response to the growing humanitarian needs at Turkey’s northwestern land and maritime borders. However, after the COVID-19 period, when the situation at the border settled down, the office closed. Working in coordination with its Izmir office, IOM has collaborated with law enforcement agencies and migration management authorities to provide assistance, pushbacks, and support to migrants and refugees in the region. However, it no longer has representation in Edirne.

Additionally, Turkish NGOs, including ASAM and Refugee Rights Turkey (RRT), provide legal assistance, psychological support, and humanitarian aid to migrants in Edirne, while also supporting Kırklareli, and simultaneously document human rights violations related to border enforcement practices. The ASAM has been present in the region for a long time, particularly during the 2020 Pazarkule Process, with humanitarian aid activities for migrants and a diverse range of human resources.¹⁴⁹ The ASAM plays a crucial role in addressing pushbacks by Greece in Edirne while maintaining a strong operational connection with Istanbul. In Edirne, ASAM conducts field assessments in key border areas, documenting pushback incidents and

¹⁴⁷ N. E. Gokalp Aras, and Z. Sahin Mencütek, "Border Management and Migration Controls Turkey-Country Report", 2019, *Multilevel Governance of Mass Migration in Europe and Beyond Project* (#770564, Horizon2020) Report Series, available at <https://respondmigration.com/wp-blog/border-management-migration-controls-turkey-report>

¹⁴⁸ SR11_WP3_Meso-Level Interview_Istanbul_02 (with a nation-wide NGO representative).

¹⁴⁹ <https://sgdd.org.tr/en/about-us-2/>

monitoring irregular migration flows. It provides humanitarian assistance, including food, clothing, and interpretation services, to migrants affected by pushbacks. Additionally, ASAM engages in advocacy and reporting, highlighting violations and advocating for the rights of migrants. The strong link between Istanbul and Edirne allows ASAM to respond effectively to migration challenges, ensuring a comprehensive approach to addressing pushbacks and forced returns.

The RRT has been actively working in Edirne since 2018 to address pushbacks and forced returns, providing legal assistance, monitoring, and advocacy for migrants and asylum seekers.¹⁵⁰ The Association assists individuals held in the removal centres in Edirne and Kırklareli, ensuring their rights are upheld as part of the legal support mission. For legal support, RRT has the Administrative Detention Support Hotline. For monitoring and reporting, it observes pushback practices at the Greek and Bulgarian borders, documenting violations and collaborating with relevant institutions. Additionally, they challenge unlawful administrative decisions related to international and temporary protection cases through the case law database, which serves as a legal resource for similar cases.

Most importantly, they conduct on-the-ground assessments of irregular migration flows and return mechanisms, which contribute to the protection of refugees' rights in Edirne, particularly in the context of increasing border control measures and restrictive migration policies. During the interviews, it was stated that rather than directly processing legal aid requests, the Edirne Field Office operates in coordination with RRT's Istanbul Headquarters, specifically through the Administrative Detention Support Unit. This unit is responsible for assigning legal assistance based on requests received from Edirne and Kırklareli.

The respondents emphasised the changes since Pazarkule and the current rise in Edirne and Kırklareli (a temporary reduction in Edirne, followed by an increase, and a current significant increase in Kırklareli).

"Up until the Pazarkule process, it was extremely busy. The number of apprehensions was consistently reported and widely publicised in the media. Eventually, border activity became highly visible, both at the Kırklareli-Bulgaria border and the Edirne border. Following the Pazarkule process, the pandemic emerged, and media coverage of the issue declined significantly. Attempts to cross the border dropped considerably. During those two years of the pandemic, crossings were very limited, and from the meetings we held with other institutions, we know that there was a general slowdown. However, in the last one to two years—basically, since we returned to our offices and normal life resumed post-pandemic—there has been a noticeable increase in crossing attempts, as seen in the media. For Kırklareli, this may seem like a new phenomenon. The governor recently stated that Kırklareli is no longer part of the irregular migration route, but this statement is far from reality—it seems more like a wish than a fact." (Interview with an NGO representative, April 2024, Edirne).¹⁵¹

"Back in 2016, there was a somewhat 'let them pass' approach, albeit a controlled one. When I compare that period with 2023, I recall incidents where a clearly visible vehicle was simply turned back rather than apprehended. What you were referring to was perhaps a more subtle form of this. After Pazarkule, there was a period of relative leniency, but after 2023, the level of discipline in interventions changed dramatically. Now, the approach has become one of catching every bird that flies, meaning an extremely strict enforcement strategy." (Interview with an NGO representative, April 2024, Edirne)¹⁵²

¹⁵⁰ RRT. (2018). Available at: <https://mhd.org.tr/edirne-saha-ofisimiz-faaliyete-gecti/> (Accessed 4 March 2025).

¹⁵¹ SRII_WP3_Meso-Level Interview Edirne_02 (with a nation-wide NGO representative).

¹⁵² SRII_WP3_Meso-Level Interview, Edirne-01

The Edirne Bar Association is another critical non-state actor. There is a "Migration and Asylum Commission" within the Bar Association, and 12 lawyers work under this commission.¹⁵³ However, while the Edirne Bar Association holds a significant position in the region's legal landscape, there have been observations and statements from NGO representatives regarding its limited engagement in certain areas. Additionally, the respondents from Izmir, due to the lack of support from the Edirne Bar Association, despite the physical distance, lawyers from this city support many cases regarding deportations and administrative detention.

“But Edirne is very interesting. I went there this summer due to two or three cases—actually, I had been there four or five times in the past as well. Thankfully, we won the case there. But it is strange, almost like *The Silence of the Lambs*—there’s no one, no lawyers. We had to travel from Izmir several times. They are within walking distance, yet they don’t get involved.” (Interview with a lawyer from Izmir, January 2024, Izmir).¹⁵⁴

However, alongside humanitarian organisations, smuggling networks and informal facilitators also play a major role in shaping migration patterns in the region. Human smuggling networks operate within Edirne’s border zones, assisting migrants in navigating informal crossing routes into Greece, particularly along the Meriç River and remote forested areas. These networks, often run by local middlemen and corrupt facilitators, exploit the vulnerability of migrants by charging excessive fees for transportation and guidance. Additionally, informal brokers acting as ‘local guides’ play a crucial role in organising unauthorised crossings, capitalising on both state enforcement gaps and migrants’ desperation to reach European soil.

In the context of pushforward strategies, human smugglers play a pivotal role in facilitating the onward movement of migrants who find themselves unable to settle legally or access protection mechanisms within a given territory. Smuggling networks become instrumental in this process, as they provide the logistical means for migrants to move onward when states actively discourage settlement through legal, administrative, and security-driven restrictions. However, during the Pazarkule crisis, the interviewees claimed that state authorities in Turkey demonstrated a selective tolerance toward human smugglers, allowing their activities to operate with minimal interference as part of a broader pushforward strategy. Rather than outright facilitating irregular migration, the state's approach reflected a calculated non-enforcement stance, in which smuggling networks were not actively dismantled, effectively enabling migrants to attempt crossings into Greece with the assistance of informal facilitators.

The findings revealed that smuggling networks operate at multiple scales, ranging from transnational organisations that manage large-scale movements across regions to localised facilitators who provide more immediate passage across specific border areas. Their role in pushforward dynamics is particularly visible in contexts where states engage in non-refoulement-compliant deterrence strategies, such as withholding legal status, restricting access to services, increasing policing, and forcibly relocating migrants away from key transit hubs. In such environments, smugglers effectively fill the gap left by inaccessible legal migration pathways, providing alternative-but often exploitative—routes for those who have been systematically excluded from formal protection regimes.

Human smugglers are both a consequence and a catalyst of pushforward strategies. While their activities are inherently outside the bounds of formal migration governance, their role is deeply embedded in the broader political economy of migration control. One key way in which human smugglers were able to operate during the Pazarkule event was through the relaxation

¹⁵³ <https://www.edirnebarosu.org.tr/Detay/goc-ve-iltica-komisyonu-119779>

¹⁵⁴ SRII_WP3_Meso-Level Interview Izmir

of policing measures in key transit areas, particularly in Istanbul and Edirne, which served as major staging points for migrants seeking to reach the border. During the fieldwork, statements were also made regarding the presence of various actors who supported the pushforward process during the Pazarkule events, but whose exact institutional or group affiliations could not be identified.

In addition, local actors play an important role in the pushback and pushforward processes of immigrants. Local vendors, especially villagers, human smugglers, taxi drivers, bus companies and jewellers, are among these actors.

"In the village, smugglers are well-known. Every village has its two or three smugglers. Everyone knows who they are. Smugglers play a crucial role in this operation, but they are highly organised and operate within a massive network. They have connections in Istanbul. There are also smaller subcontractors in Edirne—people who provide services such as phone repair, taxi services, and others. This business has a place in the local economy." (interview with an NGO representative, April 2024, Edirne).¹⁵⁵

"Some of those involved in smuggling before eventually took on other jobs. Of course, these people also rowed boats, got on dinghies, and even inflated them. But in my village, thank God, this never happened. Back then, the governor had said something about this—offering a can of gasoline to boatmen or a daily wage, something like that. Some incentives were given at that time to facilitate crossings. In the end, even fuel was provided to boatmen so they could take people across (to Greece). That was how things were back then." (Interview with a border village mukhtar, April 2024, Edirne)¹⁵⁶

One of the key findings of the fieldwork is the presence of a multi-actor structure that responded to Greece's pushbacks with pushforwards, particularly during and for some time after the Pazarkule process. This can be seen as a return response to the increasing pushbacks at a time when the Statement was no longer functioning effectively. Like pushbacks, pushforwards operate in a grey area; however, while interviewees mentioned dozens of buses arriving from Istanbul, suggesting a tacit tolerance for these crossings, NGO representatives working in the region interpreted this as a different strategy for controlling irregular migration. At this point, the active involvement of existing human smugglers in the villages is evident in the following excerpts from interviews.

"What happened to them after that, we don't know. Those whom Greece pushed back—we helped them, fed them, and then sent (*salladik*) them forward again (which corresponds to push-forward operations). (Interview with a human smuggler from a border village, April 2024, Edirne)¹⁵⁷

"My job was to send them across. God knows, and so do the villagers. We did this for years, but back then, we tried to stay out of sight. Then, they declared it legal—crossing people over was allowed. I don't know how they recorded my job description, but my work involved assisting migrants. They paid me a wage of around 2,000 to 2,500 liras per month. They paid us for seven months, then it ended." (Interview with a human smuggler from a border village, April 2024, Edirne)¹⁵⁸

The relationship between Edirne and Istanbul, particularly in terms of border crossings, has been well-known for many years. However, during the Pazarkule process, it was noted that not only migrant smugglers but also state actors coordinated with Istanbul. The significance of Istanbul as a major transit hub was emphasised.

"In Istanbul, the ones who had been sent back from here were picked up and taken back to Istanbul by car. In some of the nearby villages, cars were waiting—we saw them there. But

¹⁵⁵ SRII_WP3_Meso-Level Interview_Edirne_01

¹⁵⁶ SRII_W3_Meso-Level Interview_Edirne-05

¹⁵⁷ SRII WP3 Meso-Level Interview, Edirne-05

¹⁵⁸ SRII WP3 Meso-Level Interview, Edirne-07

that has stopped now. They come from everywhere, but most of them are gathered in Istanbul before arriving here." (Interview with a mukhtar of a border village, April 2024, Edirne)¹⁵⁹

"Yes, now it has really stopped. They are gone, but back then, there were so many of them. Some groups had as many as 100 or even 150 people. They came last summer; it was an intense summer. Yes, they came, but they were transported mostly by cars with Istanbul license plates. It was like a convoy. We couldn't even walk around the village. After Edirne, they were sent here. It still happens, but less now. And then, suddenly, it starts again." (Interview with a mukhtar of a border village, April 2024, Kirklareli).

In the border villages of Edirne, human smuggling has long been embedded within local economies and social structures, with longstanding community involvement in irregular border crossings. Unlike large-scale transnational smuggling networks, which operate through complex logistical chains spanning multiple countries, local facilitators in rural areas play a more direct and intimate role in guiding migrants across the border.

For decades, certain individuals in almost every village have facilitated irregular migration, leveraging their intimate knowledge of the terrain, security patrol patterns, and informal crossing routes. These local actors often function as small-scale service providers, arranging safe passage, temporary shelter, and transportation for migrants attempting to cross into Greece or Bulgaria. While the identities of those involved are often well-known within the villages, enforcement actions against them remain limited and sporadic, reflecting a degree of local normalisation and tacit tolerance of these activities.

The economic dimension of smuggling in these villages cannot be overlooked. Many rural communities near the border experience limited economic opportunities, making migrant facilitation a lucrative alternative source of income. Participation in smuggling varies widely, ranging from individual guides who personally lead groups across the border to larger informal networks that coordinate with urban-based smugglers in Istanbul or Edirne. These localised actors sometimes operate independently, while in other cases, they are integrated into broader smuggling infrastructures, working under mediators who distribute payments and organise logistics.

Furthermore, the social fabric of these villages allows for collective involvement in human smuggling. In some cases, entire families or community groups participate, with different members specialising in various roles, such as providing food and shelter, monitoring security forces, or serving as lookouts during border crossings. This distributed nature of participation makes smuggling less visible and more resilient to law enforcement crackdowns, ensuring its continuity despite state efforts to curb irregular migration.

Ultimately, the role of local villagers in human smuggling in Edirne's borderlands highlights the blurring of formal and informal migration infrastructures. These actors function not only as facilitators of movement but also as key intermediaries between migrants, transnational smuggling networks, and state migration enforcement mechanisms. Their long-standing presence in the region underscores the deeply rooted, community-based nature of border economies, where migration control policies, economic survival strategies, and historical patterns of cross-border movement intersect.

In the context of pushforward dynamics in Edirne, taxi drivers have played a crucial intermediary role in facilitating migrant mobility, particularly in connection with human smuggling networks operating between Istanbul and the border region. As Istanbul serves as a key transit hub where migrants initially gather and seek passage toward Europe, smuggling

¹⁵⁹ SRII WP3 Meso-Level Interview, Edirne-08

networks rely on localised transportation infrastructures, including taxis, to manage and coordinate movement toward Edirne and its surrounding border villages.

Taxi drivers in Edirne have been observed to function as both independent facilitators and subcontractors within broader smuggling networks, transporting migrants from designated meeting points, such as bus stations, informal gathering hubs, or smuggler-coordinated locations, to key border crossing zones near Pazarkule, Ipsala, and the Maritsa (Meriç) River. Their role is particularly significant in pushforward scenarios, where migrants, unable to settle in Istanbul due to restrictive policies, are systematically funnelled toward alternative destinations, often with limited legal or humanitarian support. In these cases, taxi drivers serve as a critical link between urban centres and border regions, ensuring that migrants are transferred efficiently to locations where they can attempt to cross.

Furthermore, the economic incentives associated with human smuggling in Edirne have reinforced the entanglement of local taxi services with irregular migration flows. Many drivers operate within an informal economy, charging exorbitant fees for short-distance transport or coordinating directly with smuggling brokers who arrange clandestine border crossings. This highlights the intersection between local economic actors and transnational migration facilitation, where pushforward strategies—through administrative barriers, restricted asylum access, and controlled urban policing—indirectly sustain the demand for illicit mobility services.

Ultimately, the involvement of taxi drivers in Edirne's migration landscape exemplifies how state-imposed pushforward mechanisms interact with localised smuggling infrastructures, creating an ecosystem where migrants are systematically redirected rather than formally expelled. This dynamic underscores the fluid and adaptive nature of border economies, where both state policies and non-state actors shape migratory movements in ways that transcend formal migration governance structures.

"Now, the migrants who have been pushed back call a taxi from here and go to Istanbul. There is a central hub in Istanbul that directs all the money through a single system. Bringing people from there is forbidden, but taking them there is allowed. After all, how could they possibly track what happened here, whether they crossed or not? If they didn't make it across, we are here to take them back. The centre of this whole operation is in Istanbul." (Interview with a taxi driver for a border village)¹⁶⁰

In analysing pushforward practices from Edirne, it is crucial to recognise that these mechanisms are not solely confined to Edirne itself; instead, state actors based in Istanbul play a significant role due to their institutional capacity, administrative reach, and geographical proximity. Istanbul serves as a central hub for coordinating and operationalising migration control strategies, exerting influence over how migrants are directed toward or away from border regions.

A notable example of this centralised orchestration can be seen in the Pazarkule Event, where Istanbul-based state institutions and security agencies played a pivotal role in shaping the response and managing migrant movements. The event demonstrated how decision-making processes in Turkey's migration governance are not solely localised but rather embedded in a broader, hierarchical structure of state control, with Istanbul functioning as a command centre.

This complex network of actors suggests that pushforward strategies are not merely reactive measures to the pushbacks by Greece and Bulgaria at border sites but are, in fact, the outcome

¹⁶⁰ SR11_W3_Meso-Level Interview_Edirne-04

of a coordinated, multi-level governance framework. Istanbul's role, in particular, highlights the interplay between central and provincial migration authorities, demonstrating how migration control is structured not just through border enforcement but also through urban administrative mechanisms that influence migrant mobility even before they reach the borders.

In light of the above-given reflections from the fieldwork findings, the role of non-state and informal actors can be summarised as follows:

1. Humanitarian Organisations and Legal Advocacy Groups
NGOs provide legal aid, psychological support, and humanitarian assistance to migrants in Edirne and Kırklareli. They play an essential role in documenting human rights violations, advocating against pushbacks, and monitoring migration control practices. However, their ability to counter grey areas is limited due to legal and structural constraints, particularly the restrictive conditions in removal centres and the lack of access to detained migrants.
2. Human Smuggling Networks and Informal Facilitators
Smuggling networks and local facilitators (such as taxi drivers and village intermediaries) are deeply embedded in the migration economy of Edirne and Kırklareli. These actors exploit policy-induced vulnerabilities by offering transportation, logistical support, and guidance for border crossings, often in coordination with broader transnational smuggling networks.
 - Smugglers in border villages play a crucial role in organising irregular crossings, utilising their local knowledge and community ties to circumvent state enforcement mechanisms.
 - Taxi drivers act as intermediaries between Istanbul and Edirne, transporting migrants to key border zones while operating within informal financial and logistical networks.

One of the most striking findings from the fieldwork is the apparent selective tolerance of state authorities toward smuggling networks during the Pazarkule crisis. Respondents reported that, while official policies criminalise human smuggling, state actors at times deliberately avoided dismantling certain networks, effectively allowing smugglers to facilitate outward movement in alignment with Turkey's broader migration strategy. This tactical non-enforcement approach reflects a pragmatic use of informal actors in migration governance, reinforcing pushforward mechanisms as a response to Greece's pushbacks.

The fieldwork revealed that pushforward is a strategic tool for migration governance. The pushforward practices in Edirne and Kırklareli cannot be understood merely as ad hoc responses to Greece's pushbacks; instead, they represent a structured governance approach designed to redirect migration flows without overtly violating non-refoulement obligations. The fieldwork findings indicate that:

- Pushforward mechanisms are implemented through a combination of direct enforcement (escort operations, security patrols) and indirect coercion (withdrawal of legal protections, denial of services, and forced relocation).
- The coordination between Istanbul and Edirne is a crucial element in these strategies, with Istanbul serving as the primary hub for the mobilization and redirection of migrants toward border areas.
- The role of specialised military and paramilitary units in enforcing pushforward mechanisms suggests a shift toward a securitized approach to migration governance, where migrants are strategically redirected rather than formally processed for return or protection.

The analysis of migration governance in Edirne and Kırklareli reveals a complex and multi-layered system in which state and non-state actors interact within the framework of

pushforward strategies, particularly in response to Greece's systematic pushbacks. The findings from the fieldwork suggest that pushforward mechanisms in these regions are neither spontaneous nor isolated occurrences but rather tactically coordinated practices involving various governmental, security, and informal actors. This conclusion highlights the structural dimensions of pushforward practices, emphasising the role of key institutions, security forces, and locally embedded networks, such as smugglers, taxi drivers, and village intermediaries, in facilitating or enforcing onward movement.

The governance of migration in Edirne and Kirklareli reflects the broader tensions within Turkey's migration policy, particularly in the context of the EU-Turkey relations and the evolving dynamics of border control. While Greece's pushbacks have led to a heightened securitisation of border management, Turkey's pushforward strategies highlight a more complex and multi-actor approach that includes both formal and informal actors operating at different levels.

Ultimately, the findings from this study underscore the fragmented and hybrid nature of migration governance in Turkey, where legal, security, humanitarian, and smuggling networks intersect to shape mobility patterns. The use of pushforward mechanisms, whether through security-driven enforcement or selective toleration of smuggling networks, represents a strategic adaptation to the limitations of formal return policies. As migration pressures continue to evolve, understanding these multi-scalar governance structures will be essential for assessing the long-term implications of pushforward strategies within the EU-Turkey border regime.

5.1.2 Implementation/ Doings of RMI

Drawing on extensive field interviews conducted in Edirne and the surrounding border areas, this section explores the different roles played by state authorities, migration enforcement agencies, law enforcement, local governance structures, smugglers, taxi networks, NGOs, and international organisations in executing or resisting push-forward practices. While presenting the actors, a way of doing so was also provided for each actor. Therefore, the key points are provided here.

5.1.2.1. Actions by different actors

State Actors: The Institutionalised Enforcement of Pushforwards

Turkish Law Enforcement: Gendarmerie, Police, and Border Security Forces

The gendarmerie and police special forces are the primary operational enforcers of pushforward strategies. These actors are responsible for intercepting migrants at the border, processing them administratively, and ensuring they are either transferred to removal centres or funnelled toward the border rather than integrated into Turkey's asylum or protection system. The following quotations summarise the routine procedures in the selected entry points.

“At first, if the gendarmerie apprehends someone, they detain them. A report is issued stating that this person—or rather, the group—has been caught. The case file always includes a statement indicating that three to five people were apprehended, along with details on confiscated or secured belongings. All of these procedures are handled by law enforcement. They take individuals to the hospital for medical screening and then return them to hand them over to the Removal Centre. The process is conducted under the command of the gendarmerie, and once the individual is transferred to the Directorate of

Migration Management, an identification card is issued to confirm their identity.” (Interview with an NGO representative, April 2024, Edirne)¹⁶¹

There are claims that special police and gendarmerie units, particularly border patrol teams, are often involved in not only returning migrants to detention facilities but also in directing them toward crossings into Greece and Bulgaria. The quotation below reflects this argument.

“ We (referring to Turkey) push migrants back to Greece as if they had originally come from Greece to Turkey—do you understand? This is done to make it more visible. Especially around 2020, lawsuits were filed against Greece, as you know. I am aware of more than seventy cases that have been filed against them. Therefore, after these lawsuits, officials became more aware of the process. However, we also have our own initiatives in this field.” (Interview with an NGO representative, June 2024, İstanbul)¹⁶²

Migration Authorities: The PDMM and DGMM's Role in Administrative Pushforwards
The PDMM in Edirne and the PMM in Ankara play critical roles in executing pushforward policies at the administrative level. Their actions focus on processing irregular migrants through legal loopholes that ensure they do not remain in Turkey but rather self-deport to the EU.

" Once a deportation order is issued, individuals are sometimes transferred elsewhere, likely as a measure to manage caseload distribution and alleviate pressure on western provinces." (Interview with an NGO representative, April 2024, Edirne)¹⁶³

" Individuals often do not know what they are signing. They are required to sign numerous documents, including work and registration papers, as well as deportation orders. However, they are rarely informed about the decisions made against them or whether there is any legal recourse available." (Interview with an NGO representative, April 2024, Edirne)¹⁶⁴

In some cases, authorities intentionally delay legal processing or ensure that migrants do not have access to legal remedies within the required timeframe, which forces them into irregular channels.

" The seven-day appeal period for deportation decisions is highly restrictive, especially given that courts start counting this period from the moment the individual is irregularly notified." (Interview with an NGO representative, April 2024, Edirne)¹⁶⁵

" Previously, individuals caught leaving Turkey irregularly would immediately receive a deportation order. Technically, Turkey has the legal right to terminate protection for non-compliance with the relevant regulations. However, in practice, Turkey does not always enforce this, and procedures vary." (Interview with an NGO representative, April 2024, Edirne)¹⁶⁶

Non-State Actors: Smugglers, Local Intermediaries, and NGOs

Smuggling Networks and the Role of Local Actors in Pushforward Practices

Smugglers, transport networks, and local facilitators operate within the broader ecosystem of pushforward strategies. Rather than directly facilitating pushforward movements, the state's

¹⁶¹ SRII_WP3_Meso-Level Interview, Edirne-01

¹⁶² SRII_WP3_Meso-Level Interview, İstanbul-02

¹⁶³ SRII_WP3_Meso-Level Interview, Edirne-01

¹⁶⁴ SRII_WP3_Meso-Level Interview, İstanbul-02

¹⁶⁵ SRII_WP3_Meso-Level Interview, Edirne-02

¹⁶⁶ SRII_WP3_Meso-Level Interview, Edirne-01

strategic tolerance of smugglers ensures that migrants rely on irregular networks to continue their journey. The quotations below explain their role in terms of ways of doing things.

" Now, the migrants who have been pushed back call taxi drivers from here, hire a taxi, and go to Istanbul. Apparently, there is a central hub in Istanbul that directs all the money through a single system. Bringing people in from there is forbidden, but taking them to Istanbul is allowed." (Interview with a mukhtar of a border village, April 2024, Edirne)¹⁶⁷

" So, people were being pushed from both sides—sometimes from the Greek side, sometimes from here. At times, those pushed back by Greece were mixed with those brought from Istanbul." (Interview with a mukhtar of a border village, April 2024, Edirne)¹⁶⁸

The Role of NGOs and Legal Aid Organisations in Contesting Pushforwards

NGOs working in the migration sector face severe restrictions when intervening against pushforward practices. Legal representatives struggle to gain access to removal centres, and migrants often cannot access their rights due to procedural barriers.

" We submit petitions, but we rarely receive responses. Private security officers are not migration experts. We first have to explain the issue to them before they pass the information along to the relevant authorities." (Interview with an NGO representative, April 2024, Edirne)¹⁶⁹

" In large removal centres, the shortage of personnel is likely a contributing factor—these centres may be processing thousands of individuals at any given time, resulting in neglected notifications and delayed case processing." (Interview with an NGO representative, April 2024, Edirne)¹⁷⁰

As previously stated, pushforward can occur in different forms, and the distinctions between them are often quite blurred. In the case of forced pushforward, unlike facilitated movement, indirect pressure is exerted to compel migrants to enter a third country. This may involve denying legal status, withdrawing basic services, detaining migrants in precarious conditions, or applying security and administrative pressures that make it impossible for them to stay. The detailed excerpt below exemplifies this particular type of pushforward.

" These events now seem very distant, and we are living as if we never truly experienced them. However, the pandemic has still caused significant changes. In 2022, an accumulated population had settled here, and this population, at any cost, no longer wanted to stay. They had no access to registration, and it was a particularly chaotic period. The desire to leave was extremely strong, with powerful push factors driving them away." (Interview with an NGO representative, June 2024, İstanbul)¹⁷¹

The following quotation reflects the level of violence that migrants face at the borders during pushbacks.

" It was last year. They came (migrants) as if they were setting up a new homeland. We don't even see them while they're crossing. When Bulgaria pushes them back, they end up here. The men (Bulgarian border guards) throw them over the barbed wire walls. They beat them. They are covered in blood, devastated. They push them towards this side. They arrive naked. Sometimes, they have no shoes, not even underwear. They ask for help—some of us

¹⁶⁷ SRII WP3 Meso-Level Interview, Edirne-07

¹⁶⁸ SRII WP3 Meso-Level Interview, Edirne-06

¹⁶⁹ SRII WP3 Meso-Level Interview, Edirne-01

¹⁷⁰ SRII WP3 Meso-Level Interview, Edirne-02

¹⁷¹ SRII_WP3_Meso-Level Interview, İstanbul-02

give them shoes, others give them clothes. They are covered in blood, starving. We feel sorry, especially for the little ones." (Interview with a mukhtar of a border village, April 2024, Kırklareli)¹⁷²

Briefly, the pushback& pushforward mechanism in Edirne has proven to be a highly effective means of informal return. By ensuring that migrants face structural barriers to protection while simultaneously providing no legal alternatives, Turkish authorities encourage self-deportation or irregular crossings into the EU. However, this process also fuels smuggling networks, increases human rights violations, and reinforces state impunity in migration governance. The criminalisation of migration leads to greater exploitation, as migrants are left with few options other than relying on smugglers. Ultimately, pushforward strategies represent a hybrid form of migration control, blending formal state mechanisms with informal coercion, making it an essential feature of Turkey's migration policy.

How Effective Are Pushforward Strategies?

1. **Pushforwards as a Covert Return Mechanism**
Pushforward practices are highly effective as a means of informal return. Unlike formal deportations, which require bureaucratic and legal procedures, pushforwards coerces migrants into leaving without a formal removal order. By limiting migrants' ability to claim asylum or secure legal representation, pushforwards make departure seem like the only viable option.
2. **The Role of Structural Violence and Deterrence**
 - The presence of intensified security measures, combined with an intentional lack of humanitarian support, makes continued presence in Turkey unfeasible for many migrants.
 - Detention conditions and administrative barriers limit migrants' legal recourse, effectively discouraging them from seeking formal entry into the country.
3. **Unintended Consequences and the Smuggling Economy**
 - While pushbacks reduce formal deportation numbers, they fuel smuggling networks by increasing demand for illicit border crossings.
 - The criminalisation of migration leads to greater human rights abuses, as migrants are left with few alternatives but to rely on smugglers and corrupt networks.

The pushback& pushforward mechanism in Edirne reinforces structural violence, strengthens smuggling networks, and exacerbates vulnerabilities among migrant populations. They represent a hybrid form of migration control that blends formal governance mechanisms with informal coercion.

5.1.3. Materials and Technologies

5.1.3.1. At the National Level

The PMM has developed a comprehensive framework for managing migration, integrating robust technological systems, physical infrastructures, and international cooperation to enhance border security and manage migrant flows effectively. The strategic use of personnel,

¹⁷² SRII WP3 Meso-Level Interview, Kırklareli-04

advanced technology, and detailed policies aims to address the challenges posed by irregular migration and improve the overall management of migration in Turkey.

As outlined in the 2019-2023 strategic plan¹⁷³ by the PMM, the organisation employs a total of 4,051 personnel. This includes 1,621 permanent staff, 119 contracted employees, 162 service procurement workers, 888 temporary staff, and 1,262 permanent workers. The PMM operates through a central organisation and provincial units, headed by a Director-General, Deputy Director-Generals, 13 service units, and permanent boards and commissions. The provincial organisation comprises 81 provincial directorates and district group directorates, removal centres, temporary accommodation centres, reception and accommodation centres, and shelters for victims of human trafficking. The PMM is responsible for managing various physical structures and information technology resources, including¹⁷⁴:

- PMM international protection bureaus (decision centres) and mobile decision teams
- 30 removal centres with a total detention capacity of 22,140 individuals
- 81 provincial directorates and 35 district directorates
- Voluntary return offices at the border gates
- Coordination and Joint Risk Analysis Centre (NACORAC)
- Temporary accommodation centres
- 270 mobile migration points
- 67 verification centres for data updates of TP/IP holders

GöçNet, the migration database, integrates various inter-agency modules, including fingerprint and picture recording, restriction codes, language detection systems, and enhanced traveller recording systems.¹⁷⁵ It includes 26 modules: the e-Residence Module, Visa Module, International Protection Module, and Entry Ban Module. GöçNet provides comprehensive management of residence permit applications, visa processes, and international protection applications. YİMER 157 (Foreigners Communication Centre) offers 24/7 service in Turkish, English, Russian, German, Arabic, and Persian.¹⁷⁶

The Migration Board, led by the MoI, sets migration strategies, coordinates, and implements them, comprising representatives from various ministries and institutions. The PMM, authorised by Article 163 of Presidential Decree No. 4, can establish overseas organisations, including migration advisers at embassies and consulates. These advisers facilitate the deportation or voluntary return of irregular migrants, liaising with relevant countries to ensure smooth operations.

From 2019 to 2023, the MoI enhanced border security to combat terrorism and human smuggling. Key developments include:¹⁷⁷

- Constructing 230 km of security walls and patrol roads, totalling 1,160 km and also installing 227 km of razor wire systems on these walls (at the Turkey-Syria border)
- Building 23.5 km of stone-reinforced embankments, patrol roads, and high-security panel fences on the Turkey-Iraq border

¹⁷³ PMM, Ibid., 2023.

¹⁷⁴ Ali Yerlikaya (@AliYerlikaya), “81 ilimizde 270 adet mobil göç noktası aracımız hizmet veriyor”, 7 December 2024. Available at: <https://x.com/AliYerlikaya/status/1865277713839165820> (Accessed 28 February 2025); PMM, Ibid., 2024i; PMM, Ibid., 25 December 2022.

¹⁷⁵ PMM, “2023 Faaliyet Raporu”, 2024. Available at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/kurumlar/goc.gov.tr/Mali-Tablolar/FAALIYET-RAPORU/2023/2023-Yili-Idare-Faaliyet-Raporu.pdf> (Accessed 28 February 2025); Sayıştay, “2019 Göçnet Projesi Bilisim Sistemleri Denetimi Özeti”. Available at: <https://www.sayistay.gov.tr/reports/download/Xl3g485gKO-gocnet-projesi-bilisim-sistemleri-denetimi-ozeti-2019> (Accessed 28 February 2025).

¹⁷⁶ Sayıştay, Ibid.

¹⁷⁷ Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Interior, Ibid., 2024.

- Building 23.5 km of stone-reinforced embankments, patrol roads, and high-security panel fences on the Turkey-Iraq border
- Integrating 294 km of lighting systems and sensor systems along 368 km of the border
- Constructing 1,897 km of security roads, totalling 4,517 km
- Organising training sessions on integrated border management
- Building 151 elevator tower systems on the eastern and southeastern borders
- Completing 598 km of energy transmission lines
- Procuring 341 electro-optic towers, 284 thermal cameras, and 139 armoured border surveillance vehicles, funded by the EU

According to the Strategic Plan of the MoI¹⁷⁸, Turkey's return policies continue to evolve, with the capacity of removal centres reaching 22,140 as of 2023. The ratio of human trafficking victims returning to their source, transit, or third countries through voluntary and safe return programmes is 21%, a target also set for 2024 and 2025. The increase rate in voluntary and safe returns was 40% in 2022, surpassing the planned 15%. A 30% increase was recorded in 2023, with targets set for 2024 and 2025 at 20% and 20%, respectively. The target for deportations in 2022 was 53,000, but 90,000 foreigners were deported. Annual deportation targets for 2023, 2024, and 2025 are set at 50,000.¹⁷⁹

On the other hand, due to Edirne and Kırklareli being border provinces with Greece and Bulgaria, military units are stationed in these areas, and as a result, military checkpoints are present. Interviewees stated that, unlike in other provinces, Mobile Migration Points (MMPs) and Irregular Migrant Pre-Admission and Referral Centres (GÖKSEM) are not established in these regions. This absence was attributed to the presence of military control points, which serve as the primary enforcement mechanism for migration management in these border areas. However, it is important to mention them as significant new tools for the return infrastructure in Turkey. The MMPs were first piloted in Istanbul in 2022 and expanded to other provinces. These units operate 24/7, conducting identity verification for apprehended migrants, especially in high-activity regions. As of September 2024, 162 MMPs have been found in 30 cities.¹⁸⁰ GÖKSEM centres, established in February 2024, streamline the processing of irregular migrants, serving as hubs for admissions and referrals near removal centres. They collaborate with law enforcement agencies, such as the TCG, Gendarmerie, and police, to handle identification, legal processes, and humanitarian aid in a coordinated manner. These two new tools are particularly significant for controlling irregular migration and facilitating the rapid deportation of individuals.

¹⁷⁸ Ibid.

¹⁷⁹ PMM, Ibid., 2023.

¹⁸⁰ PMM. (2024c). “Gönüllü, Güvenli ve Onurlu Geri Dönüş”. Available at: <https://www.goc.gov.tr/gonullu-geri-donus> (Accessed 24 May 2024).

Photo 1: Mobile Migration Points

Source: Ordu Valiliği (2023). “Mobil Göç Noktası Aracı, Ordu’da Hizmet Vermeye Başladı”, 18 December 2024, Available at: <http://www.ordu.gov.tr/mobil-goc-noktasi-araci-orduda-hizmet-vermeye-basladi> (Accessed 4 February 2025).

Photo 2: Irregular Migrant Pre-Admission and Referral Centre (GÖKSEM)

Source: Konya Valiligi. (2024). “Valimiz İbrahim Akın, Düzensiz Göçmen Ön Kabul ve Sevk Merkezi’nde (GÖKSEM) İncelemelerde Bulundu”, 1 October 2024, Available at: <http://konya.gov.tr/valimiz-ibrahim-akin-duzensiz-gocmen-on-kabul-ve-sevk-merkezinde-goksem-incelemelerde-bulundu>; Habercim19. (2024). “Çorum’a GÖKSEM Kuruluyor”, 2 September 2024, Available at: <https://www.habercim19.com/yasam/corum039a-goksem-kuruluyor/79283> (Accessed 4 February 2025).

Figure 22 highlights Turkey’s highly securitised and technology-driven migration governance, emphasising surveillance, biometric tracking, and militarised border control. The integration of electronic monitoring, removal centres, mobile migration units, and biometric databases suggests a shift from protection-based policies to enforcement-focused migration management. While these measures enhance state control, they risk criminalising migration and limiting access to asylum, reinforcing a security-first approach over humanitarian considerations.

Figure 22: Capacities of Return Migration

Sources:

*PMM, "İçişleri Bakanımız Sayın Ali Yerlikaya Sınırlarımızdaki Üst Düzey Güvenlik Tedbirlerini Anlattı", 2024, available at:

<https://www.goc.gov.tr/kurumlar/goc.gov.tr/GOC-TV/2024/3-Mart/01-Mart/3Icisleri-Bakanimiz-Sayin-Ali-Yerlikaya-Sinirlarimizdaki-Ust-Duzey-Guvenlik-Onlemlerini-Anlatt.mp4> (Accessed 23 May 2024).

**PMM, "Göç İdaresi Başkanlığı 2019-2023 Stratejik Planı", 2023, available in Turkish at: https://www.goc.gov.tr/kurumlar/goc.gov.tr/Mali-Tablolar/STRATEJIK-PLAN-2019-2023/Stratejik_Plan_2019_2023-2.pdf (Accessed 24 May 2024).

5.1.3.2. At the Local Level

In the provinces of Edirne and Kırklareli, which share borders with Greece and Bulgaria, respectively, Turkey has implemented a range of technological measures to enhance border surveillance, manage irregular migration, and facilitate the return and readmission of individuals. These measures include the construction of physical barriers, the deployment of advanced surveillance systems, and the establishment of specialised facilities such as liaison offices and guest houses.

During the fieldwork, the physical barriers and surveillance systems were observed. To strengthen border security, Turkey has constructed physical barriers along its western borders. Specifically, at the Edirne-Greece border, the 2-meter-high panel fences, installed on 1-meter concrete blocks, were visible. These barriers are complemented by towers, cameras, and other security systems to enhance surveillance capabilities. As seen in **Photo 1**, concrete structures mark the Turkey-Greece border, and the barbed wire fences on the other side are also visible. However, when it comes to crossings, as mentioned in the previous section, all obstacles at the border are eventually overcome—if necessary, with the assistance of various actors.

Photo 3: Border Villages and Surveillance Towers (1)

Source: Photograph taken by the authors during fieldwork.

In the past, the most distinctive feature of villages was the mosque minaret located in the village centre, often near the village coffeehouse and main square. However, it has now been observed that in all border villages, technologically equipped towers, standing meters higher than the minarets, have become the dominant structures. During interviews, villagers expressed that they are constantly under surveillance and have lost certain freedoms compared to previous times, such as fishing and picnicking.

These towers, particularly those equipped with thermal and motion sensors, were described as having extensive surveillance coverage stretching for kilometres, making them a defining characteristic of the villages. Indeed, during the fieldwork, such towers were observed in all border villages. However, in villages with higher crossing activity, additional security measures and controls were more prominent, especially at village entrances, while in others, the presence of border stations was noted.

Photo 4 and **Photo 5**—taken during the fieldwork—illustrate the changing landscape of border villages, highlighting this transformation.

Photo 4: Border Villages and Surveillance Towers (2)

Source: Photograph taken by the authors during fieldwork.

Photo 5: Border Villages and Control Points

Source: Photograph taken by the authors during fieldwork.

The quotes below describe the perceptions of local representatives regarding the changing technological and physical infrastructure at the borders. They also stated the negative impacts of those changes on their daily lives.

“The cameras are watching. There are cameras connected to Ankara. There are cameras located outside the village, within the military area, and even further beyond. There are cameras everywhere. If you go down to the Meriç River, they can see you. They see you even from Ankara. They know where you are and where you came from. It’s not like before; it’s over now. You cannot go anywhere without permission from the military. Nothing happens

without the state's knowledge anymore." (Interview with a mukhtar of a border village, April 2024, Edirne)¹⁸¹

"You can't even go to a field (agricultural) without permission while the military is there. In the past, migrants used to have camps at the entrance of the village. At night, they would walk freely, passing through the gate. But now, all of that is over. Greece has put up fences and built walls. And it affected us too—now we are also restricted. If you go down to the embankment road, you will see infantry troops show up immediately. Are you going for a picnic? Planning to go down to the water? Not anymore. You need permission, even for fishing." (Interview with a mukhtar of a border village, April 2024, Edirne)¹⁸²

There are '*Tepegöz*' towers (local slang for surveillance towers), and they track everything. The moment there is movement, the soldiers arrive immediately. The entire border is monitored in this manner. Now, from here, they control vast distances. They even have thermal cameras—they see everything, even birds flying." (Interview with a mukhtar of a border village, April 2024, Edirne)¹⁸³

However, during the interviews, it was emphasised that despite all these measures, crossings continue regardless, as expressed by the phrase "water flows and finds its way." This highlights the insufficiency of the implemented measures and the persistence of migration despite all obstacles. However, it should be noted that during the interviews, while respondents drew connections between the current situation and the Pazarkule Event, their statements were not always entirely clear. What they seemed to express was that, compared to the previous fluidity and high numbers of crossings, security measures have now been significantly tightened. However, it is stated that despite the decline in Edirne, the overall increase in crossings suggests that Edirne's former role has, at least partially, shifted to Kırklareli.

"After the Pazarkule crisis, they installed new surveillance poles with cameras along the entire border. There are no blind spots anymore. From the village centre, you can see the buttons on a man's coat at the border. I once watched one of the feeds. I had the opportunity to see all of them. It's not like regular surveillance cameras—it's on a whole other level. You can no longer stand anywhere. Even if they build a solid wall, people will find a way to break through it or place a ladder. There is a huge profit in migration. Smugglers view this as a great opportunity, and massive expectations and dreams have been built around it. As long as this continues, I believe migration numbers will fluctuate—sometimes in the hundreds, sometimes in the tens or hundreds of thousands. But I'm not very hopeful." (Interview with an NGO representative, April 2024, Edirne)¹⁸⁴

"There is a seven-layer, maybe even an eight-layer fence (Turkey-Bulgaria border). If I cut through from one side and cross. These were all built on their land. They built them together with the European Union when the migration crisis began. People from the EU came here; they lined up at every border police checkpoint. It all started when migration from Syria began. Later, they pulled barbed wire toward our side. It's all German-made razor wire—it cuts anyone who tries to pass. But people still cross. If they cannot find anything, they cut down a tree, lean it against the fence, and climb over. Our village has become rich with stairs." (Interview with a mukhtar of a border village, April 2024, Kırkkale)¹⁸⁵

"At the border with Bulgaria or Greece, there is a six-layer, six-meter-high fence. They cut it with scissors, lean a ladder against it, and cross. There is always a way. They throw a carpet over it, then put a blanket on top of the carpet, and then another carpet on top of that. There is always a ladder. They leave ladders behind everywhere. They carry them with

¹⁸¹ SRII_WP3_Meso-Level Interview, Edirne-06

¹⁸² (SRII WP3 Meso-Level Interview, Edirne-06)

¹⁸³ SRII WP3 Meso-Level Interview, Edirne-07

¹⁸⁴ SRII_WP3_Meso-Level Interview_Edirne-01

¹⁸⁵ (SRII WP3 Meso-Level Interview, Kırklareli-02)

them. A ladder is brought in and taken away again. Sometimes, people leave behind scissors and ladders, but just to be safe, they bring their own. So, what difference do walls make? Smugglers will charge more as it gets harder, but people will still find a way to cross." (Interview with a border village mukhtar, April 2024, Edirne)¹⁸⁶

Photo 6: Border Villages and Border Stations/Checkpoints

Source: Photograph taken by the authors during fieldwork.

Collectively, these technological and infrastructural measures underscore Turkey's commitment to enhancing border security, managing irregular migration, and fulfilling international obligations related to return and readmission, particularly in key border provinces such as Edirne and Kirklareli.

Both provinces host Removal Centres (*Geri Gönderme Merkezleri*, GGM), which are integral to Turkey's strategy for managing irregular migration and implementing return procedures. These centres are designed to temporarily accommodate migrants who are subject to administrative detention prior to their deportation or voluntary return. They serve as a holding centre for migrants awaiting deportation or voluntary return, providing necessary services during their stay. These facilities serve as contact points for the readmission of third-country nationals and are used for interviews, consular contacts, and document collection until arrangements are made for transfer to removal centres or repatriation.

On the other hand, it has been stated that due to both cities being designated as first-degree military zones and their borders with two different countries, the MMPs are not present, given the existence of control points and military units. Similarly, in Edirne, the absence of a GÖKSEM structure is attributed to the presence of a Gendarmerie reception point/centre, which serves as a pilot example for the GÖKSEM implementation.

"We don't have a mobile registration (refers to MMP) unit here. There is no need because everywhere is already mobile. Hardly anyone stays in the cities. The number of Syrians in the area is recorded in the official statistics. I haven't checked recently, but I estimate it is around 600. Overall, there are around 500 here, so together, that's maybe 1,500 in total. For Edirne, we are probably talking about just one group. These numbers are estimates, as there isn't a permanent settlement that requires a fixed mobile migration point." (Interview with an NGO representative, April 2024, Edirne)¹⁸⁷

¹⁸⁶ SRII_WP3_Meso-Level Interview_Edirne-04

¹⁸⁷ SRII_WP3_Meso-Level_Edirne-01

"In Edirne, GÖKSEM functions somewhat differently. It seems more like an attempt to organise things systematically—to direct migrants toward official registration points and process them efficiently. But GGÖKSEM also acts as a mechanism to send migrants away. In that sense, the primary goal here is to empty Istanbul of migrants, make them turn anyway." (Interview with an NGO representative, June 2024, Istanbul).¹⁸⁸

"This structure is specific to Edirne and resembles an initial reception system. The purpose is to create a unit where law enforcement can directly transfer individuals, eliminating the need for lengthy processing times after their apprehension. This unit works in coordination with the PMM but is essentially under the jurisdiction of law enforcement. Perhaps the reason this is not widely discussed is that, after 2012, the PMM became a civilian institution. Even in Europe, law enforcement is more involved in handling irregular migration. However, there is no similar structure elsewhere in Turkey. In Edirne, this reception centre has been operational for approximately two to three years. Now, a similar structure is being established at the Pehlivan köy Removal Centre in Kırklareli." (Interview with an NGO representative, April 2024, Edirne)¹⁸⁹

5.2. The Readmissions as a part of the EUTRS

Since EUTRA has not been implemented for TCNs and no information was obtained regarding the readmission of Turkish citizens through either desk research or fieldwork, the report will still address the implementation of EUTRS for the sake of completeness, even if its application occurred before the GAPs Project. This serves as an important example for the focus of this report on returns from Europe to Europe, as well as for the readmission practices considered within the scope of forced return, which is analysed in the GAPs project beyond voluntary returns.

İzmir was considered the entry point for EUTRS. While the PDMM is a significant actor at the provincial level, the process appears to be a more centralised and non-transparent mechanism primarily coordinated by the PMM and the MoFA in Ankara. However, despite İzmir serving as the designated entry point, a significant portion of readmissions conducted under the EUTRS framework are ultimately transferred to the Pehlivan köy Removal Centre in Kırklareli. This interconnection between different locations in the field research indicates a functional linkage between multiple entry points within the operational framework of EUTRS.

Consequently, in terms of actors, the EUTRS operates within a more restricted operational framework. Given that the United Nations does not officially support the EUTRS and that it falls outside its mandate, its role remains limited. However, interviews indicated that, despite this formal restriction, both IOM and UNHCR provide support to state actors—particularly upon the arrival of readmitted groups—within the scope of their existing relationships. This support is akin to the assistance they offer to the Coast Guard, Gendarmerie, and Law Enforcement agencies in other border-crossing apprehensions, particularly in terms of humanitarian aid. On the other hand, the role of civil society organisations remains highly constrained. Furthermore, readmitted groups are systematically processed under the framework of forced return procedures, as extensively analysed in both this report and the WP4 Turkey Country Dossier.¹⁹⁰

As this dossier was being written, the EUTRS has completed its ninth year. Although Turkey suspended the implementation of the returns component in March 2020 and halted the

¹⁸⁸ SRII_WP3_Meso-Level Interview_Istanbul-02.

¹⁸⁹ SRII_WP3_Meso-Level Interview_Edirne-02

¹⁹⁰ Gökalp Aras, N. E. et al., Ibid. 2025.

readmissions of TCNs from Greece, the effects of the EUTRS and the expectations regarding its renewal remain prominent in both the political agenda and academic studies. Despite the suspension of the return component in March 2020 by Turkey, the EU kept its two promises regarding financial support (through the Facility of Refugees in Turkey/ FRIT as 6 billion) and the 1:1 resettlement scheme (to resettle a Syrian from Turkey to the EU for every Syrian being returned to Turkey from Greek islands), and still implementing. As of 4 July 2024, 67,441 Syrians have been resettled under the 1:1 resettlement scheme since 2016, representing a still small proportion of the total number of Syrians, which is estimated at 3.1 million.¹⁹¹ Also, since 2016, 2,140 migrants have been returned from the Greek islands to Turkey. However, Turkish authorities have maintained their March 2020 suspension of return operations, and no returns have occurred since then despite repeated requests from Greek authorities and the EC.¹⁹²

The EC's report¹⁹³ emphasises the significant efforts of Turkey to host and address the needs of more than four million refugees and mentions that "The Statement continued to deliver results in 2022". The report also highlights the increasing number of irregular arrivals and their significance, reminding us of Turkey's suspension of returns from the Greek islands. However, from both sides, publicly available data is limited. We do not know how many returned persons could apply or have been rejected for international protection in Turkey, what are the selection criteria for the 1:1 settlement scheme, whether the EUTRA could be implemented for the Turkish nationals or the TCNs, details about the EUTRA's and the EUTRS's suspension remain unclear, including the provisions of the Implementing Protocol between Turkey and Bulgaria.¹⁹⁴

There is no progress regarding visa liberalisation, full membership, the Customs Union or the Voluntary Humanitarian Admission Scheme.¹⁹⁵ The 7th EC Report mentioned the precondition for the Scheme, which "sustainably reduced irregular crossings between Turkey and the EU".¹⁹⁶ It seems the renewed priorities must be rediscussed as incentives for those who have lost their credibility, and to strengthen relations and cooperation.

Despite these unclear dimensions, the third fieldwork provided important preliminary findings for the EUTRA and the EUTRS. The number of interviews conducted with state actors is still limited. However, from the selected cities and the related meso-level actors, significant findings have been identified regarding the practices implemented during the return component up to March 2020 and future protections.

During fieldwork (January-July 2024), the primary focus at the meso level, particularly among non-state or IGO respondents, centred on the EUTRS, including its potential for renewal, foresight regarding new conditions for renewal, and its implications in Turkey. The most important finding regarding the consequences of suspension is the increased pushbacks and informal returns. One of the most significant impacts of the EUTRS's suspension has been an increase in informal returns, commonly referred to as pushbacks. Greece, facing a substantial accumulation of migrants at its borders, has resorted to unofficial pushback practices. These actions, while not legally sanctioned, reflect the practical challenges and political tensions

¹⁹¹ PMM. (2024). Temporary Protection. 4 July 2024. <https://en.goc.gov.tr/temporary-protection27> (Accessed 2 February 2025).

¹⁹² European Commission. (2023). Seventh Annual Report on the Facility for Refugees in Turkey. https://neighbourhood-enlargement.ec.europa.eu/seventh-annual-report-facility-refugees-turkey_en (Accessed 7 February 2025).

¹⁹³ Ibid.

¹⁹⁴ Ovacik, G., Inerli-Ciger, M, and Ulusoy, O. (2024). Taking Stock of the EU-Turkey Statement in 2024. *European Journal of Migration and Law*. 26 (20 24): 154-178.

¹⁹⁵ Ibid.

¹⁹⁶ European Commission, Ibid., 2023, p. 4.

surrounding the management of migration flows. While Greece's actions can be categorised as pushbacks, the term might not fully capture the nature of Turkey's response. Pushbacks typically imply the immediate expulsion of individuals attempting to cross the border. The respondents, mainly NGO representatives and locals in border cities, villages, and critical border-crossing points, generally claimed that despite suspending the return component, Greece continued its practice of pushbacks.

In contrast, the field study suggests that Turkey's actions involve not only expelling individuals but also facilitating their passage back towards Greece, a practice that might be more accurately described as a 'push forward' approach, as discussed earlier, which became publicly visible in 2020 (the Pazarkule Event) at the Turkey-Greece border. In the context of Turkey's response to these pushbacks, 'pushforward' seems to be a more fitting term, as it captures the idea that Turkey is not just returning individuals to their point of entry but is actively facilitating their movement back across the border into Greece. This proactive engagement goes beyond preventing entry and involves a deliberate effort to send individuals back through the border, reflecting a coordinated and systematic approach. Using the pushforward can help differentiate between the more passive act of pushback and the active role that Turkey appears to be taking in ensuring these individuals are returned to Greece. This term emphasises the ongoing cycle of returns and highlights the dynamic and reciprocal nature of the migration management practices between the two countries. The following quotes from the NGO representatives' interviews highlight pushbacks, non-refoulement violations, and critiques of the EU and MSs.

Actually, Greece discovered that unofficially conducting pushbacks was a practical and economical approach after the entry into force of the EUTRS. They also realised that the enforcement power of the EU, EU criteria, principles, UN resolutions, and the European Convention on Human Rights was ineffective. Turkey can respond to the questions and criticisms with, "Well, we learned this from Greece,". It would be understandable. (Interview with the representative of an NGO, 2024, Ankara).¹⁹⁷

Another NGO representative highlighted the reasons why the EUTRS could not be implemented and how hypocrisy can arise when EU interests are at stake, particularly in relation to human rights violations.

The EUTRS was not implemented and remained with only around 30,000 admissions. One of the reasons for this lack of implementation is the Greek authorities' limited capacity, but pushbacks reduced their migrant stock to Turkey. This situation is convenient for Greece and aligns with the broader EU perspective, which often prioritises EU interests before discussing human rights. For instance, when Süleyman Soylu stated, "Since 2019, we have stopped 2,560,000 people at the border," it essentially means that we have violated the principle of non-refoulement. Of course, this is also understood by the EU and human rights defenders within the EU. However, it means the EU borders are protected (Interview with an NGO representative, 2024, Ankara).¹⁹⁸

During the fieldwork, another significant finding was the foresight and perceptions about the renewal of the EUTRS. The state actors highlighted Turkey's expectation that the EU will support its cross-border development activities and expand the safe zone in northwest Syria for returns, in parallel with the findings of the second fieldwork. It was stated that non-state actors believe the 1:1 formula could be applied more effectively this time with Greece and that the EU and Turkey are in new and significant cooperation regarding returns. There is an expectation that the EU's financial and capacity support for Turkey's evolving and increasingly visible national return mechanism will be included in the renewed EUTRS.

¹⁹⁷ SRII_WP3_Meso-Level Interview_Ankara -02.

¹⁹⁸ SRII_WP3_Meso-Level Interview_Ankara -02.

Under the framework of the EUTRS, the new agreement is likely to establish a special relationship between Greece and Turkey regarding the Readmission Agreement and the new Statement. This policy is likely to develop primarily through the one-for-one formula directly between Greece and Turkey (Interview with an NGO representative, 2024, Ankara).¹⁹⁹

The following two quotes offer insight into Turkey's expectations of the EU, particularly regarding the return policy and, in particular, the new conditions for renewing the EUTRS.

After our military operations, we approached those regions entirely from a humanitarian perspective and made many investments. Gaziantep University has a School of Health Sciences in the area. We established an industrial zone in Çobanbey, and even last week, an international fair was held with the participation of businesspeople from various Arab countries. We have hospitals and health services in the region. We are creating educational and job opportunities. However, the region needs more investment. The EU and other Western countries need to support these safe zones. In Gaziantep alone, the number of people I am concerned with exceeds the number of refugees in Europe (Interview with a state official, 2024, Gaziantep).²⁰⁰

We [Turkey] requested that the ESSN (Emergency Social Safety Net)²⁰¹ support from the EU not be cut off when people return to Syria, and the EU did not accept our offer. These safe areas require more investment, and development in the region needs to be encouraged (Interview with a state official, 2024, Gaziantep).²⁰²

Regarding the financial dimension of the JAP and the EUTRS, the following quote highlights the unfair share of responsibilities and miscalculations and assumptions of Turkey.

In the Netherlands, the cost to the state for one person is 65 Euros per day. The annual cost for this person is approximately 23,650 Euros. For 1 million people per year, this amounts to 23 billion Euros. When considering a population of 4 million in Turkey at that time, this translates to approximately 100 billion Euros for one year. However, the amount offered to Turkey by the EU was 3+3 billion Euros. Turkey's biggest mistake is not doing these kinds of analyses and not sitting at the negotiation table. They act as if Turkey is obliged to host these people anyway (interview with an NGO representative, 2024, Ankara).²⁰³

Regarding the practices during the initial implementation of the return component of the EUTRS, the interviewed limited legal practitioners who had cases of the returnees as a part of the EUTRS stated that although the readmissions were operated only at a town called Dikili (close to İzmir, Turkey), later, there were two main removal centres (RCs) were used. It is noted that as of 1 April 2016. Initially, individuals were transferred from Greece's Lesbos Island to Dikili and were placed in Edirne and Kırklareli, two Turkish provinces. Pehlivan köy Removal Centre was specifically opened following the EUTRS. There were logistical and procedural issues in implementing the EUTRS, including the dual issuance of deportation orders by different administrative bodies, which led to legal challenges. For example, initial deportation orders issued by the Izmir Provincial Directorate of Migration Management were followed by additional orders from the Kırklareli Governorship, leading to court cases and subsequent annulments due to procedural violations. The process involved significant involvement from administrative and judicial bodies, and despite initial procedural setbacks,

¹⁹⁹ SRII_WP3_Meso-Level Interview_Istanbul-02.

²⁰⁰ SRII_WP3_Meso-Level Interview_Ankara -02.

²⁰¹ Code, The ESSN is the largest humanitarian cash programme that assisting over 1.5 million refugees, primarily individuals living under temporary and international protection in Turkey.

²⁰² SRII_WP3_Meso-Level Interview_Gaziantep -05. , See #8.

²⁰³ SRII_WP3_Meso-Level Interview_Ankara -02.

the practice continued with the transfer of individuals to return centres in a remote province, such as Kayseri, by mid-2017.

The respondents highlighted multiple instances of human rights violations, which were reported by them during the process, including forced deportations and inadequate consideration of asylum claims. Many individuals, particularly non-Syrians like Bangladeshis, Myanmarese, and Pakistanis, were subject to rapid deportations without adequate legal recourse. Specific cases highlight the lack of effective legal oversight and the potential for abuse, such as forcing individuals to sign voluntary return forms under duress and inadequate protection for those at risk of persecution.

The findings for this initial period showed that the EUTRS had faced numerous operational challenges, including the capacity limitations of Greek authorities to process returns, the bureaucratic complexity of the system, and the mixed effectiveness of implementation across different regions. The practices under the EUTRS often involved significant variations in the treatment and processing of migrants depending on their nationality and specific circumstances.

Those legal practitioners and lawyers have also emphasised the pushback practices as a significant issue, which often involve the use of force and intimidation, and there are documented cases of severe mistreatment of migrants at the borders. It is reported that there have been systemic pushbacks from both Bulgaria and Greece, with varying practices observed, including the involvement of third-country nationals in executing pushbacks in Greece and direct military involvement in Bulgaria.

For the prospects regarding the EUTRA and EUTRS, the research showed that Turkey has been developing its border management and taking the necessary measures to prevent the opening of any new sea or land routes for irregular migration from Turkey to the EU, such as the re-introduction of visa requirements for those Syrians travelling to Turkey by air and sea from a third country in 2016.²⁰⁴ However, despite increased measures at the borders, there has been a steady decrease in irregular border crossings due to domestic and foreign policy developments, such as the Taliban's takeover in 2021 and the completion of border walls at the Syrian and Iranian borders as of September 2023.

As can be seen, the research highlights the complexity of readmissions and showcases how readmission tools are interpreted and instrumentalised by the EU and Turkey, and how differentiated integration has become the norm in the EU's return policy. It has shed much-needed light on TCs' strategies to resist EU externalisation efforts, particularly their cost-benefit calculations in engagement with the EU on returns and readmissions.

The research indicates that Turkey has leveraged conditionality in its favour, rather than being a passive policy recipient. Since the Syrian mass migration, it has deployed migration as a foreign policy tool to accomplish various objectives. This was apparent in negotiations over the EUTRA in 2013, but by the time of the EUTRS in 2016, Turkey had expanded its demands. The EUTRS noted that this temporary and extraordinary measure, or purportedly 'exceptional' readmission strategy, has become the new norm, particularly after the EU Pact. Despite its failures, the EUTRS has served as a blueprint for other countries, and the EU Pact confirms expectations regarding similar bilateral cooperation with non-European countries going forward.

The EUTRA and the subsequent EUTRS represent pivotal moments in the externalisation of EU migration policy. Despite their significant aims, the practical outcomes and operational

²⁰⁴ Ovacık, G. et al., *Ibid.* 2024.

challenges highlight the complexities and limitations inherent in these agreements. The suspension of the readmission components of these agreements by Turkey since 2020 has led to a critical shift in migration dynamics in the region. Greece, facing substantial migrant accumulation at its borders, has resorted to informal pushback practices, which, although not legally sanctioned, illustrate the tensions and practical difficulties in managing migration flows. Turkey's response to these pushbacks has been characterised by actions that could be termed 'pushforward-through', where individuals are expelled and facilitated back towards Greece. This term captures the reciprocal and escalatory nature of border enforcement tactics between these two nations.

The findings underscore the complexities and political sensitivities surrounding the EUTRS and EUTRA. The evolving nature of EU-Turkey migration cooperation highlights the need for more balanced and comprehensive approaches that address immediate migration management needs and the underlying causes of displacement. Future agreements must reconcile the practicalities of border control with the imperatives of human rights and sustainable development, ensuring that policies are effective, ethical, and just. The EU's shift towards informalisation and differentiated externalisation must be carefully managed to avoid undermining the broader goals of stability, security, and respect for international law.

This case study enhances our understanding of readmission arrangements and externalisation policies by showcasing Turkey's strategic use of conditionality and leveraging its geopolitical position in EU negotiations. Future research should examine the evolving EU-Turkey migration dynamics, the long-term effects of informal readmission agreements, and the roles of other non-EU countries in similar externalisation agreements to gain broader insights into global migration governance.

6. Conclusion

This report has examined Turkey's return migration infrastructure (RMI), with a particular focus on push-forward strategies at the Turkey-Greece and Turkey-Bulgaria borders, as well as readmissions under the EUTRS (2016). By analysing return movements from Europe to Europe, the study highlights how Turkish authorities manage migrant mobility through indirect means, including incentives for onward movement toward Greece and Bulgaria, as well as readmission agreements or similar political statements. The findings reveal a complex interplay of formal and informal mechanisms, state and non-state actors, and geopolitical dynamics that shape Turkey's migration governance.

Turkey's return migration infrastructure occupies a highly strategic yet deeply contested position within Europe's broader migration governance framework. As this report illustrates, Turkey is not only a transit country but also an integral part of Europe's externalised border regime, managing return operations under bilateral and multilateral agreements. The implementation of the EUTRS, the dynamics of pushbacks, pushforwards, and readmission procedures, and the evolving legal and institutional landscape reveal a migration control system that is both structured and fragmented, coercive and adaptive.

The practice of pushbacks from Greece and Bulgaria to Turkey has been extensively documented, but this report also highlights the emerging role of pushforwards as an integral mechanism of return infrastructure. Particularly since 2020, the Turkish state has used legal, procedural, and logistical incentives to channel irregular migrants toward the Greek and Bulgarian borders, either by restricting their mobility within Turkey or by facilitating their transit toward border areas such as Pazarkule and Kırklareli. The pushforward mechanism

demonstrates a strategic adaptation by Turkey, functioning both as a negotiation tool with the EU and as a means of reducing the presence of unwanted migrant populations within Turkey's major cities, particularly Istanbul.

One of the most critical findings is that return governance in Turkey is not a static policy field but a dynamic and multi-scalar assemblage, reflecting shifting political priorities and evolving bilateral and multilateral agreements along with the below-given highlighted ones:

Key Findings

1. Pushforward Practices as a Strategic Response
 - Pushforwards have emerged as an alternative to formal return mechanisms, particularly in Edirne and Kırklareli, where Turkish authorities facilitate migrant movement toward EU borders. These practices involve a mix of active facilitation (e.g., relaxed border controls, logistical support) and selective non-enforcement, often in response to Greece's pushbacks.
 - The Pazarkule Events (2020) exemplified this strategy, with Turkish security forces, local smugglers, and village intermediaries collaborating to redirect migrants. This multi-actor infrastructure underscores the blurred lines between state and non-state involvement in migration control.
2. The EU-Turkey Statement and Its Limitations
 - The EUTRS, designed to facilitate returns from Greece to Turkey, operated primarily between 2016 and 2020. However, its implementation was sporadic and politically selective.
 - The centralised and opaque structure of EUTRS readmissions, overseen by the PMM and the MoFA, limited the autonomy of PDMMs and excluded international organisations, such as UNHCR and IOM, from monitoring, as well as NGOs.
3. Geopolitical and Policy Implications
 - Turkey's return migration strategies align with EU externalisation policies, emphasising deterrence and onward movement over structured legal mechanisms. However, the reliance on informal actors and smuggling networks raises concerns about sustainability and human rights violations.
 - The discretionary nature of Turkey's enforcement system creates a dual reality: some migrants are informally encouraged to leave, while others are detained and processed under readmission agreements.

Those findings of this report underscore the need for a critical reassessment of both Turkish and EU return migration policies. In light of the research, several crucial policy recommendations can be mentioned:

1. Enhancing Transparency and Accountability
 - Improve documentation and data-sharing mechanisms between provincial and national authorities to ensure oversight.
 - Establish independent monitoring bodies to assess compliance with international human rights standards.
2. Addressing Legal and Human Rights Gaps
 - Clarify the legal status of return practices to ensure compliance with the principle of non-refoulement.
 - Guarantee access to asylum procedures and legal representation for all migrants, regardless of their mode of entry.
3. Re-evaluating the EU-Turkey Readmission Framework (including the EUTRS-type political agreements)

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- Revise the EUTRA and EUTRS to incorporate transparent, rights-based procedures and equitable burden-sharing between Turkey and the EU.
 - Expand the role of international organisations in monitoring returns to ensure adherence to humanitarian principles and standards.
4. Balancing Security and Humanitarian Concerns
- Develop integration policies for migrants who cannot be returned, reducing reliance on deterrence-based measures.
 - Address root causes of irregular migration through regional cooperation and development initiatives.

A combination of formal agreements and informal, coercive practices shapes Turkey's return migration infrastructure. Pushforward strategies in Edirne and readmissions under the EUTRS illustrate the tension between migration control and human rights obligations. While these mechanisms serve short-term geopolitical and economic interests, their long-term sustainability is questionable. Addressing these challenges requires a holistic approach that prioritises legal safeguards, transparency, and international cooperation over reactive enforcement measures.

The findings of this report underscore the need for further research on the lived experiences of migrants subjected to these practices, as well as the evolving role of non-state actors in the governance of migration. Only by bridging the gap between policy and practice can Turkey and the EU develop effective and humane migration management systems, including returns.

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8. Annexes

8.1. Annex 1

EK-1: KOLAYLAŞTIRILMIŞ ÇIKIŞ FORMU

..... GÜMRÜK MÜDÜRLÜĞÜ

.../.../2024

Sayı: 2024/...

1- Çıkış Yapan Kişiyeye İlişkin Bilgiler

Adı Soyadı	Pasaport No/Tanıtım Kartı No	Gönüllü Geri Dönüş Talep Formu/ Yol İzin Belgesi (Var/Yok)	Açıklamalar (Ek bilgi / Sunulan belgeler / Ön izinler)

2- Araca İlişkin Bilgiler

Araç Modeli-Yılı	Araç Sahibi	Plaka No	Şase No	Motor No	Araçın Tescil Düşümü (Yapıldı/Yapılmadı)

3- Çıkış Yapacak Kişinin Beraberinde Götüreceği Eşyaya İlişkin Bilgiler

	Eşyayı belirten özellikler (Model-sayı vb.)	Tahmini (Yaklaşık) Kıymet (TL)
Ev Eşyası		
Mesleklerin icrası için beraberinde götürdüğü aletler ve takımlar		
Diğer (Belirtiniz)		

Bu belgede yer alan bilgilerin doğru olduğunu beyan ve taahhüt ederim.

Beyan sahibinin adı, soyadı ve imzası

Onaylayan gümrük personelinin adı, soyadı ve imzası

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